

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute

Volume 5: No. (2), June, 2022

President of the Journal : Prof. Dr. Ahmed Abd El Mageed

Editor –in-Chief : Prof. Dr. Shaaban Abd-Rabou

Secretary of the Journal

Prof. Dr. Shaaban Abd-Rabou

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Noha H. Ahmed

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Editorial Board Abroad

Dr. Alvin M. Simmons, FRES

Research Entomologist
USDA, ARS, U.S. Vegetable Laboratory
2700 Savannah Highway
Charleston, SC 29414
USA

Prof. Dr. Dong Chu

College of Plant Health and Medicine
Qingdao Agricultural University
No. 700, Changcheng Road
Chengyang, Qingdao, Shandong 266109
CHINA

Dr. Doo-Sang Park,

Korean Collection for Type Cultures (KCTC),
Microbiological Resource Center,
Korea Research Institute of Bioscience & Biotechnology (KRIBB), 125 Gwahangno,
Yuseong, Daejeon 305-806,
SOUTH KOREA

Dr. Gregory A. Evans

USDA/ APHIS/ PPQ c/o Systematic Entomology Laboratory
Bldg 005, Room 137,
BARC-WEST 10300 Baltimore Ave.
Beltsville, MD 20705
USA

Prof. Dr. Hassan Ghahari
Department of Entomology
Science & Research Campus
Islamic Azad University
Poonak – Hesarak
Tehran
IRAN

Dr. HDR. Helene Delatte
UMR "Peuplements Vgtaux et Bio-agresseurs en Milieu Tropical"
CIRAD-3P 7, Chemin de l'IRAT
Ligne Paradis
97410 Saint Pierre
La Runion
FRANCE

Egyptian Editorial Board

Prof. Dr. Mohamed Ibrahim Abdel Mageed
University of Ain Shames
Faculty of Agriculture,
Cairo,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mohamed Gomaa Abbass
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Aly Soliman
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Aly H. El-Sherbiny
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Eman Radwan
Central Agricultural Pesticides Laboratory,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Magdy Welson
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mahmoud El-Naggar
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mohammad Hendi
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute *is* an official journal of the Plant Protection Research Institute, *Agricultural* Research Center. It includes original research papers on basic and applied research in all aspects of plant protection. In additions to original research papers, also published reviews and scientific notes or short communications on critical issues relevant to plant protection. Subject areas include, but are not restricted to the following fields: Field pests, vegetable, aromatic, medicinal and ornamental plant pests, orchard pests, locust and grasshopper, beekeeping sericulture, spray technology, alternatives methods of control pests, survey and classification of agriculture pests and new biocontrol technology pests

Abbreviation of the Journal: Egypt. J. of Plant Prot. Res. Inst.`

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute
Volume 5: No. (2), June, 2022

Contents

- 1- **Ghada, E. Abd-Allah and Walaa, H. Ahmed (2022):** Effect of host plant difference on the biology and life table parameters of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (2): 123–128. **123 –128**
- 2- **Ogwulumba, S.I.; Isuk, E.J.; Okon, D. N. and Ariri, F.C. (2022):** Effect of poultry manure mixed at different rates of jatropha leaf powder on root-knot nematode (*Meloidogyne* spp.) infecting onion (*Allium cepa* L.) in Ishiagu, Southeast, Nigeria. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (2): 129–138. **129–138**
- 3- **Zienab, A. E. Hassanein (2022):** Efficiency of some essential oils on *Ascosphaera apis* the pathogen chalkbrood disease Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (2): 139–142. **139–142**
- 4- **Hamid, Sakenin; Reijo, Jussila; Najmeh, Samin and Balakrishnan, M. Manjusha (2022):**A faunistic study on Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) in North West of Iran. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (2): 143–148. **143–148**
- 5- **Manar, Y. Amin; Abeer, O. Abotaleb and Refaat, A. Mohamed (2022):** Susceptibility of different life stages of *Callosobruchus maculatus* and *Callosobruchus chinensis* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae :Bruchidae) to ECO₂FUME gas and its impact on cowpea seeds quality. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (2): 149–164. **149–164**
- 6- **Aisha, Anas El Mosalami; Abdel-Sattar, Mohammed Metwally; Awad, Ali Abdallah and Mohamed, Abdel-Hady (2022):** Occurrence of mites associated with stored products in some localities in Egypt. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (2): 165–172. **165–172**
- 7- **Hoda, M. Refai; Sherif, M. El- Safty; Mohammed, Abd El-Aziz and Mahmoud, M. Ghuniem (2022):** Occurrences and risk assessment of pesticide residue in tea in Egypt. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (2): 173–183. **173–183**
- 8- **Sherif, A. S. F; Marwa, B. M. Gomaa and Konper, H. M. A. (2022):** Royal jelly quantity means (Mg/Cups) under different diets and bars level within two successive years. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022) , 5 (2): 184–191. **184–191**
- 9- **Abo-Hashem, A.A.; Nadia, M. M. and Fatma, K. Khidr (2022):** Estimation of damage and losses caused by different species of snails on certain crops at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022) , 5 (2): 192–197. **192–197**

Continued

- 10- Tarek, A. Abd El Rahman and Asmaa, A. Eissa (2022): 198-206**
Statistical study to investigate the effect of climate fluctuations and contamination of bee products with pesticides on the change in beekeeping in Gharbia Governorate, Egypt. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (2): 198–206.
- 11- Bashandy, A. S. and Awwad, M. H. (2022): 207–214**
An examination of palatableness of some leaf plants utilizing two terrestrial snails in Egypt. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (2): 207–214.

Effect of host plant difference on the biology and life table parameters of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

Ghada, E. Abd-Allah¹ and Walaa, H. Ahmed²

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

²Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, For Girls, Cairo, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 3 / 4 / 2022

Accepted: 13 / 6 / 2022

Keywords

Spodoptera spp.,
castor plant, onion
plant, pepper plant, and
life table.

Abstract:

The biological aspects and life table of larvae of the cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) were studied under laboratory conditions on the leaves of three plant hosts, castor, onion, and pepper. The study revealed that onion leaves are not favourable for *S. littoralis* so larvae feeding on onion leaves could not complete the whole life cycle, but could complete the total larval instars only. While, both pepper leaves and castor leaves (Control) *S. littoralis* complete their life cycles and life span. It is worth noting that the total larval stage of *S. littoralis* feeding on castor leaves (Control) was recorded at 35.6 days while the total larval stage on onion leaves was decreased than control and recorded at 34.6 days, but the total larval stage on pepper leaves was higher than control and recorded 37.9 days. The incubation period, life cycle and generations periods for larvae fed on castor leaves were higher than larvae fed on pepper leaves that recorded 6.7, 60, and 63.3 days, respectively, on castor leaves and 9, 72.2, and 77.5 days, respectively, on pepper leaves. The longevity and life span of both female and male was lower on castor leaves than on pepper leaves. The longevity of females and males was 13.6 and 6.3 days, respectively, for castor leaves, and 20.7 and 10 days, respectively, for pepper leaves. Also, the life span of females and males was 73.6 and 66.3 days, respectively, on castor leaves; and 92.9 and 82.2 days, respectively, on pepper leaves. Also, the results showed that the daily mean number of deposit eggs was higher on castor leaves (32.4) than on pepper leaves (21.4). Also, the results demonstrated that *S. littoralis* had a capacity to multiply about 1.91 and 1.55 on castor and pepper leaves, respectively. So, castor leaves are a more suitable host plant for *S. littoralis* than onion or pepper hosts.

Introduction

Sweet pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) is a very important crop for both the local and export markets (Shehata *et al.*, 2013). It is known for its antioxidant properties as it is a good source of vitamins A and C as well as

phenolic compounds (Shotorbani *et al.*, 2013). Also, it is believed to prevent certain types of cardiovascular diseases, cancer, atherosclerosis, and hemorrhage (Marin *et al.*, 2004).

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is one of the most important commercial

vegetable crops that are grown in India and used as spices, vegetables, or medicines. The genus *Allium* also contains a number of other species such as the Japanese bunching onion (*Allium fistulosum*), Egyptian onion (*Allium proliferum*), and Canada onion (*Allium canadense*). There are over 600 species of *Allium*, distributed throughout Asia, Europe, North America, and Northern Africa. The bulb and leaves are rich in minerals like calcium, carbohydrate, and phosphorous. Also, it contains proteins and vitamin C (Slimestad *et al.*, 2007).

The cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is one of the most destructive lepidopterous pests in Egypt (Azab *et al.*, 2001). The effect of larval diet on the biology of the pest has been studied by many authors, Badr (1967) and Patel *et al.* (1968). Moussa *et al.* (1960) indicated that *S. littoralis* feeds on approximately 112 plant species belonging to 44 families. Some authors namely, Rizk *et al.* (1988) and Adham *et al.* (2009) mentioned the biology of *S. littoralis* and the effect of different hosts on the development and reproductive capacity. Also, Velasco and Walter (1993) reported that the survival of insects and larvae in the growth and reproductive phase were highly affected by food and quality.

The present study aimed to evaluate the effect of pepper leaves and onion leaves on the biology and life table of *S. littoralis* as methods of control.

Materials and methods

1. Rearing insect:

A laboratory strain of cotton leaf worm, *S. littoralis* (Maintained for above 30 generations) supplied from the division of the cotton leafworm of Plant Protection Research Institute (PPRI), Dokki, Egypt. First larval stages were reared on unsprayed pepper and onion leaves and compared with

castor leaves (As control) in the laboratory under constant conditions of 27 ± 2 °C, photoperiod of 14L:10D, and $65 \pm 5\%$ RH.

2. Application method:

The experiment was conducted as follows: The first instar larvae of *S. littoralis* were reared on onion leaves, pepper leaves, and castor leaves (As control), and the biology was followed. After the emergence of an adult female, as the result of nutritional difference and separation of one female in each replicate for each kind of food, the daily number of eggs laid was evaluated and counted carefully for life table calculation.

3. Statistical analysis:

L.S.D. values were calculated by Costat program (Costat software, 1990) and life table results were analyzed by the life table program (Abou-Setta *et al.*, 1986).

Results and discussion

1. Effect of food difference on the biology of *Spodoptera littoralis* :

The results in Table (1) indicated that 1st instar larvae reared on onion leaves, could not complete the life cycle, it completes the larval stage only that was less than larvae reared on pepper leaves and castor leaves and recorded 34.6, 37.9, and 35.6 for onion leaves, pepper leaves and castor leaves, respectively. CABI (2014) listed the main hosts' crops of *S. littoralis* in Europe, *Allium* spp. (Onion) was one of these hosts. Al-Shannaf (2011) indicated that pepper was one of the main hosts of *S. littoralis*. The incubation period, total larval stages, and total life cycle of *S. littoralis* increased with the pepper host plant than with the castor plant. The incubation period was 9 and 6.7 days on pepper and castor plants, respectively, and this increase was significant. Also, the total life cycle of *S. littoralis* on the pepper host plant was higher than the castor plant, respectively, which was

72.2 and 60 days for pepper and castor, respectively.

Table (1): Effect of different plant hosts on the life cycle of *Spodoptera littoralis* at 65± 5% RH.

Host plant	Incubation period	Average period of different developmental larval instars (in days)						Total larval stage	Pre-pupa	pupa	Life cycle
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th				
Pepper leaves	9± 0.5	6.3± 0.6	7.7± 1.7	8.3± 0.8	5± 0.9	5.3± 0.6	5.3± 0.6	37.9± 0.5	5.3± 0.6	20± 0.5	72.2± 1.5
Onion leaves	9± 0.5	7.7± 0.8	5.7± 0.3	4.3± 0.8	4.3± 0.3	6.3± 1.2	6.3± 0.8	34.6± 0.5			
Castor leaves	6.7± 0.3	8.3± 0.6	5± 0.5	5.3± 0.3	4± 0.5	4± 0.5	9± 0.5	35.6± 0.8	4± 0.5	13.7± 0.6	60± 1.1
L. S.D. at 0.05	0.67							0.11		0.66	0.09

Data in **Table (2)** demonstrated that female generation and female and male longevity increased significantly with pepper host plant than with castor plant. The female generation was 77.5 and 63.3 days with pepper and castor plants, respectively, while the female longevity was 20.7 and 13.6 days for pepper and castor plants, respectively. Male longevity was 10 and 6.3 days for pepper and castor plants, respectively.

The life span of *S. littoralis* in females and males decreased with the castor plant than with a pepper host plant and this decrease was significant

Table (2): Effect of different feeding on longevity and life span of both males and females of *Spodoptera littoralis* at 65± 5% RH.

Food	Duration of different adult stages (In days)						
	Female					Male	
	Pre-oviposition	Generation	Post-oviposition	Longevity	Life span	Longevity	Life span
Pepper leaves	5.3± 0.3	77.5± 1.4	3.7± 0.3	20.7± 0.6	92.9± 4.6	10± 0.4	82.2± 1.8
Castor leaves	3.3± 0.3	63.3± 0.9	2.3± 0.3	13.6± 0.5	73.6± 4.4	6.3± 0.3	66.3± 1.3
L. S.D. at 0.05		0.13		0.13	0.13	0.93	0.13

Data in **Table (3)** demonstrated that the oviposition period decreased significantly with the castor host plant than with the pepper plant which was 8 and 11.7 days for castor and pepper plants, respectively. The total average of eggs was lower with the pepper host plant than the castor plant, so, the daily mean of deposit eggs was lower with

which were 73.6 days with castor and 92.9 days with a pepper host plant of female, while it was 66.3 and 82.2 days with castor and pepper host plants of male, respectively. These results contrasted with Al-Shannaf (2011) who studied the effect of thirteen host plants on food consumption and some biological aspects for larvae of *S. littoralis* and indicated that larvae fed on pepper leaves had a shorter life span than larvae fed on castor leaves. The results revealed that castor plants were more suitable host plants than pepper plants.

the pepper host plant than the castor plant which was 32.4 eggs on castor plants and 21.4 eggs on pepper plants. Although the oviposition period was lower on castor than on pepper, the daily mean number of deposit eggs was higher on castor than on pepper plants. These results were in agreement with Al-Shannaf (2011) that proved that female

moths produced from larvae fed on castor bean oil leaves laid the highest number of eggs 2171 eggs; but pepper produced the least number 790 eggs, respectively.

Table (3): Effect of different temperatures on the oviposition period and fecundity of females of *Spodoptera littoralis* at 65 ± 5% RH.

Temperature °C	Oviposition period (In days)	Number of deposited eggs	
		Total average	Daily mean
Pepper leaves	11.7± 0.3	249.8± 0.6	21.4
Castor leaves	8± 0.5	259.1± 1.2	32.4
L. S.D. at 0.05	0.93		

2. Life table parameters:

The calculated life table parameters which have been taken into consideration in the present study were generation (T), net reproduction rate (R_o), intrinsic (r_m), finite rate of increase (λ), and generation doubling time (G.D.T.), all these data present in Table (4). The net reproduction rate (R_o) was 114870 and 73290 days within a single generation on leaves of the castor and pepper, respectively. The duration of one generation of *S. littoralis* as shown in the same table lasted about 65.82 and 77.51 days on leaves of the castor and pepper, respectively. The value of the intrinsic rate of increase (r_m) which expresses the relationship between fecundity, generation time, and survival differed from one host plant to another. Castor leaves have a higher value of r_m than pepper leaves. The higher value of (r_m) is attributed to a greater rate of fecundity per female (R_o) and shorter generation time (r_m = log R_o /T) at the

favourable host than the other. However, when the values of the r_m were converted to the finite rate of increase (λ) by the procedure outlined it is clear that the population of *S. littoralis* had a capacity to multiply about 1.19 and 1.55 on castor and pepper leaves, respectively. The generation doubling time (G.D.T.) has values of 7.99 and 9.75 the castor leaves have a higher result than pepper leaves.

Similar results on the life table of *S. littoralis* were in harmony with El-Sayed *et al.* (1973) and Mohamed (2003), which proved that female moths prefer egg laying on the same host plant. Also, Al-Shannaf (2011) proved that *S. littoralis* female moths produced from larvae fed on castor bean oil leaf, laid the highest number of eggs 2171.8 and 2139.6 eggs; but pepper leaves produced the least number, 790.6 and 778.1 eggs, in two generations, respectively.

Table (4): Effect of host difference on life table parameters of *Spodoptera littoralis* female

Parameters	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i> fed on castor leaves	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i> fed on pepper Leaves
Net reproduction rate (R _o)	114870	73290
Mean generation time (T)	65.82	77.51
Intrinsic rate of increase (r _m)	0.177	0.145
Finite rate of increase (λ)	1.19	1.55
Generation doubling time (G.D.T.) (days)*	7.99	9.75

References

Abou-Setta, M.M.; Sorrel R. W. and Childers, C. C. (1986): Life 48: ABASIC computer program

to calculate life table parameters for an insect or mite species. Florida Entomology, 69 (4): 690- 697.

- Adham, F. K.; Rashad, E. M.; Shouky, C.F. and Enas, E. N. (2009):** Host plants shifting affects the biology, and biochemistry of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). J. Biol. Sci., 2 (1): 63 – 71.
- Al-Shannaf, H. M. H. (2011):** Estimated food consumption and feeding effect with different host plants on the development and reproductive capacity of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: noctuidae). Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 4 (2): 1-8
- Azab, S.G.; Sadek, M.M. and Crailsheim, K. (2001):** Protein metabolism in larvae of the cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis*, (Lepidoptera = Noctuidae), and its response to three mycotoxins. J. Econ. Entomol., 30(5): 817 – 823.
- Badr, N.A. (1967):** Effect of different host plants on the development and reproduction of the cotton leafworm, *Prodenia litura* F., M.Sc. Thesis, Alexandria University.
- CABI (2014):** CAB INTERNATIONAL: Crop protection compendium. Datasheet on *Spodoptera littoralis*.
- Costat software (1990):** Microcomputer program analysis, version 4. 20, CoHort Software, Berkely, CA, USA.
- El-Sayed, A. N.; El- Rafiei, K.; Hosny, M.M. and Badawi, A. (1973):** Effect of host plants on the biology of the cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Bull. Soc. Ent. Egypt, 57: 27-32.
- Marin, A.; Ferreres, F.; Tomas-Barberan, F. and Gil, M.I. (2004):** Characterization and quantitation of antioxidant constituents of sweet pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.). J. Agric. Food Chem., 52: 3861-3869.
- Mohamed, H.H. (2003):** Comparative study of host plants on growth, development and fecundity of the cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). J. Egypt. Ger. Soc. Zool., 42(E):167-183.
- Moussa, M.A.; Zaher, M.A. and Kotby, F. (1960):** Abundance of the cotton leafworm, *Prodenia litura* F. in relation on host plants. L. Host plants and their effect on biology. Bull. Soc. Ent. Egypte, 44: 241-251.
- Patel, H.L.; Patel, R.M. and Patel, V.C. (1968):** Effect of food and temperature on the durations of various stages of tobacco leaf-eating caterpillar, *Prodenia litura* F. India. Tob., 15 (4): 174 – 176.
- Rizk, G.A; Hussein, S.M. and Hafez, H.F. (1988):** Studies on biotic potential of the cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) with special reference to the effect of host plants on larval susceptibility to synthetic pyrethroids. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, Econ. Ser., 17: 47 – 55.
- Shehata, S.A.; Ibrahim, M.I.A.; El-Mogy, M.M. and El-Gawad, K.F.A. (2013):** Effect of hot water dips and modified atmosphere packaging on extending the shelf life of bell pepper fruits. Wulfenia J., 20(3): 315-328.
- Shotorbani, N.M.; Jamei, R. and Heidari, R. (2013):** Antioxidant activities of two sweet pepper *Capsicum annuum* L. varieties phenolic extracts

and the effects of thermal treatment. Avicenna J. Phytomedicine, 3(1): 25-34.

Slimestad, R.; Fossen T. and Vagen, I.M. (2007): Onions: A source of unique dietary flavonoids. J Agric. Food Chem., 55(25):10067-10080.

Velasco, L.R. and Walter, G.H. (1993): Potential of host

switching in *Nezara viridula* (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) to enhance survival and reproduction. Environ. Entomol., 22(2): 326-333.

Effect of poultry manure mixed at different rates of jatropha leaf powder on root-knot nematode (*Meloidogyne* spp.) infecting onion (*Allium cepa* L.) in Ishiagu, Southeast, Nigeria

Ogwulumba, S.I.; Isuk, E.J.; Okon, D. N. and Ariri, F.C.

Department of Crop Production Technology, Federal College of Agriculture Ishiagu, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 5 / 4 / 2022

Accepted: 26 / 5 / 2022

Keywords

Infection, control options, reduction, growth, yield, and integration.

Abstract:

Costly and sometimes very harmful chemical pesticides to humans and the environment are the main means of combating root-knot nematodes available to farmers in Ishiagu, southeastern Nigeria, and elsewhere. The uses of animals and plants waste give positive results in sustainable control programs. This study assessed the effect of poultry fertilizer mixed with different levels of jatropha leaves in controlling the infection of root node nematodes on onions at the Research and Teaching farm of the Federal College of Agriculture Ishiagu, Ebonyi State, Nigeria in 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons. The treatments used were: 10 t/ha of poultry manure (PM) + 5 t/ha of Jatropha leaf powder (JLP), 10 t/ha of PM + 10 t/ha of JLP, 10 t/ha of PM + 15 t/ha of JLP, 10 t/ha of PM and Carbofuran (Control) at 100g/ plot. Experiments were designed in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) and replicated three times. Data were taken on growth measurement indicators (Plant height and number of leaves), crop characteristics (Number of bulbs and weight of bulbs at harvest), and characteristics of nematodes infection (Number of galled roots and root gall index at harvest). Treatments significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced root galling and gall index with the application of 10 t/ha PM + 15 t/ha JLP with a significant increase in growth and yield parameters of onion. Since 10t/ha of PM + 15t/ha of JLP significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced nematode infection and promoted the growth and yield of onion, farmers in Ishiagu community are therefore advised to adopt this manure integration.

Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) also known as the bulb onion or common onion belongs to the family of *Alliaceae*. It is a vegetable that is the most widely cultivated species of the

genus *Allium* (Ndon *et al.*, 2015). Onion is grown in many tropical countries, including Ghana and Nigeria, but the production in Nigeria is concentrated in the northern states.

Onion can be planted at any season of the year, but it is mostly a warm-weather loving crop. Best results have been reported when grown through irrigation. Survey showed that drip irrigation system performed superior over surface irrigation on onion according to Begali *et al.* (2015). Onion is normally propagated through seed. However, some farmers have been reported to propagate onion through the bulb or set. On cultivation, nursery practice management is the most important practice to produce healthy seedlings (Choudhary, 2018).

All the plant parts are edible but the bulb and the lower stem sections are the most popular as seasonings or as vegetables in stews. It can also be used as a condiment and extensively in flavouring of processed meat, spicing of various food preparations and also used for medicinal purposes (Alabi, 2014).

Effective production of onion is however hampered by action of nematode infections. Wide array of nematodes poses serious problems in the cultivation of onion, which have therefore caused tremendous setbacks in the production of this important vegetable crop (Ellis, 2016 and Mbaukwu *et al.*, 2016). Parasitic nematodes, especially the root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) are the most destructive parasitic nematode pests hampering world agricultural production in general and vegetable production in particular (Taylor *et al.*, 2016). *Meloidogyne* species pose significant threats to crop production especially in Africa and other developing countries and account for the huge losses in a wide range of agricultural crops.

Onion is one of the sensitive crops to root-knot nematodes. *Meloidogyne* species is an obligate parasite which is regarded as one of the most important parasitic genera (Crichley, 2011). Gowda *et al.* (2019)

reported that root-knot nematodes can cause 50 – 60 % loss in vegetable crops. The market value of most economic crops is drastically reduced as a result of root-knot nematode attacks resulting in disfiguring quality of the crop produce, including onion. Nematodes are difficult to control because of their wide host range and high rate of reproduction, with the female capable of reproducing up to thousand eggs per female (Netarajan *et al.*, 2016).

To protect the crops from pest attacks, farmers usually rely on quick pest management options, mainly synthetic chemicals like carbofuran. Despite the efficacious attribute of synthetic pesticides, continuous usage has its challenges such as development of pesticide resistant pests. Overuse and misuse of synthetic pesticide can result in harmful effects on humans and the environment and toxicity to non-target organisms, thus impacting negatively on biodiversity (Geraldin *et al.*, 2020). Constituent compounds of synthetic pesticides have been attributed to chronic human ailments either due to consumption or exposure. Most of the synthetic pesticides are not easily biodegradable thus accumulate in the environment and cause pollution to soil and ground water in addition to depletion of the ozone layer.

One of the alternatives to the use of chemical pesticides in controlling pests and improving soil fertility as well is the use of organic or botanical materials. Soil amendment using organic or botanical manure sources have been reported to reduce nematodes infections and population, increase growth and yield through the release of nutrients into the soil (Ogwulumba and Mba, 2016). The use of organic manure especially poultry manure is preferred in this regard because it can provide a sustainable and environmentally acceptable soil management at little or no direct cost to the poor farmers in

developing countries, who cannot afford costly imported chemical pesticides. The use of organic materials for soil amendments do not only control nematodes population but also add nutrients to the soil thereby enhancing yield. Poultry manure supplies other essential plant nutrients and serves as a source of soil organic matter that improves soil properties and nutrient retention (Mijindadi and Erhabor 2016 and Ogwulumba and Mba, 2016). Although poultry manure is common in most localities, its nematicidal properties have not been fully exploited by vegetable farmers (Mcsorley *et al.*, 2014).

Jatropha curcas L., a member of the family Euphorbiaceae, is a large drought-resistant multipurpose shrub with several attributes and considerable potential and has evoked interests all over the tropics as a potential bio-fuel crop (Takeda, 1982; Martin and Mayeux, 1984 and 1985 and Jones and Miller, 1991). The leaves, latex, roots and seed oil have medicinal, insecticidal and nematicidal properties (Aminul-Islam *et al.*, 2011).

The main aim of the study is to determine or evaluate the effectiveness of poultry manure amended with different levels of *Jatropha* leaves in the management of root-knot nematodes infecting onion.

Materials and methods

The experiment was carried out at the Research and Teaching farm of the Federal College of Agriculture Ishiagu, Ebonyi State, Nigeria in 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons. Ishiagu is located in the derived savannah zone of the South Eastern Nigeria and lies within latitude 05° 56' N and longitude 07° 41' E. It has mean annual rainfall and temperature of 1350 mm and 29°C, respectively.

1. Experimental materials:

Seeds of red onion variety were obtained from Ishiagu local market and

used for the experiment. Poultry manure was obtained from the battery cage of Federal College of Agriculture Ishiagu farm, while *Jatropha* leaves were sourced from Ishiagu community.

2. Experimental design and treatments:

2.1. Design:

Experiments were designed in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) and replicated three times that giving a total of fifteen plots with each plot measuring 2m by 2m.

2.2. Treatments:

The five treatments used in the experiments were:

Poultry manure 10 tons/ha amended with 5tons/ha, 10 tons/ha, 15 tons/ha of *Jatropha* leaves; 10 tons/ha of poultry manure only and Carbofuran, a synthetic nematicide used as the control.

2.2.1. Nursery preparation/transplanting:

Seedlings were raised in sterilized soil under a shade for three weeks before transplanting the vigorous and healthy ones to the field.

2.2.2. Land preparation:

The experimental site was cleared, ploughed and harrowed, marked out, and subsequently prepared into beds.

2.2.3. Preparation/application of treatments:

The *Jatropha* leaves were dried at room temperature and ground to powder and added to the well cured poultry manure at the stipulated levels accordingly. The treatments were randomly applied to the plots and worked into the soil using a garden fork three days before transplanting of the onion seedlings.

2.2.4. Plant spacing/ population:

A plant spacing of 50 cm by 50 cm was used, thereby giving a population of 16 plants per plot and 240 plants for the experiment. This would give 40,000 plants per hectare.

3. Data collection:

- i. Plant height (cm): This was determined by measuring the height of the plant from the base using a meter rule at 3, 6, and 9 weeks after planting.
- ii. Number of leaves: This was determined by counting the number of leaves per stand at 3, 6, and 9 weeks after planting.
- iii. Number of bulbs at harvest: This was determined by counting the number of bulbs per plot at harvest.
- iv. Weight (g) of bulbs at harvest: This was determined by weighing the bulbs according to plots at harvest using Camry digital weighing balance.
- v. Number of galled roots at harvest: This was determined by counting the number of roots with galls at harvest
- vi. Number of galls per root at harvest: This was determined by counting the number of galls on every root, scaled according to Ogwulumba and Okonta (2015) below:

Rate	Number of galls	Infection level
0	No galls	No infection
1	1 – 10	Mild
2	11 – 20	Moderate
3	21 – 30	Moderately high
4	31 – 40	High
5	41 – 50	Very high
6	51 and above	Severe

4. Data analysis:

Collected data were analyzed using analysis of variance according to

Table (1): Effect of poultry manure mixed with different levels of *Jatropha* leaves on plant height (cm) of onion plants at intervals of 3, 6, and 9 Weeks after planting during 2020 and 2021 growing seasons.

Treatment	3WAP		6WAP		9WAP	
	2020	2021	2020	2021 2020	2020	2021
PM at 10t/ha + JLP at 5t/ha	28.72	27.98	34.23ab	33.89b	37.18 b	37.56 b
PM at 10t/ha + JLP 10t/ha	31.81	32.01	37.33bc	38.12b	41.04 b	42.01b
PM at 10t/ha + JLP at 15 t/ha	40.11	39.76	49.84d	50.87d	54.34 c	55.01 c
PM at 10t/ha	26.23	25.78	30.52a	32.32b	34.06 b	33.98 ab
Carbofuran (Control)	20.37	21.32	25.93a	27.04a	29.19a	29.92 a
LSD (0.05)	NS	NS	5.22	5.07	7.15	5.76

Key: PM = poultry manure JLP = *Jatropha* leaf powder NS = Not significant

Results in Table (2) showed that there was no significant effect on the

the procedure for randomized complete block design (RCBD). Significant treatment means were separated and compared using Fisher’s Least Significant Difference (F- LSD) and all inferences were made at 5% level of probability according to Obi (2002).

Results and discussion

Data are shown in Table (1) reveal that there is not have any significant ($P>0.05$) effect on the plant height of onion at 3 weeks after planting (WAP). However, the treatments significantly ($P<0.05$) affected the plant height at 6 and 9 WAP. The highest plant height of 54.14 cm and 55.01cm respectively in 2020 and 2021 were obtained from the plots treated with 10 t/ha of poultry manure (PM) + 15 t/ha of *Jatropha* leaves (JLP), while the plants treated with carbofuran (control) gave the lowest plant height of 29.19 cm and 29.92 cm respectively at 9 WAP. lots treated with 10 t/ha of PM + 15 t/ha of JLP significantly differed from other treatments except 10 t/ha of PM + 10 t/ha of JLP at 6 and 9 W AP. Plots treated with 10 t/ha of PM + 10 t/ha of JLP did not differ significantly from 10 t/ha of PM + 5 t/ha of JLP, 10 t/ha of PM + 10 t/ha of JLP, and carbofuran.

number of leaves by the treatments at 3 WAP. The treatments significantly

affected the number of leaves produced by the plants at 6 and 9 WAP. The highest mean value of leaves of 9.51 and 9.92 respectively in 2020 and 2021 were recorded from plots treated with 10 t/ha of PM + 15 t/ha of JLP, while the lowest mean value of 5.12 and 5.33 were obtained from carbofuran at 9 WAP in 2020 and 2021 respectively. Plants

treated with 10 t/ha of PM + 15 t/ha of JLP significantly differed from other treatments at 6 and 9 W AP. Plants treated with 10 t/ha of PM + 10 t/ha of JLP did not differ significantly from that one's treated with 10 t/ha of PM + 5 t/ha of JLP, 10 t/ha of PM, and carbofuran at 6 and 9 WAP.

Table (2): Effect of poultry manure mixed with different levels of *Jatropha* leaves on onion plants leave number at intervals of 3, 6, and 9 Weeks after planting during 2020 and 2021 growing seasons.

Treatment	3WAP		6WAP		9WAP	
	2020	2021	2020	2021	2020	2021
PM at 10t/ha + JLP at 5t/ha	4.05	4.17	6.27c	6.09b	7.1b	7.25c
PM at 10t/ha + JLP 10t/ha	4.43	5.72	6.84c	7.01c	7.21bc	7.19bc
PM at 10t/ha + JLP at 15 t/ha	5.05	7.74	9.11d	9.42d	9.51d	9.92d
PM at 10t/ha	3.19	4.53	5.71b	5.91aba	6.1ab	6.43ab
Carbofuran (control)	3.81	4.11	4.28a	5.02 a	5.12a	5.33a
LSD (0.05)	NS	NS	1.16	1.22	1.38	1.41

Key: PM = poultry manure JLP = *Jatropha* leaf powder NS = Not significant

Results in Table (3) showed that there was a-significant effect on number of bulbs of onion by the treatments. There was enhanced yield on the plots treated with poultry manure at 10 t/ha amended with *Jatropha* at 15 t/ha, which gave the

highest mean value of 34.31, while plots treated with Carbofuran gave the lowest mean value of 12.04. 10 t/ha of PM + 15 t/ha of ILP significantly ($P < 0.05$) differed from other treatments.

Table (3): Effect of poultry manure mixed with different levels of *Jatropha* leaves on onion plants bulbs' number during 2020 and 2021 growing seasons.

Treatment	2020	2021
PM at 10t/ha + JLP at 5t/ha	18.17 bc	18.09bc
PM at 10t/ha + JLP 10t/ha	20.12 c	20.23c
PM at 10t/ha + JLP at 15 t/ha	34.31 c	35.21d
PM at 10t/ha	15.31 bc	15.41ab
Carbofuran (control)	12.04 a	12.14a
LSD (0.05)	5.19	5.21

Key: PM = poultry manure JLP = *Jatropha* leaf powder NS = Not significant

Results in Table (4) showed that there was a significant ($P < 0.05$) effect by the treatments on the weight of bulbs of onions at harvest. 10 t/ha of PM + 15 t/ha of JLP gave the highest mean value of 806

g and 809 g respectively in 2020 and 2021 while Carbofuran gave the lowest mean value of 273.3(g). The treatments were significantly ($P < 0.05$) differed from each other.

Table (4): Effect of poultry manure mixed with different levels of *Jatropha* leaves on onion plants weight bulbs (g) at intervals of 3, 6, and 9 Weeks after planting during 2020 and 2021 growing seasons.

Treatment	Weight (g)	
	2020	2021
PM at 10t/ha + JLP at 5t/ha	416 b	423 b
PM at 10t/ha + JLP 10t/ha	460b	471 b
PM at 10t/ha + JLP at 15 t/ha	806 c	819 c
PM at 10t/ha	300 a	297 a
Carbofuran (Control)	273 a	272 a
LSD (0.05)	50.16	51.01

Results in Table (5) showed that the treatments significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced the number of galled roots and galls per root at harvest. 10 t/ha of PM

+ 15 t/ha of JLP gave the highest reduction rate on both the number of galled roots and the number of galls per root respectively.

Table (5): Effect of poultry manure mixed with different levels of *Jatropha* leaves on galled roots and the number of galls per root of onion at harvest during 2020 and 2021 growing seasons.

Treatment	No. of galled roots		No. of galls/root	
	2020	2021	2020	2021
PM at 10t/ha + JLP at 15	28.33 b	27.13b	4.33 d	3.92 d
PM at 10t/ha + JLP 10t/ha	27.33 b	25.22 b	4.04 c	3.83 c
PM at 10t/ha + JLP at 15	8.67 a	6.32 a	2.03a	1.89 b
PM at 10t/ha	30.04 c	33.12 c	4.64 e	4.11 e
Carbofuran (control)	6.43 a	5.78 a	2.67 b	1.34 a
LSD (0.05)	2.35	2.41	0.21	0.18

Treatments did not show any effect on the plant heights or the number of leaves after three weeks from planting, but the effect was appeared after 6 and 9 weeks from planting. These results agree with Ayed (2002), who mentioned that the mixture had not decomposed well enough at 3 WAP for plant fertilization., to gives its effect on onion growth. The results also agreed with the works of Falodun and Peters (2019) which stated that there was a significant relationship amongst the treatments on growth parameters at 6, 8, and 10 WAP on onions. Michigan State University's report published in SFGATE Newsletter in 2020, mentioned that Organic fertilizers, take about 5 to 9 weeks to break down into the soil depending on the nature of the organic fertilizer.

Plots treated with poultry manure at 10 t/ha mixed with *Jatropha* at 15 t/ha produced significantly better leaves. This could be due to the high level of nutrients added to the soil due to high level of *Jatropha* leaves mixed with poultry droppings. The highest yield values was obtained with the treatment (PM at 10 t/ha + JLP at 15 t/ha) carbofuran (Control) gave the lowest yield mean values in each case because carbofuran contains only nematicidal properties while the decomposition of poultry and *Jatropha*

leaves added more nutrients to the soil for the plant absorption and utilization. These results are in line with Ehigiator *et al.* (2013), Sonbeer *et al.* (2017) and Falodun and Egharevba (2018) who reported that enhanced growth and yield attributes of onion, carrot, and beans were obtained due to the application of *Jatropha* leaves at 15 t/ha and poultry manure at 10 t/ha. Funda *et al.* (2019) found out that application of chicken manure significantly improved number of bulbs, bulb weight, bulb height, number of shoot tip, number of dried leaves of onion compared to control.

Using of poultry manure combined with *Jatropha* leaves showed a significant reduction on nematode infections on the crop (Onion). The mixture of poultry waste and *Jatropha* leaves works as a nematicidal pesticide, which reduces the incidence of infection. When this fertilizer mixture is used with in rate of 10 tons/hectare of poultry waste with 15 tons/hectares of *Jatropha* leaves, it led to a reduction in nematode numbers and enhancing growth and parameters returning to the crop. These results are in agreement with Ogwudire *et al.* (2019), who stated that root extracts of *Jatropha* was statistically significant on the control of *Meloidogyne incognita*. The results also agreed with Agu *et al.* (2013), whose

study indicated that root-gall nematode diseases of okra were significantly affected by *Jatropha curcas* and the consequent pod proximate composition were achieved. Poultry manure had been proven to have nematicidal properties in treatment of nematode infections, but combination (Amendment) with other organic/botanical manure sources such as *Jatropha* gives best results (Sonbeer *et al.*, 2017, Ehigiator *et al.*, 2013 and Falodun and Egharevba, 2018). Also, Ogwulumba and Mba (2016) found out that plant manure sources were effective in the control of root-knot nematode infections and boosting the yield of Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranean*) Another study by Ogwulumba *et al.* (2010) indicated that *Meloidogyne javanica* infections on Roma tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) could be controlled under different soil amendments. Poultry manure and *Jatropha* leaves are indicated to improve soil fertility status, soil organic matter, micro-nutrient status and micro-nutrient qualities of the soil (Maerere *et al.*, 2001; Adeniyi and Ojeniyi 2003; Akande and Adediran 2004). It also promotes the CEC of the soil (Akinrindi and Obigbesan, 2000). Ogwudire *et al.* (2019) found out that *Jatropha curcas* leaves contain phytochemicals such as alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids and tannins which have shown high mortality rate against the population of *Meoidogyne incognita*.

It is concluded that Based on the findings of this study, application of poultry manure at 10 t/ha mixed with *Jatropha* leaves at 15 t/ha significantly reduced the activities of root-knot nematodes attacking onion according to the enhancing of the growth and yield characteristics.

It is recommended that Application of poultry manure at 10 t/ha combined with *Jatropha* leaves at

15 t/ha as soil amendments significantly suppresses the activities of root-knot nematodes, improves growth and yield of onion. This is therefore recommended to onion farmers to mitigate the menace of root-knot nematodes in the farms.

References

- Adeniyi, N. O. and Ojeniyi, S. O. (2003):** Comparative and effectiveness of different levels of poultry manure with NPK fertilizer on residual soil fertility nutrient uptake and yield of maize. Moor Journal of Agric., 2: 191-197.
- Agu, C. M.; Nwobaga, A. C.; Uwaudu, C. G. and Peter-Oro, C. A. (2013):** Effects of *Jatropha curcas* on root-gall nematode diseases and the consequent proximate composition of okra (*Abelmonchus esculentus* L.) Moench. Retrieved from: <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Akande, M. O. and Adediran, J. A. (2004):** Effects of terralyt plus fertilizer on growth, nutrients uptake and dry matter yield of two vegetable crops. Moor J. of Agric. Res., 5:12 -18.
- Akinrindi, E. A. and Obigbesan, G. O. (2000):** Evaluation of the fertility status of selected soils for crop production in five ecological zones of Nigeria. Proceedings of 26th Annual Conference of Soil science Society of Nigeria, Ibadan pp. 279-286.
- Alabi, O. (2014):** Nutrient contents and storability of two tropical onions, *Allium cepa* L. cultivars under different storage structures. Proc. of 18th Horticultural Society of Nigeria Conference, IAR/ABU, Zaria. May 28-Jun 1.

- Aminul-Islam, A. K. M.; Yaakob, Z. and Anuar, N. (2011):** *Jatropha*: A multipurpose plant with considerable potential for the tropics. *Scientific Research and Essays*, 6(13): 2597- 2599.
- Ayed, A. (2002):** Effect of chicken manure, sheep manure and inorganic fertilizer on yield and nutrient uptake by onion. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences*, 5(2): 266-268.
- Begali, A. N.; Patil, H. B.; Guled, M. B. and Patil, R. V. (2015):** Effect of Scheduling of Drip Irrigation on Growth, Yield and Water Use Efficiency on Onion (*Allium cepa*). *Kanakata Journal of Agricultural Science*, 14(3): 116-120.
- Choudhary, D. R. (2018):** Scientific cultivation of Onion. in : *Phytochemistry of Fruits and Vegetables*. Dr. Peter, K. V. (Ed.) pp. 239-260. Brillion Publishing, New Delhi.
- Crichley, K. M. (2011):** Bio control potential of endophytic bacteria on *Meloidogyne* spp. and its effect on growth in Bhendi. *Journal of bio pesticides*, 3(4): 452-454.
- Ehigiator, J. O.; Falodun, E. J. and Egharevba, R. K. A. (2013):** Growth and yield on onion as influence by organic and inorganic fertilizer in Edo Rainforest of Nigeria. Dept. of Crop Science, University of Benin, Nig. Retrieved from: <https://www.ajol.info/indoor>.
- Ellis, M. E. (2016):** Root-Knot Nematode of Onion Plants – Controlling Onion Root-Knot Nematodes. Retrieved from: <https://www.gardeningknowhoh.comn>
- Falodun, E. J. and Egharevba, P. (2018):** Effect of different doses of *Jatropha* leaf extract on growth and development of french bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) and brinji (*Solanum melongena*). *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 6 (5): 2692-2705.
- Falodun, E. J. and Peters, K. (2019):** Influence of poultry manure rates and spacing on growth, yield, nutrients concentration, uptake, and proximate composition of onion (*Allium cepa*). Retrieved from: <https://www.notulaebiologicae.ro>.
- Funda, Y.; Sefak, L.; Ceylam, K. and Nilgum, S. M. (2019):** Retrieved from: www.researchgate.net
- Geraldin, M. W.; Lengai, E. and Mbega, R. (2020):** Phytochemical activity and role of botanical pesticides in pests management for sustainable agricultural crop production. *Scientific African*, 7 (5): 234-237.
- Gowda, M.; Sellaperumal, C.; Rai, A. B. and Singh, B. (2019):** (Indian Institute of Vegetable Research). Root-Knot nematodes menace in vegetable crops and their management in India: A Review. Retrieved from: www.researchgate.net
- Jones, N. and Miller, J. H. (1991):** *Jatropha curcas*: A multipurpose species for problematic sites. *Land Resources Series*, 1: 1-12.
- Maerere, A. P.; Kimbi, G. G. and Nonga, D. M. (2001):** Comparative Effectiveness of animal manures on soil chemical properties, yield and root growth of amaranthus (*Amaranthus cruentus* L.). *AJST*, 1:14-21.

- Martin, G. and Mayeux, A. (1984):** Reflections on oil crops as sources of energy: 2. curcas oil (*Jatropha curcas*): A possible Fuel. *Oleagineux*, 39(5): 283-287.
- Martin, G. and Mayeux, A. (1985):** Curcas oil (*Jatropha curcas* L.): A possible fuel. *Agric Trop.*, 9:73-75.
- Mbaukwu, O.; Ruffina, A. N. and Maureen, C. O. (2016):** Extraction and Identification of Plant Parasitic Nematode from Some Vegetable Crops Cultivated By Local Farmers in Abakiliki, Nigeria. Project: Studies on the proximate and mineral composition of leaves, stem and root of *Catharanthus Roseus* (Linn). Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Retrieved from: <https://www.researchgate.net>.
- Mcsorley, N. O.; Parley, F. and Adams, F. K. (2014):** Utilizing the potential of poultry manure in soil amendments. Retrieved from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publishing>.
- Mijindadi, R. and Erhabor, L. (2016):** Effect of organic amendment on soil fertility and plant nutrients in a Post-Fire mediterranean ecosystem. *Journal of Plant and Soil*, 367(1-2):211-215.
- Ndon, B. A.; Ndaeyo, N. U.; Udoh, D. J. and Asuquo, P.E. (2015):** Crop Production in the Tropics. Concept Publications Limited, Lagos, Nig.
- Netarajan, A. M.; Dike, M. C. and Amatobi, C. I. (2016):** Field evaluation of extracts of five Nigerian species for control of post flowering insect pests of cowpea. *Plant Protection Sc.*, 56: 74-80.
- Obi, I. U. (2002):** Statistical methods of detecting difference between treatment means and research methodology issue of laboratory and field experiment. Retrieved on 19th January, 2018.
- Ogwudire, V. E.; Ojiaka, F. O. and Mbaka, C. C. (2019):** Nematicidal effects of *Jatropha curcas* L. Root extracts for the control of nematode *Meloidogyne incognita*. Retrieved from: www.researchgate.net.
- Ogwulumba, S. I. and Mba, E. U. (2016):** Effect of plant manure sources on root-knot nematode infections and yield of bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterraneum* L.) verdcourt in the Derived Savanna. Retrieved from: www.researchgate.net.
- Ogwulumba, S. I. and Okonta, J. (2015):** Studies on *Meloidogyne javanica* on roma tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) under different soil amendments. Retrieved from: www.researchgate.net.
- Ogwulumba, S. I.; Uguoke, K. and Ogbuji, R. O. (2010):** Studies on *Meloidogyne javanica* on roma tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) under different soil amendments. Retrieved from: www.researchgate.net.
- Sonbeer, C.; Kaushik D.; Prakash, K.; Savita, B. and Narajen, L. (2017):** Effect of different doses of *Jatropha* leaf extract on growth and development of French bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) and Brinja (*Solanum melongena*). *International Journal of Current*

Microbiology and Applied Sciences, 6(5): 2692 – 2705.

Takeda, Y. (1982): Development study on *Jatropha curcas* oil as a substitute for diesel oil in Thailand. Interim Report of the Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand.

Taylor, M.; Touray, M.; Cimen, H. and Gulsen, S. H. (2016): The

Impact of Chemical Nematicides on Entomopathogenic Nematode Survival and Infectivity. Journal of Nematology. Vol. 53 DOI: 10.21307/JOFNEM-2014-049.

Efficiency of some essential oils on *Ascosphaera apis* the pathogen chalkbrood disease

Zienab, A. E. Hassanein

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 10 / 4 /2022

Accepted: 22/ 6 /2022

Keywords

Honey bee, natural oils, chalkbrood, safe control, disease, and *Ascosphaera apis*.

Abstract:

Chalkbrood is a fungal disease of honey bee brood caused by *Ascosphaera apis*. This disease is now found throughout the world, chalkbrood has been extensively studied in biology and Host-Pathogen interactions. The essential oils tested exhibited significant antimicrobial activities against honey bee *Apis mellifera* Linnaeus (Hymenoptera: Apidae) it is very difficult to reproduce chalkbrood in a large number of colonies, so this study evaluated the efficacy of mixed oils (Thyme oil, clove oil, and camphor oil) in equal concentrations (5%) and formic acid (65%) against chalkbrood disease during the spring season of 2020 in Sidi Salem, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, Egypt. The obtained results indicated that the average reduction of mixed oils on sealed brood reached 85.5% and 76.9% on unsealed brood. Also, the reduction of formic acid was 91.7% on sealed brood and 85% on unsealed brood, the obtained results indicated that all tested materials were effective against chalkbrood disease under field conditions.

Introduction

The honey bee *Apis mellifera* Linnaeus (Hymenoptera: Apidae) is an important pollinator of various crops and plants in the world, it has a high economic value and suffers from many diseases including chalkbrood. Chalkbrood in honey bee is a fungal brood disease caused by *Ascosphaera apis* (Gilliam, 1990). These infected larvae then become black or white mummies. The name of the disease refers to the appearance of dead larvae, several studies have shown essential oils to be effective in controlling bee diseases such as a fungal disease (Higes *et al.*, 1998).

An increased rate of resistance of various *A. apis* strains. Chalkbrood affects the honey yield (Zaghoul *et al.*,

2005) . White mummies are due to infection with mycelia of *A. apis* (Davis and Ward , 2003) .

Furthermore, pesticides and antifungal chemicals present in honey represent a major human health hazard (Frazier *et al.*, 2008). Chalkbrood is established in colonies infected with other diseases or by stress situations aggravating bee mortality (Evison and Jensen, 2018) . Use available natural compounds and fungicides has been investigated for the treatment of chalk brood both in the laboratory and in the field (Hornitzky, 2001 and Davis and Ward, 2003). Also, a comparison of methods to controlling of chalkbrood (Flores *et al.*, 2004) chalkbrood has been extensively studied on pathogen biology and host pathogen interactions

and including morphology (Liu *et al.*, 2018).

The aim of the present study is to evaluate some natural products for controlling chalkbrood disease in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during spring, season 2020.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental site:

The experiments were conducted in an apiary at Sidi Salem, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during the spring season of 2020. Whereas the study required fifteen colonies of carniolan hybrid nearly of equal strength. The experiments were divided into three parts every part were five colonies (Control without treatment – mixed natural oils 5% – formic acid 65%). To take measurements, square inches were used before and after the treatment for three months to measure both sealed and unsealed brood which infected with chalkbrood disease every 12 days and placing a plastic sheet under a comb covered with vaseline to catch the mummies every 3 days.

2. Materials:

2.1. Mixed oils (Thyme oil, clove oil and camphor oil)

2.2. Formic acid.

The mixed natural oils were used with concentrations 5% and formic acid 65%.

3. Determination of chalkbrood infection:

Table (1): Reduction percentages of infection with *Ascosphaera Apis* in *Apis mellifera* colonies treated with mixed oils and formic acid on sealed brood.

Date	Infestation before treatment%		Infestation after treatment%		Reduction%	
	Mixed oils	Formic acid	Mixed oils	Formic acid	Mixed oils	Formic acid
March	15	15	3	2	80	86.7
April	20	21	4	3	82	85
May	10	21	2	2	85.5	91.7
Total	45	48	9	7		
Mean	15	16	3	2.3		

Data in Table (2) showed that the reduction of formic acid in unsealed brood were (85%) , the reduction of

Chalkbrood mummies were collected from the sheet, entrance and counted every three day from March until May (Sokovic *et al.*, 2009). The reduction percentage of chalkbrood mummies was calculated according to (Henderson and Tilton, 1955) .

Reduction % =

$$100 \times 1 - \frac{\text{Treatment after} \quad \text{Control before}}{\text{Treatment before} \quad \text{Control after}}$$

Results and discussion

The main problem for research in chalkbrood is the difficulty to induce the disease in a controlled way because of different rates of mummification in the colonies (Morawetz *et al.*, 2019). Mixed natural oils, namely thyme oil, clove oil, and camphor oil 5%, and formic acid 65% were evaluated against *A. apis* under field conditions.

Data in Table (1) indicated that the reduction of infection in sealed brood was clearly reduced after treatments with mixed oils and formic acid. Whereas the reduction percentages of mixed oils reached (85.5%) and formic acid reached (91.7%) on sealed brood, respectively, the obtained data showed that the highest reduction of infection was in May. These results are in agreement with Boudegga *et al.* (2010) and Dellacasa *et al.* (2003).

mixed oils reached (76.9%) . The obtained data clearly shows the highest activity of formic acid against

chalkbrood (*A. apis*), it also showed the effectiveness of mixed natural oils in controlling, safety and its lack of toxicity compared to pesticides. Figure (1) illustrated that Formic acid has a higher effect on mummies shedding

than natural oils, knowing that its were also effective, safe and economical. The data showed that April has a larger number of fallen mummies than other months.

Table (2): Reduction percentages of infection with *Ascosphaera Apis* in *Apis mellifera* colonies treated with mixed oils and formic acid on unsealed brood .

Date	Infestation before treatment %		Infestation after treatment %		Reduction%	
	Mixed oils	Formic acid	Mixed oils	Formic acid	Mixed oils	Formic acid
Unsealed brood						
March	20	18	6	4	67.9	76.2
April	26	25	8	5	72.7	82.3
May	16	14	4	2	76.9	85
Total	62	57	18	11		
Mean	20.7	19	6	3.7		

Figure (1): Number of chalkbrood mummies collected from colonies during spring.

The obtained data correspond to Abdel-Hameed (2007) who found that the percentage of reduction with chalkbrood was obtained by formic acid, varrozal. Also, harmony with Aboulila (2012), who tested some natural materials against chalkbrood disease Beheira Governorate during 2009–2010 and recording good results. In conclusion, it's recommended using natural oils for controlling *A. apis* and it must be a useful component of integrated pest management (IPM) for honey bee diseases.

References

Abdel-Hameed, M. A.A. (2007): Studies on certain honey bee diseases. Ph.D. Thesis, Fac. Agric, Zagazig University.

Aboulila, A.S. M. (2012): New approaches for controlling pests and diseases in honey bee colonies. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. Agric, Ain Shams University.

Boudegga, H.; Boughalleb, N.; Barbouche, N.; ben – Hamouda, M.H. and Mahjoub, M.E. (2010): Invitro inhibitory actions of some essential oils on *Ascosphaera apis*, a fungus responsible for honey bee chalkbrood. J. Apic . Res. 49(3): 236- 242.

Davis, C. and Ward, W. (2003): Control of chalkbrood disease with natural products, A report for the RIRDC. Publication no.

- 03-107. Act. Kingston. Au .1-23.
- Dellacasa, A.D.; Bailac, P.N.; Ponzi, M.I.; Ruffinengo, S.R. and Eguaras, M.J. (2003):** In Vitro activity of essential oils from San Luis-Argentina against *Ascospaera apis*. J. Essent. Oil Res., 15: 282–285.
- Evison, S. E. and Jensen, A. B. (2018):** the biology and prevalence of fungal disease in managed and wild bees. Ecol. Parasites. Boil. Control, 26: 105-113.
- Flores, J. M.; Gutierrez, I. and Puerta, F. (2004):** A comparison of methods to experimentally induce chalk brood disease in honey bees. Span. J. Agricult. Res., 2(1):79-83.
- Frazier, M.; Mullin, C.; Frazier, J. and Ashcraft, S. (2008):** What have pesticides got to do with it? am. Bee J., 148: 521-523.
- Gilliam, M. (1990):** Chalkbrood disease of honey bees, *Apis mellifera*, caused by the fungus, *Ascospaera apis*, a review of past and current research. Proc. of the Vth International Colloquium on Invertebrate Pathology and Microbial Control. The xx iii Annual Meeting of the Society for Invertebrate and Pathology ,20-24 August. Adelaide. Australia,pp. 398-402.
- Henderson, C. F. and Tilton, E. W. (1955):** Test with acaricides against the brown wheat mite. J. Econ. Entom.,48: 157 -161.
- Higes, P.M.; Saurez, M.; liorent, J.; Paya, V. M. J. and Vincente, M. A. (1998):** The efficiency of essential oil in controlling the *Ascopheroses* in honey bee (*Apis mellifera*) under field conditions. Revistalbcro Americana de Micrologie , 15 (3) :151 -154 .
- Hornitzky, M. (2001):** Literature review of chalkbrood: A report for the RIRDC. publication no .01 -150. Act, Au, Kingston.
- Liu, Z.; Hou, M.; Qiu, Y.; Zhao, B.; Nile, H. and Su, S. (2018):** Changes in an antioxidant enzymes activity and metabolomics profiles in the guts of honey bee (*Apis mellifera*) larvae infected with *Ascospaera apis*. Insect.11,419.
- Morawetz, L.; Koglberger, H.; Griesbacher, A.; Derakhshifar, I.; Crailsheim, K.; Brodschneider, R. (2019):** Health status of honey bee colonies (*Apis mellifera*) and disease-related risk factors for colony losses in Austria. PLoS ONE 14(7): e0219293
- Sokovic, M. D.; Vukojevic, J.; Marin, P.D.; Brkic, D. D.; Vajs, V. and van Griensven, I. J. (2009):** Chemical composition of essential oils of thymus and menthe species and their anti-fungal activities. Molecules, 14(1): 238-249.
- Zaghloul, O.A.; Mourad, A.K.; Elkady, M. B.; Nemat, F.M. and Morsy, M.E. (2005):** Assessment of losses in honey yield due to the chalk brood disease, with reference to the determination of its economic injury levels in Egypt. Commun. Agric. Appl. Boil. Sci., 70 (4):703-714.

A faunistic study on Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) in North West of Iran

Hamid, Sakenin¹; Reijo, Jussila²; Najmeh, Samin³ and Balakrishnan, M. Manjusha⁴

¹Department of Plant Protection, Qaemshahr Branch, Islamic Azad University, Qaemshahr, Iran.

²Zoological Museum, Section of Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences, Department of Biology, FI-20014 University of Turku, Finland.

³Young Researchers and Elites Club, Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran.

⁴Department of Zoology, Government College Kasaragod, Vidyanagar – 671123, Kerala, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 13 / 4 / 2022

Accepted: 12 / 6 / 2022

Keywords

Ichneumonidae, fauna, new records, distribution, and Iran.

Abstract:

The fauna of ichneumonid wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) is studied in Ardabil, East Azarbaijan and West Azarbaijan provinces (North West of Iran). In total 38 species in 32 genera and 15 subfamilies, Acaenitinae (One species), Adelogathinae (One species), Anomaloninae (Four species and four genera), Banchinae (Four species and three genera), Campopleginae (10 species and six genera), Cremastinae (One species), Cryptinae (Four species and four genera), Ichneumoninae (One species), Mesochorinae (One species), Metopiinae (Two species and two genera), Ophioninae (One species), Phygadeuontinae (Three species and two genera), Pimplinae (One species), Tryphoninae (Three species and three genera) and Xoridinae (One species).

Introduction

Ichneumonidae is a large family of Hymenoptera, including over 24,000 described (Yu *et al.*, 2016) and 100,000 estimated species worldwide (Gauld, 2000). The ichneumonid wasps are important parasitoids in different stages of several destructive agricultural pests, and in recent years they have been successfully used as biological control agents (Gupta, 1991; Wahl, 1993 and Quicke, 2015).

The purpose of this paper is to record the species of Ichneumonidae of Iran as part of ongoing faunistic studies of Ichneumonidae in Iran. In the present study, a total of 38 ichneumonid species

were collected, of which five species are recorded for the first time from Iran.

Materials and methods

The specimens of the present study were collected by Malaise traps and sweeping net from different areas of Iran. The specimens of this research are preserved in the collections of the authors. Here we follow Yu *et al.* (2016) for nomenclature, classification, and distributional data.

Results and discussion

In this faunistic survey, totally 38 species in 32 genera and 15 subfamilies were collected and identified from northwestern Iran (Ardabil, East Azarbaijan and West Azarbaijan provinces). Five species,

Adelognathus tetratinctorius (Thunberg, 1824), *Atractodes angustipennis* Förster, 1876, *Cubocephalus brevicornis* (Taschenberg, 1865), *Dusona signator* (Brauns, 1895), and *Phygadeuon ovatus* Gravenhorst, 1829 are new records for the fauna of Iran.

1. Subfamily Acaenitinae Foerster, 1869

1.1. *Coleocentrus exareolatus* Kriechbaumer, 1894

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Myandoab (Vali-Abad), 1♀, June 2010.

General distribution: Belarus, Bulgaria, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Romania and Russia.

2. Subfamily Adelognathinae Thomson, 1888

2.1. *Adelognathus tetratinctorius* (Thunberg, 1824)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Ahar (Zyarloo), 1♀, June 2007. New record for Iran.

General distribution: Armenia, Belgium, Canada, Finland, Japan, Kazakhstan, Poland, Russia, Sweden, USA, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

3. Subfamily Anomaloninae Viereck, 1918

3.1. *Agrypon rugifer* (Thomson, 1894)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Mianeh (Khanghah), 2♀♀, August 2009.

General distribution: Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Russia and Sweden.

3.2. *Atrometus insignis* Förster, 1878

Material examined: Ardabil province, Germe, 3♀♀, 18.vi.2015.

General distribution: Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Hungary, Israel, Morocco, Poland, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

3.3. *Erigorgus procerus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Ardabil province, Meshginshahr, 1♂, 1♀, 17.vii.2013.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Moldova, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

3.4. *Perisphincter brevicollis* (Wesmael, 1849)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Mianeh (Haji-Hematloo), 1♂, 2♀♀, August 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

4. Subfamily Banchinae Wesmael, 1845

4.1. *Alloplasta tomentosa* (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Ardabil province, Bilehsavar, 2♀♀, 3.vii.2017.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Poland and Romania.

4.2. *Lemophagus pulcher* (Szépligeti, 1916)

Material examined: Ardabil province, Aslanduz, 1♀, 13.vi.2015.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy and Switzerland.

4.3. *Lissonota argiola* Gravenhorst, 1829

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Ourmieh (Seroo Road: Zeynaloo), 2♀♀, August 2010.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Moldova, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

4.4. *Lissonota mutator* Aubert, 1969

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Myandoab (Dehmansoor), 2♀♀, June 2010.

General distribution: Bulgaria, Germany, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom.

5. Subfamily Campopleginae Foerster, 1869

5.1. *Bathyleptes rufiventror* Aubert, 1979

Material examined: Ardabil province, Germe, 1♀, 18.vi.2015.

General distribution: Armenia, Georgia, Russia and Turkey.

5.2. *Campoplex eudoniae* Horstmann & Yu, 1999

Material examined: Ardabil province, Namin, 1♀, 17.vi.2015.

General distribution: Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland and United Kingdom.

5.3. *Campoplex rothii* (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Shabestar (Alibigloo), 1♀, July 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

5.4. *Dusona notabilis* (Förster, 1868)

Material examined: Ardabil province, Bilehsavar, 2♀♀, 3.vii.2017.

General distribution: Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom.

5.5. *Dusona signator* (Brauns, 1895)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Marand (Darandash), 1♀, September 2016. New record for Iran.

General distribution: Bulgaria, China, former Czechoslovakia, France, Hungary, Japan, Korea, Moldova, Romania and Russia.

5.6. *Dusona subimpressa* (Förster, 1868)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Mianeh (Khanghah), 2♂♂, August 2009.

General distribution: Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Japan, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia and Spain.

5.7. *Echthronomas tricincta* (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Kaleybar, 1♀, 11.viii.2014.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Sweden, Turkey and United Kingdom.

5.8. *Eriborus dorsalis* (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Ardabil province, Namin, 1♂, 17.vi.2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Poland, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

5.9. *Eriborus perfidus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Shabestar (Haft-Cheshmeh), 1♂, 1♀, July 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Bulgaria, China, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Italy, Latvia, Poland, Romania, Spain and United Kingdom.

5.10. *Nemeritis elegans* (Szépligeti, 1901)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Soofian (Andabil), 1♂, July 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Russia, Ukraine and former Yugoslavia.

6. Subfamily Cremastinae Förster, 1869

6.1. *Temelucha anatolica* (Sedivy, 1959)

Material examined: Ardabil province, Aslanduz, 3♀♀, 13.vi.2015.

General distribution: France, Georgia, Israel, Russia, Tunisia, Turkey and Turkmenistan.

7. Subfamily Cryptinae Kirby, 1837

7.1. *Aconias tarsatus* (Bridgman, 1881)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Marand (Darandash), 2♀♀, September 2016.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

7.2. *Atractodes angustipennis* Förster, 1876

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Ahar (Dashbelagh), June 2007. 1♂, 1♀, New record for Iran.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, USA and United Kingdom.

7.3. *Colocnema rufina* (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Mianeh (Aghcheh-Qeshlagh), 1♂, 2♀♀, August 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Luxembourg, Moldova, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

7.4. *Cubocephalus brevicornis* (Taschenberg, 1865)

Material examined: West Azarbijan province, Ourmieh (Seroo Road: Zeynaloo), 1♀, August 2010. New record for Iran.

General distribution: Austria, Canada, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Poland, Russia, USA and United Kingdom.

8. Subfamily Ichneumoninae Latreille, 1802

8.1. *Ichneumon veressi* (Kiss, 1915)

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Myandoab (Dehmansoor), 1♀, June 2010.

General distribution: Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Turkey and former Yugoslavia.

9. Subfamily Mesochorinae Foerster, 1869

9.1. *Mesochorus fulgurans* Curtis, 1833

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Naqadeh (Damirchi), 1♂, 2♀♀, September 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Japan, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom.

10. Subfamily Metopiinae Foerster, 1869

10.1. *Chorinaeus longicornis* Thomson, 1887

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Ahar (Zyarloo), 2♀♀, June 2007.

General distribution: Azerbaijan, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Kazakhstan, Lithuania, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

10.2. *Exochus lentipes* Gravenhorst, 1829

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Soofian (Andabil), 2♂♂, July 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

11. Subfamily Ophioninae Shuckard, 1840

11.1. *Enicospilus inflexus* (Ratzeburg, 1844)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Bonab (Chopoghloo), 3♀♀, September 2016.

General distribution: Bulgaria, Canary Islands, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Morocco, Poland, Spain, Turkey, Turkmenistan and United Kingdom.

12. Subfamily Phygadeuontinae Foerster, 1869

12.1. *Agrothereutes aterrimus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Ourmieh (Seroo Road: Nazlu), 2♀♀, August 2010.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Poland, Russia, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

12.2. *Phygadeuon hercynicus* Gravenhorst, 1829

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Naqadeh (Damirchi), 1♀, September 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

12.3. *Phygadeuon ovatus* Gravenhorst, 1829

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Ourmieh (Band), 1♂, 1♀, August 2010. New record for Iran.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

13. Subfamily Pimplinae Wesmael, 1845

13.1. *Dolichomitus sericeus* (Hartig, 1847)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Ahar (Dashbelagh), 1♂, June 2007.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, Canada, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, Germany, Greece, Poland, Romania, Turkey, USA and former Yugoslavia.

14. Subfamily Tryphoninae Shuckard, 1840

14.1. *Cladeutes discedens* (Woldstedt, 1874)

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Myandoab (Vali-Abad), 1♀, June 2010.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Japan, Norway, Russia, Turkey and United Kingdom.

14.2. *Eridolius rufonotatus* (Holmgren, 1857)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Mianeh (Aghcheh-Qeshlagh), 1♀, August 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

14.3. *Exenterus ictericus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Ourmieh (Seroo Road: Nazlu), 3♀♀, August 2010.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and former Yugoslavia.

15. Subfamily Xoridinae Shuckard, 1840

15.1. *Ischnoceros rusticus* (Geoffroy, 1785)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Soofian (Heydar-Abad), 1♀, July 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia,

Spain, Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Acknowledgments

Sincere thanks to D.R. Kasparyan (Russia), M.R. Shaw (UK), A.M. Pentead-Dias (Brazil) and M.G. Fitton (UK) for scientific cooperation. The authors are grateful to Dr. S. Abd-Rabou (Egypt) and two anonymous reviewers for their insightful comments.

References

Gauld, I.D. (2000): The Ichneumonidae of Costa Rica, 3. Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute, 63: 1–453.

Gupta, V.K. (1991): The parasitic Hymenoptera and biological control and our knowledge of the African Ichneumonidae.

Insect Science and its Application, 12: 9-18.

Quicke, D. (2015): The Braconid and Ichneumonid Parasitoid Wasps: Biology, Systematics, Evolution and Ecology. Wiley-Blackwell, Oxford, UK, xv + pp.681.

Wahl, D.B. (1993): Family Ichneumonidae. *In*: Goulet, H. and Huber, J.T. (eds.), Hymenoptera of the world: An identification guide to families. Canada Communications Group, Ottawa, pp. 668.

Yu, D.S.; van Achterberg, C. and Horstmann, K. (2016): Taxapad 2016, Ichneumonoidea 2015. Database on flash-drive. www.taxapad.com, Nepean, Ontario, Canada.

Susceptibility of different life stages of *Callosobruchus maculatus* and *Callosobruchus chinensis* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae :Bruchidae) to ECO₂FUME gas and its impact on cowpea seeds quality

Manar, Y. Amin; Abeer, O. Abotaleb and Refaat, A. Mohamed

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 17 / 4 /2022

Accepted: 23 / 6 /2022

Keywords

Callosobruchus spp.,
ECO₂FUME gas,
germination, cowpea,
and seeds quality.

Abstract:

ECO₂FUME gas is an alternative to toxic phosphine fumigant and as a quarantine treatment for the control of a particularly recalcitrant pest, *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) and *Callosobruchus chinensis* Linnaeus (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae:Bruchidae). This gas was used to fumigate stored cowpea piles under gas-proof sheets to assess its performance against different developmental stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis*. The mortality was determined on four developmental stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis*, employing ECO₂FUME at different concentrations 25, 30, 40, and 50 g/m³ for 3-days. All stages of both insect species in packed cowpea stacks were completely controlled at 3-days when applied with an ECO₂FUME application rate of 50 g/m³. Cases of pupae of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* exhibit the highest resistance to other stages, with 78.2 and 73.93% mortality, respectively, at 40 g/m³ after 3-days post-exposure to ECO₂FUME. Suppression of F₁ generation was obtained after fumigation with the same concentration (50 g/m³). Quality (In terms of cowpea germination) and all chemical constituents of cowpea seeds were non significantly (P≤0.05) affected by the fumigation concentration of 50 g/m³.

Introduction

The cowpea, *Vigna unguiculata* (L.), is a high-nutritive legume that is widely cultivated for human and animal consumption. Cowpeas have a high nutritional value due to their high protein, carbohydrate, fat, sodium, potassium, and iron content in dry seeds (Hall, 2004). The most important and common pests of stored cowpea seeds in many parts of the world, as well as in

Egypt, are *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) and *Callosobruchus chinensis* Linnaeus (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae :Bruchidae). Through their postharvest feeding and reproductive activity, these insects target stores cowpea seeds and other legumes, contaminate afflicted seeds, and cause physical damage and quality loss (Ali *et al.*, 2005 and Musa and Adeboye, 2017). They are responsible

for considerable economic loss and consequent weight and germination reduction in stored cowpea (Vales *et al.*, 2014). Fumigants are the most common tools for the management of these insects (Akinkurolere *et al.*, 2006). Many fumigators today rely on pesticide sprays or tablets, such as magnesium phosphide and aluminum phosphide. Regardless of the fact that stored goods insects are becoming increasingly resistant to phosphine (Mau *et al.*, 2012; Nayak *et al.*, 2013; Corrêa *et al.*, 2014; Manivannan, 2015; Nguyen *et al.*, 2016; Jagadeesan and Nayak, 2017 and Konemann *et al.*, 2017) that has far-reaching consequences in terms of grain biosecurity and global trade (Norwood, 2017). Although effective, these products can pose safety, environmental and performance challenges, resulting in higher treatment costs and posing regulatory hurdles.

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is a gaseous fumigant that can be toxic to insects at high concentrations and takes a long time to kill all stages of insects (Hasan *et al.*, 2016). CO₂ has features that make it an ideal candidate for co-fumigation with PH₃. It facilitates the equivalent distribution of PH₃ throughout the grain mass (Constantin *et al.*, 2020), ensuring that insects are exposed to both gases simultaneously. In addition, simultaneous exposure to the two gases can cause increased toxicity and minimize the survival of insects, thereby decreasing tolerance and resistance levels to PH₃ that vary substantially among insect species and their different life stages (Jagadeesan and Nayak, 2017; Venkidusamy *et al.*, 2018 and Cato *et al.*, 2019). CO₂ as well as preventing the flammability of PH₃, which is important an occupational safety (Constantin *et al.*, 2020).

With the advent of ECO₂FUME cylinderized gas fumigants, a gas

formulation having a mixture of 2% PH₃ by weight (2.6 percent by volume) in CO₂ (98 percent by weight) offers an alternative treatment option that addresses limitations posed by other offerings on the market. ECO₂FUME has little amount of phosphine and becomes a non-flammable and ready-to-use gas mixture (Tumaming *et al.*, 2012). For fumigating food and non-food commodities, this formulation is safe, effective, and easy to apply (Meenatchi and Alagusundaram, 2014).

The aim of this study was to determine the optimal dosages (Application rate) of ECO₂FUME® gas for the control of common pests of stored legumes, *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis*. Additionally, to find out the response of different developmental stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* to different concentrations of ECO₂FUME gas at 30°C.

Furthermore, the present study was carried out to investigate the effect of the 50 g/m³ ECO₂FUME gas on the quality of cowpea seeds by germination, hardness, cooking time, and chemical composition.

Materials and methods

The field application of ECO₂FUME gas was conducted in El-Baharia Oasis Shona, Giza Governorate, Egypt. ECO₂FUME gas cylinders (Fumigant gas produced by CYTEC, Canada), piles of 240 Jute bags each of 100 kg cowpea seeds, protective clothes, silo check (PH₃ detector) Silo.Chek MARKII is manufactured by the CANARY COMPANY Pty Ltd, AUSTRALIA. This device detects high fumigation phosphine levels greater than 1 ppm up to 2000 ppm. The automatic sampling model (Which was used in this study) had a sample tube, which connect to the gas-sampling lines coming from the pile under fumigation and a built-in pump and battery. After connecting the sample tube with the gas-sampling

lines, the key switch downturned to on. A period of up to 3 minutes was elapsed to allow the PH₃ sensor to record the final reading of PH₃ concentration. Sealing materials, weight digital scale, and plastic sheets (14x20m).

1. Insect cultures:

Two species of legume seed insects were used, *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* were reared on cowpea seeds in the Stored Grains Pest Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agriculture Research Center (ARC), Giza, Egypt. Adult male and female insects were placed in each jar to lay eggs and covered with muslin by a rubber band to prevent insect escape. The jars containing insects were incubated at 28±2 °C and 75±5% RH. for 1 week. Then the parent adults were sieved out and discarded. Different stages of insects such as eggs, larvae, pupae and adults were maintained separately to carry out mortality studies. To collect newly deposited eggs of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis*, adults were maintained on cowpea in ventilated plastic cages. At different periods of time, eggs of known age (2 days old), larvae (After 7-8 days old), pupae (2-3 days old), or adults (3-days after emergence) were obtained for treatments (Wong-Corral *et al.*, 2013).

2. Fumigation procedures:

Three piles of 240 Jute bags each of 100 kg cowpea seeds. From the stock cultures maintained in the rearing room, cloth bags (10x16 cm) each contained 10 g cowpea seeds infested with one of the different stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* eggs, larvae, pupae and adults (30 individuals for each bag in case of adult) were prepared and introduced into the pile and distributed in the four directions (North, South, Middle and West). The total numbers of bags for each concentration of ECO₂FUME gas were 48 bags; 12 bags for each direction (North, South, Middle and West). The

pile was covered exactly and tightly with a plastic sheet 14x20m. After sealing the place of fumigation where the gas cylinder was introduced inside the pile and the gas cylinder was put on platform balance to calculate the required dose. Similar numbers of cloth bags of insect stages were distributed in another cowpea seeds pile using the same procedures without ECO₂ FUME gas to be used as a control.

Four doses of ECO₂FUME (25, 30, 40, and 50 g/m³) were used. After 3-days of exposure to ECO₂FUME gas, the piles were aerated, and the cloth bags containing adults were inspected directly. Bags of the other insect stages were incubated at 28±2 °C and 60±5% RH until adults emerge (F1 progeny). The percentage of insect mortality was estimated and corrected according to Abbott's formula (Abbott, 1925).

3. Effect of ECO₂FUME gas on quality and chemical constituents of cowpea seeds:

The effect of ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ on quality (Germination, hardness, relative humidity, and cooking time) and chemical constituents (Protein, lipids, carbohydrate, moisture, and ash) contents of fumigated and non-fumigated cowpea seeds were studied at both zero time and after 3-months of storage. Twenty-five cowpea seeds (Fumigated and non-fumigated) were put into each dish on top of the moist paper. The three dishes were placed under the lights to allow the seeds' germination. After 7-days, the numbers of germinated seeds were counted and expressed as percent germination.

Hardness and relative humidity testing were carried out by the Penetrometer system (Digital Force Gauge Model FGN-20G, Nidec-Shimpo Corporation Jap.) and grain moisture meter (DRAMINSKI SA Owocowa 17, 10-860 Olsztyn-Poland), respectively. Two hundred of

(Fumigated and non-fumigated) cowpea seeds were soaked for 1 h in tap water. Afterward, they were placed in an aluminum pot with 2000 ml of water. The average cooking time (min) for three replicates was recorded.

Protein, lipids, carbohydrate, moisture, and ash contents of fumigated and non-fumigated cowpea seeds were determined according to the method of AOAC (1990).

4. Statistical analysis:

Percentages of adult mortality were calculated using the initial number of individuals placed in each cage. In the case of eggs, larvae, or pupae, the mean number of emerging adults in the control treatments was utilized as the initial number of individuals when calculating the mortality rate. For statistical analysis, the average percent mortality of the tested insects was calculated and corrected using Abbott's formula (Abbott, 1925). Toxicity values (LC50 and LC99) were calculated by probit analysis (Finney, 1971) using Ldp-line software to obtain the toxicity regression lines. Obtained results were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) in SAS (Anonymous, 2003). All percentages were Arcsine transformed before analysis. To elucidate the general differences between the two pests, stages, and different ECO₂FUME gas concentrations factorial analysis was conducted using Proc ANOVA in SAS. Means were compared by Tukey's HSD (P=0.05 level) in the same program.

Results and discussion

Different concentrations of ECO₂FUME gas were evaluated against the different stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* in cowpea piles under gas-proof cover at 30°C, stored at El-Baharia Oasis Shona, Giza Governorate, Egypt. The effects of various concentrations of ECO₂FUME gas on the mortality of the different

developmental stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* are presented in Table (1).

The results revealed that the mortality rate of different developmental stages is directly proportional to the concentrations of the ECO₂FUME gas, hence mortality rates for all different developmental stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* exposed to different concentrations of ECO₂FUME gas increased with increasing the gas concentrations.

We observed that all different developmental stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* in the vials, treated with 50 g/m³ for 3-days were dead after fumigation reaching 100% mortality, indicating that this concentration is effective in controlling all life stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis*. No significant differences were observed among the mortality of different developmental stages of *C. maculatus* treated with 25 and 30 g/m³ ECO₂FUME gas for 3-days compared to the vials treated with 40 and 50 g/m³ ECO₂FUME gas for 3-days (P < 0.05). However, it was observed a significant difference between the mortality of different developmental stages of *C. chinensis* post-exposure to 25, 30, 40 and 50 g/m³ ECO₂FUME gas for 3-days (P > 0.05). These findings were supported by other studies on the insecticidal activity of ECO₂FUME gas against other stored product insects.

Table (2) shows the results of the factorial analysis of the overall trend between the two pests, stages, and exposure concentrations. The exposure concentrations had a significant effect on *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* mortality (F=201.87 and p=0.0001). The exposure concentrations were the most influential component, with a substantial influence. Neither pests, nor stages had a significant effect.

Table (1): The percentage mortality (Mean±SE) of the different developmental stages of *Callosobruchus maculatus* and *Callosobruchus chinensis* post-exposure to different concentrations of ECO₂FUME gas.

Conc (g/m ³)	Mortality% (Mean±SE)							
	<i>Callosobruchus maculatus</i>				<i>Callosobruchus chinensis</i>			
	Egg	Larvae	Pupae	Adults	Egg	Larvae	Pupae	Adults
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25	19.06±0.02 ^c	36.27±0.09 ^c	27.18±0.03 ^c	72.2±0.04 ^c	34.05±0.02 ^d	39.79±0.03 ^d	22.93±0.02 ^d	69.99±0.02 ^d
30	33.33±0.02 ^c	46.29±0.04 ^c	33.33±0.06 ^c	87.73±0.03 ^c	59.06±0.01 ^c	58.3±0.0 ^c	49.44±0.0 ^c	91.00±0.01 ^c
40	83.06±0.01 ^b	82.48±0.01 ^b	78.2±0.0 ^b	96.6±0.0 ^b	81.49±0.02 ^b	78.57±0.01 ^b	73.93±0.02 ^b	98.87±0.01 ^b
50	100±0.00 ^a	100±0.00 ^a	100±0.00 ^a	100±0.00 ^a	100±0.00 ^a	100±0.00 ^a	100±0.00 ^a	100±0.00 ^a

Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level using Tukey's HSD test, (P= 0.05)

Table (2): Factorial analysis of obtained data is presented in Table 1.

Factor	Level	Mean	Factor	Level	Mean
Pest	<i>Callosobruchus maculatus</i>	38.97±30.3 ^a	Con.	25	73.24±11.71 ^a
	<i>Callosobruchus chinensis</i>	33.68±25.5 ^b		30	52.81±6.02 ^b
				40	19.25±4.29 ^c
F		5.23	50		00.00±00.00 ^d
P		0.0254			
Stage	Egg	36.25±32.098 ^{ab}	F		201.87
	Larvae	32.07±26.55 ^b			
	Pupae	40.65±33.15 ^a			
F		4.58	P		0.0001
P		0.0138			

Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

Lethal concentration values and parameters of mortality regression line *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* at different developmental stages 3-day post-exposure to different concentrations of ECO₂FUME gas are presented in Table (3). The efficacy of ECO₂FUME varies depending on the life stage of insects within their life cycle. The results showed that the ECO₂FUME concentration required to obtain 50% mortality of *C. maculatus* adult, larvae, pupae and egg were 20.38, 29.23, 31.71 and 31.76 g/m³ respectively. While it was 21.25, 27.95, 31.54 and 28.44 g/m³ for the adult, larvae, pupae and egg of *C. chinensis* respectively. The obtained correlation coefficient values of regression lines of

the two tested insects indicated a high significant correlation between the ECO₂FUME gas concentrations and mortality percentages (Table, 3).

Adult survivorship from two-days old eggs, larvae and pupae of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* at different concentrations of ECO₂FUME gas in cowpea seeds are depicted in Table (4). Treatment of two-days old eggs of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* with different concentrations of ECO₂FUME caused a significant reduction in the progeny of both insect species after 3-days of exposure compared with progeny production in the control treatment (P < 0.05). The number of *C. maculatus* progeny was 58.0, 48.0, 69.0 and 103.0 in control while the numbers

of progeny were 45.0, 32.0, 10.0 and 00.0 at ECO₂FUME concentrations of 25, 30, 40 and 50 g/m³, respectively. Similarly, the treatment with ECO₂FUME at concentrations of 25, 30, 40 and 50 g/m³ reduced the progeny numbers of *C. chinensis* to be 60.0, 70.0, 15.0 and 00.0 compared with 91.0, 171.0, 81.0 and 44.0 in the control. It was also clear that the treatment with ECO₂FUME induced a higher reduction in the progeny of *C. chinensis* than *C. maculatus*. The concentration level of 40 g/m³ caused the highest reduction in the progeny production of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* from treated two-days old eggs was 85.5 and 81.5% respectively. While 50 g/m³ was able to prevent adult emergence completely in both insects. It is obvious that the rate of failure to get adult emergence increased with increasing ECO₂FUME gas concentrations in all stages that have been treated.

All ECO₂FUME gas concentrations were effectively caused a significant reduction in emerging adults from treated larvae of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* ($P < 0.05$). When the larvae of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* were treated at 25, 30 and 40 g/m³ ECO₂FUME gas caused a reduction of 36.6, 46.3, 83.1% and 39.8, 63.1, 78.6% respectively, when compared to the control treatment. *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* larvae treated at 50 g/m³ of ECO₂FUME gas showed 100% mortality based on the adult emergence, indicating that the concentration 50 g/m³ resulted in non-completion of the development of immature stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* (Table, 4). It was observed a significant difference among the number of adults who emerged from treated cowpea seeds with 25, 30 and 40 g/m³ ECO₂FUME gas for 3-days compared to the untreated seeds ($P < 0.05$). Whereas the concentration of 50 g/m³ of ECO₂FUME gas success to achieve

complete protection by preventing adults from emerging from treated pupae 3-days post-exposure. It was confirmed that 50 g/m³ of ECO₂FUME gas was effective in controlling all life stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* 3-days post-exposure at 30°C (Table, 4).

The effect of ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ on some properties of cowpea seeds (Germination%, relative humidity, hardness, and cooking time) of treated and non-treated cowpea seeds at initial application and after 3 months of storage are presented in Table (5). All ECO₂FUME treatments induced a non-significant effect on germination%, relative humidity, hardness, and cooking time of treated cowpea seeds at initial application and after 3-months of storage compared with control treatment ($P < 0.05$). The average germination percentage in both fumigated and nonfumigated cowpea seeds at zero time was 100.0%. This indicates that the ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ had no effect on germination percentage at zero time. But after 3-months of storage, the average germination percent of cowpea seeds, whether fumigated or nonfumigated decreased, but the decrease in nonfumigated samples was higher. This indicates that the ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ had improved cowpea seed germination after storage.

The average hardness of the nonfumigated samples was 54.38 N, and that for fumigating samples was 54.16 N. Neither fumigated at 50 g/m³ nor storage for 3 months significantly changes the hardness of cowpea seeds (Table, 5). Applying ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ caused a non-significant effect on relative humidity, hardness, and the cooking time of treated cowpea seeds at initial application and after 3 months of storage compared with control treatment ($P < 0.05$) (Table, 5). The effect of ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ on the major chemical constituents of cowpea seeds of fumigated and nonfumigated cowpea seeds at zero time and after 3-months of storage are presented in Table (6).

Table (3): Relative lethal concentrations (LC) of ECO₂FUME gas for both pests at different stages after 3-days post-exposure.

Tested insects	Stage	LC ₅₀ (g/m ³)	LC ₉₉ (g/m ³)	Confidence limits(g/m ³ .)				Slope	r	X ²
				LC ₅₀		LC ₉₉				
				Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper			
<i>Callosobruchus maculatus</i>	Adults	20.38	45.31	16.73	22.64	39.89	57.96	6.71±1.17	0.98	0.61
	Larvae	29.23	59.40	27.76	30.57	53.34	69.36	7.55±0.74	0.98	5.98
	pupae	31.71	62.24	24.65	37.24	62.05	138.01	7.94±0.63	0.97	6.69
	Egg	31.76	53.51	30.65	32.89	49.51	59.42	10.27±0.84	0.97	5.97
<i>Callosobruchus chinensis</i>	Adults	21.25	41.10	18.02	23.17	36.78	51.22	8.12±1.46	0.99	0.93
	Larvae	27.95	65.17	26.13	29.50	57.97	77.12	6.33±0.62	0.93	3.35
	Pupae	31.54	73.30	29.83	33.21	63.01	92.41	6.35±0.71	0.94	1.58
	Egg	28.44	57.12	26.95	29.76	51.39	66.61	7.68±0.77	0.95	5.88

Table (4): Adult survivorship from two-day old eggs, larvae and pupae of *Callosobruchus maculatus* and *Callosobruchus chinensis* post exposure to different concentrations of ECO₂FUME gas.

Gas conc. (g/m ³)	Seeds status	No. emerging adults from treated eggs				No. emerging adults from treated larvae				No. emerging adults from treated pupae			
		C.m.	Reduction %	C.c.	Reduction %	C.m.	Reduction %	C.c.	Reduction %	C.m.	Reduction %	C.c.	Reduction %
25	Untreated	58 ^a	-	91 ^a	-	41 ^a	-	103 ^a	-	125 ^a	-	122 ^a	-
	Treated	45 ^b	34.1	60 ^b	36.6	26 ^b	39.8	62 ^b	63.1	101 ^b	19.2	103 ^b	15.6
30	Untreated	48 ^a	-	171 ^a	-	54 ^a	-	203 ^a	-	141 ^a	-	98 ^a	-
	Treated	32 ^b	59.1	70 ^b	46.3	29 ^b	63.1	75 ^b	63.1	94 ^b	33.3	48 ^b	51
40	Untreated	69 ^a	-	81 ^a	-	65 ^a	-	196 ^a	-	177 ^a	-	69 ^a	-
	Treated	10 ^b	81.5	15 ^b	83.1	11 ^b	78.6	42 ^b	78.6	31 ^b	82.5	18 ^b	73.9
50	Untreated	103 ^a	-	44 ^a	-	176 ^a	-	56 ^a	-	170 ^a	-	124 ^a	-
	Treated	00 ^b	100	00 ^b	100	00 ^b	100	00 ^b	100	00 ^b	100	00 ^b	100

Mean followed by the same letter are not significantly different using Tukey's HSD test, (P= 0.05).

C.m. = *Callosobruchus maculatus* C.c. = *Callosobruchus chinensis*

Table (5): The effect of ECO₂FUME gas (Mean±SE) at 50g/m³ on some properties of treated and untreated cowpea seeds at initial time and after 3-months of storage.

Parameters	Initial time		After storage	
	Untreated Mean±SE	Treated Mean±SE	Untreated Mean±SE	Treated Mean±SE
Germination%	100±0.0 ^a	100±0.0 ^b	89.32±0.43 ^a	90.68±0.5 ^b
Hardness	54.38±0.7 ^a	54.16±0.7 ^b	54.38±0.6 ^a	54.16±0.7 ^b
Relative humidity	6.23±0.1 ^a	9.03±0.1 ^b	6.37±0.14 ^a	9.23±0.15 ^b
Cooking time(min)	45±1.1 ^a	44.67±1.1 ^b	42.67±0.29 ^a	43±0.3 ^b

Mean followed by the same letter are not significantly different using Tukey's HSD test, ($P= 0.05$)

Table (6): The effect of ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ on the major chemical constituents of fumigated and nonfumigated cowpea seeds at initial time and after 3-months of storage.

Constituents	Initial time		After storage	
	Untreated Mean±SE	Treated Mean±SE	Untreated Mean±SE	Treated Mean±SE
Protein	25.173±0.18 ^a	25.22±0.17 ^b	25.16±0.19 ^a	25.26±0.2 ^b
Lipid	1.67±0.13 ^a	1.55±0.12 ^b	1.64±0.04 ^a	1.51±0.05 ^b
Carbohydrates	55.97±0.3 ^a	56.12±0.3 ^b	56.3±1.22 ^a	56.37±0.47 ^b
Moisture	7.58±0.20 ^a	7.39±0.30 ^b	7.16±0.14 ^a	7.16±0.14 ^b
Ash	3.13±0.20 ^a	2.9±0.21 ^b	3.03±0.03 ^a	2.77±0.03 ^b

Mean followed by the same letter are not significantly different using Tukey's HSD test, ($P= 0.05$)

In general, the results showed that protein and carbohydrates contents were slightly increased, and the lipid, moisture, and ash contents were slightly decreased in fumigated cowpea seeds with ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ at zero time and after 3-months of storage. Maximum increase for protein (0.047 and 0.1%) and carbohydrates (0.15 and 0.07%) was detected in treating seeds with ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ at zero time and after 3 months of storage, respectively, compared with nonfumigated cowpea seeds. Also, the maximum decrease of lipid (0.12 and 0.13%), moisture (0.19 and 0.00%), and ash (0.23 and 0.26%), respectively, was observed at 50 g/m³ at zero time and after 3 months of storage compared with nonfumigated cowpea seeds. The results indicate that there was no significant effect of fumigation at this concentration level either at zero time or after 3 months of storage at ambient temperature and humidity (P < 0.05). From our results, fumigation using ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ did not significantly affect the major chemical constituents or properties of cowpea (P < 0.05).

Different concentrations of ECO₂FUME gas were evaluated against the different stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* in cowpea piles under gas-proof cover at 30 °C. The results revealed that the mortality rate of different developmental stages is directly proportional to the concentrations of the ECO₂FUME gas; hence mortality rates for all different developmental stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* exposed to different concentrations of ECO₂FUME gas increased with increasing the gas concentrations. For instance, Amin *et al.* (2020) reported that the efficacy of ECO₂FUME gas was increased as the concentration increased furthermore, a dose of 50 g/m³ induced 100% mortality of all insect stages after 3-

days of treatment. Insects are stressed by the increased levels of CO₂, which allows lower levels of phosphine to be more effective in achieving 100% mortality of all life stages including the egg stage in shorter periods of time. Increased carbon dioxide accelerates the penetration rate of the fumigant and enhances the respiration rate of insects thereby making them more susceptible to phosphine (Leesch, 1992 and Chadda *et al.*, 2004). Complete mortalities were achieved for the adults and immature stages of *Ephestia cautella* (Walker), *Ephestia calidella* Guenee (Lepidoptera:Pyralidae) and *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* (Linnaeus) (Coleoptera : Silvanidae) after fumigation with ECO₂FUME gas 3-days post-exposure (Mohamed and Sayed, 2017). The results of the fumigation trials of mixed-age cultures of *Sitophilus zeamais*, *Tribolium castaneum* and *O. surinamensis* in packed rice stacks were completely controlled for all stages at 2 and 3-days when applied with an ECO₂FUME application rate of 50g/m³ (Kengkanpanich *et al.*, 2018). For the management of stored commodity pests, a mixture of CO₂ and PH₃ is being evaluated as a viable fumigant (Leelaja *et al.*, 2007 and Valmas and Ebert, 2006). Many studies show that the addition of CO₂ to PH₃ enhances the toxicity of PH₃ and reduces the dose required to kill insects (Constantin *et al.*, 2020). A recent study against mixed-age populations of PH₃-resistant *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.) (Coleoptera: Bostrychidae) indicated that the toxicity of PH₃ was enhanced up to 28-fold when it was combined with 30% CO₂ (Manivannan *et al.*, 2016). The exposure period required for killing all the immature stages of *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* (L.) (Coleoptera : Silvanidae), *Lasioderma serricorne* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Anobiidae) and *Plodia interpunctella*

(Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) can be reduced to 1-day from 5-days when PH_3 is used in combination with 24% of carbon dioxide (Hartsell *et al.*, 2005), and these findings are also in agreement with that of Constantin *et al.* (2020) reported that an observed enhancement in toxicity toward the rusty grain beetle, *Cryptolestes ferrugineus* with the PH_3+CO_2 mixture was consistent. The most likely explanation for this enhanced toxicity of phosphine comes from two physiological responses to CO_2 exposure: one of them, low concentrations of CO_2 possibly increase aerobic energy metabolism through higher oxygen uptake (Kashi and Bond, 1975) which was well known to enhance phosphine toxicity (Bond *et al.*, 1967 and Kashi, 1981 a and b) and another explanation is at concentrations above 15%, CO_2 stimulates the opening of spiracles (Matthews and White, 2011). Facilitating more gaseous exchange (Mitcham *et al.*, 2006) could favor increased phosphine uptake in tissues. The presence of CO_2 is also essential during fumigation which causes suffocation to insects and results in quick mortality of insects in modified atmospheric storage (Sujeetha *et al.*, 2015).

Changing a few factors like concentration can change the insecticidal effect of ECO_2FUME . Our results showed that the concentration level had the premier impact on the mortality for the two pests at various developmental stages 3-days post-exposure to ECO_2FUME gas with Neither pests, nor stages having a significant effect (Amin *et al.*, 2020).

According to lethal concentration values and parameters of the mortality regression line, *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* adults were more ECO_2FUME sensitive than the other stages, which required treatment of 45.31 and 41.10 g/m^3 , respectively to reach 99% mortality after 3-day post-

exposure to ECO_2FUME gas followed by eggs which required treatment of 53.51 and 57.12 g/m^3 , respectively to reach 99% mortality after 3-day post-exposure to ECO_2FUME gas. The adults of *C. maculatus* are the most susceptible with regard to the developmental states during which they are exposed, and these adults demonstrate high activity and sensitivity to hypoxia. Similarly, the corium is soft in young eggs, which can leak water and oxygen during exposure to a controlled atmosphere, with higher mortality and susceptibility in mature eggs. This is due to the high respiratory activity in the formation of larvae (Iturralde-García *et al.*, 2016).

The most ECO_2FUME -tolerant stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* were pupae and larvae, which required treatment of 62.24, 59.40 g/m^3 and 73.30, 65.17 g/m^3 , respectively to reach 99% mortality after 3-day post-exposure to ECO_2FUME gas. Admixtures of phosphine with CO_2 resulted in reducing the lethal concentrations to achieve increasing mortality of *R. dominica* (Manivannan *et al.*, 2016). The obtained results are in harmony with the findings of other investigators on the efficacy of combinations of phosphine plus carbon dioxide against some stored product insects. Adults of *C. maculatus*, *R. dominica* and *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) proved to be the most susceptible stage post-exposure to mixtures of phosphine and carbon dioxide at 30°C, respectively (El-Lakwah *et al.*, 1992a, b and c). The diverse responses of different life stages of *C. maculatus* could be due to the variation in their respiration rates, differences in body size of life stages and the sex of adults (Iturralde-García *et al.*, 2016). A considerable relationship exists between the respiratory rate and the body mass of insects. Pupal states have a low oxygen

demand, the former being more tolerant to hypoxia due to their metabolic rate, which is slow compared with other stages, as noted in a study on *C. subinnotatus* (Mbata *et al.*, 2000). The increased tolerance of larvae and pupae to ECO₂FUME gas could be due to the lower respiration rates in these life stages (Hoback and Stanley, 2001). Thus, a high mortality rate in adults was observed compared to the other stages of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* even at the same concentration and exposure time. Moreover, larvae and pupae of *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis* are surrounded by the seed material shielded from the external atmosphere providing an additional layer of obstruction to the ECO₂FUME gas. The integrity of the outer layer and metabolic status of the insect's stage are some of the defining factors that make some individuals more susceptible to ECO₂FUME than others (McDonough *et al.*, 2011). Phosphine and CO₂ formulation can be an effective fumigant when applied even though different levels of sensitivity occur as a function of insect species and life stage (Hartsell *et al.*, 2005).

The treated cowpea seeds, having eggs, larvae and pupae showed 100% mortality 3-days post-exposure with 50 g/m³ of ECO₂FUME gas indicating that the treatment schedule was effective in eliminating all life stages of the *C. maculatus* and *C. chinensis*. Similar results were obtained by Perera *et al.* (2018) reported that dose/ time regimes of ECO₂FUME can be recommended for the fumigation of rice for the control of *S. oryzae*, at 700 ppm (50 g ECO₂FUME /m³)/ 36 h. Meenatchi *et al.* (2018) reported that the mixture of PH₃ and CO₂ significantly affects the mortality of various life stages of *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) the synergistic effect of CO₂ on phosphine

toxicity is further supported by the fact that, CO₂ exerts lethal effects on insects causing their death by dehydration at the cellular level and creating a lack of triglycerides for energy metabolism. Complete mortality of all stages of *E. Cautella*, *E. Calidella* and *O. surinamensis* after the application of 50 g/m³ of ECO₂FUME (Mohamed and Sayed, 2017).

ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ had no effect on some properties of cowpea seeds (Germination%, relative humidity, hardness and cooking time). ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ had no effect on germination percentage at zero time, however, had improved cowpea seed germination after the storage period (3 months). Mekali *et al.* (2013) indicated no loss in germination on employing CO₂ of <20%. The increase in the concentration of CO₂ in CA treatments and exposure time benefits the vigor of chickpea germination (Iturralde-García *et al.*, 2016). Saha *et al.* (2015) obtained similar values to those of the control as in this study using 89.5% ambient CO₂.

Overall, the results showed that protein and carbohydrates contents were slightly increased, and the lipid, moisture and ash contents were slightly decreased in fumigated cowpea seeds with ECO₂FUME gas at 50 g/m³ at zero time and after 3 months of storage. In consistent with our results, no negative effects were identified to fruit quality (Physical, chemical and sensory analysis) after the treatment, storage and shelf life in green pepper fruit treated with phosphine (ECO₂FUME) for 24 h at 500, 1000 and 2000 ppm (Ertürk *et al.*, 2018). The quality of grains is not affected by treatment with a CO₂-rich atmosphere and the application meets the requirements of organic markets (Annis *et al.*, 1991).

Our study provides information about the insecticidal efficacy of ECO₂FUME gas for the management of

C. maculatus and *C. chinensis* in infested cowpea seeds. As indicated by the results of this study, exposure with 50 g/m³ of ECO₂FUME gas indicated that the treatment was effective in eliminating all life stages of the two insects, prevented progeny production and improved germination of the cowpea seeds, and increased the major chemical constituents of cowpea seeds (Protein and carbohydrates) after 3 months of 50 g/m³ of ECO₂FUME application. However, research efforts must be undertaken to evaluate the fumigation technology with ECO₂FUME gas to be economically feasible and compete with existing storage insect control technologies. Further studies are required in the development of commercial and continuous ECO₂FUME gas treatment and what the economic, ecological, and optimal treatment time according to the actual storage.

References

- Abbott, W. S. (1925):** A method of computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. *J. Entomol.*, 18:265-267.
- Akinkurolere, R.O.; Adedire, C.O. and Odeyemi, O.O. (2006):** Laboratory evaluation of the toxic properties of forest anchomanes, *Anchomanes difformis* against pulse beetle *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *Insect Sci.*, 13:25-29.
- Ali, M.A.M.; El-Sayed, F.M.A. and El-Bishlawy, H.M.I. (2005):** Damage and quantitative loss caused by *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera: Bruchidae) to some cowpea and faba bean varieties. *Egypt. J. Agric. Res.*, 83:563-581.
- Amin, M.Y.; Aamir, M.M.I.; Mohamed, R.A. and Abd-Alla, S.M. (2020):** Control of the rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) using some insecticide alternative safe methods. *Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst.*, 3:535-543.
- Annis, P.C.; Graver, J.V.S. and Highley, E. (1991):** New operations manuals for safe and effective fumigation of grain in sealed bag-stacks. In International working Conference on Stored-Product Protection, pp. 747-755.
- Anonymous (2003):** SAS Statistics and graphics guide, release 9.1. SAS Institute, Cary, North Carolina 27513, USA.
- AOAC (1990):** Association of Official Analytical Chemistry, 15th Ed. Arlington, West Virginia, USA, Washington DC: Official methods of analysis, USA.
- Bond, E. J.; Monro, H. A. U. and Buckland, C. T. (1967):** The influence of oxygen on the toxicity of fumigants to *Sitophilus granarius* (L). *J. Stored Prod. Res.*, 3:289-294.
- Cato, A.; Afful, E.; Nayak, M.K. and Phillips, T.W. (2019):** Evaluation of knockdown bioassay methods to assess phosphine resistance in the red flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). *Insects*, 10:140.
- Chadda, I.C.; Jayraj, K. and Dhuri, A.V. (2004):** New method of phosphine and carbon dioxide application and its optimization. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Controlled Atmosphere and Fumigation in Stored Products. FTIC Ltd., Publishing, Israel, Gold-Coast, Australia, pp. 455-465.

- Constantin, M.; Jagadeesan, R.; Chandra, K.; Ebert, P. and Nayak, M.K. (2020):** Synergism between phosphine (PH₃) and carbon dioxide (CO₂): implications for managing PH₃ resistance in rusty grain beetle (Laemophloeidae: Coleoptera). *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 113: 1999-2006.
- Corrêa, A.S.; Tomé, H.V.V.; Braga, L.S.; Martins, G.F.; De Oliveira, L.O. and Guedes, R.N.C. (2014):** Are mitochondrial lineages, mitochondrial lysis and respiration rate associated with phosphine susceptibility in the maize weevil *Sitophilus zeamais*?. *Ann. Appl. Biol.*, 165:137-146.
- El-Lakwah, F.A.; Saleh, M.K.; Omer, E.E. and Mohamed, R.A. (1992a):** Efficiency of phosphine alone and in combination with carbon dioxide against the various stages of cowpea weevil *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F.) (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *Egypt. J. Appl. Sci.*, 7:80-98.
- El-Lakwah, F.A.; Saleh, M.K.; Omer, E.E. and Mohamed, R.A. (1992b):** Efficacy of phosphine, carbon dioxide and their mixtures against the various stages of lesser grain borer *Rizopertha dominica* (F.) (Coleoptera: Bostrychidae). *Egypt. J. Appl. Sci.*, 7:99-117.
- El-Lakwah, F.A.; Saleh, M.K.; Omer, E.E. and Mohamed, R.A. (1992c):** Efficacy of phosphine, carbon dioxide and their mixtures against the various stages of rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *Egypt. J. Appl. Sci.*, 7:203-221.
- Ertürk, S.; Fatih, Ş.E.N.; Alkan, M. and Ölçülü, M. (2018):** Effect of different phosphine gas concentrations against *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande, 1895) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) on tomato and green pepper fruit, and determination of fruit quality after application under low-temperature storage conditions. *Turk. J. Entomol.*, 42:85-92.
- Finney, D.F. (1971):** Probit Analysis. Cambridge University Press, London. pp.256. Guedes RNC, Guedes NMP, Rosi-Denadai CA (2011) Sub-lethal effects of insecticides on stored-product insects: current knowledge and future needs. *Stewart Postharvest Rev.*, 7:1–5.
- Hall, A.E. (2004):** Breeding for adaptation to drought and heat in cowpea. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 21:447-454.
- Hartsell, P.L.; Muhareb, J.S.; Arnest, M.L.; Hurley, J.M.; McSwigan, B.J. and Deskin, R. (2005):** Efficacy of a mixture of phosphine/carbon dioxide on eight species of stored product insects. *Southwest Entomol.*, 30:47-54.
- Hasan, M.M.; Aikins, M.J.; Schilling, W. and Phillips, T.W. (2016):** Efficacy of controlled atmosphere treatments to manage arthropod pests of dry-cured hams. *Insects*, 7:44.
- Hoback, W.W. and Stanley, D.W. (2001):** Insects in hypoxia. *J. Insect Physiol.*, 46:533–542.
- Iturralde-García, R.D.; Borboa-Flores, J.; Cinco-Moroyoqui, F.J.; Riudavets, J.; Del Toro-Sánchez, C.L.; Rueda-Puente EO et al. (2016):** Effect of controlled atmospheres on the insect *Callosobruchus*

- maculatus* Fab. in stored chickpea. J. Stored Prod. Res., 69:78-85.
- Jagadeesan, R. and Nayak, M.K. (2017):** Phosphine resistance does not confer cross-resistance to sulfuryl fluoride in four major stored grain insect pests. Pest Manag. Sci., 73:1391-1401.
- Kashi, K.P. (1981a)** Toxicity of phosphine to five species of stored-product insects in atmospheres of air and nitrogen. Pestic. Sci., 12:116-122.
- Kashi, K.P. (1981b):** Response of five species of stored-product insects to phosphine in oxygen-deficient atmospheres. Pestic. Sci., 12:111-115.
- Kashi, K.P. and Bond, E.J. (1975):** The toxic action of phosphine: role of carbon dioxide on the toxicity of phosphine to *Sitophilus granarius* (L.) and *Tribolium confusum* DuVal. J. Stored Prod. Res., 11:9-15.
- Kengkanpanich, R., Suthisut, D. and Sitthichaiyakul, S. (2018):** Application of ECO₂FUMER phosphine fumigant for the complete control of major stored product insect pests in milled rice in Thailand. Julius-Kühn-Archiv., 463:618-625.
- Konemann, C.E.; Hubhachen, Z.; Opit, G.P.; Gautam, S. and Bajracharya, N.S. (2017):** Phosphine resistance in *Cryptolestes ferrugineus* (Coleoptera: Laemophloeidae) collected from grain storage facilities in Oklahoma, USA. J. Econ. Entomol., 110:1377-1383.
- Leelaja, B.C.; Rajashekar, Y.; Reddy, P.V.; Begum, K. and Rajendran, S. (2007):** Enhanced fumigant toxicity of allyl acetate to stored-product beetles in the presence of carbon dioxide. J. Stored Prod. Res., 43:45-48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jspr.2005.09.004>
- Leesch, J.G. (1992):** Carbon dioxide on the penetration and distribution of phosphine through wheat. J. Econ. Entomol., 85:157-161.
- Manivannan, S. (2015):** Toxicity of phosphine on the developmental stages of rust-red flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* Herbst over a range of concentrations and exposures. J. Food Sci. Technol., 52:6810-6815.
- Manivannan, S. ; Koshy, G.E. and Patil, S.A. (2016):** Response of phosphine-resistant mixed-age cultures of lesser grain borer, *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.) to different phosphine-carbon dioxide mixtures. J. Stored Prod. Res., 69:175-178.
- Matthews, P.G. and White, C.R. (2011):** Regulation of gas exchange and haemolymph pH in the cockroach *Nauphoeta cinerea*. J. Exp. Biol., 214:3062-3073.
- Mau, Y.S.; Collins, P.J.; Daghli, G.J.; Nayak, M.K. and Ebert, P.R. (2012):** The rph2 gene is responsible for high level resistance to phosphine in independent field strains of *Rhyzopertha dominica*. PLoS ONE, 7:34027.
- Mbata, G.N.; Hetz, S.K.; Reichmuth, C. and Adler, C. (2000):** Tolerance of pupae and pharate adults of *Callosobruchus subinnotatus* Pic (Coleoptera: Bruchidae) to modified atmospheres: a function of metabolic rate. J. Insect Physiol. 46:145-151.
- McDonough, M.X.; Campabadal, C.A.; Mason, L.J.; Maier,**

- D.E.; Denvir, A. and Woloshuk, C. (2011):** Ozone application in a modified screw conveyor to treat grain for insect pests, fungal contaminants, and mycotoxins. *J. Stored Prod. Res.*, 47:249-254.
- Meenatchi, R. and Alagusundaram, K. (2014):** The current status of fumigation in India: Constraints and recent developments. *Trends in Entomology*, 10:97-103.
- Meenatchi, R.; Alice, R. P.S.J. and Paulin, P.P. (2018):** Synergistic effect of phosphine and carbon dioxide on the mortality of *Tribolium castaneum* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) in Paddy. *J. Agric. Sci.*, 10:503-510.
- Mekali, J. ; Naganagoud, A.; Kapasi, M.; Sreenivas, A.G.; Nidoni, U. and Baskar, K. (2013):** Management of *Rhyzopertha dominica* Fab. under modified atmospheric condition in stored sorghum. *J. Entomol. Stud.*, 2: 34-43.
- Mitcham, E.; Martin, T. and Zhou, S. (2006):** The mode of action of insecticidal controlled atmospheres. *Bull. Entomol. Res.*, 96:213-222.
- Mohamed, R.A. and Sayed, A.A. (2017):** Efficiency of ECO₂FUME gas against some dry and semi-dry date fruit insect pests in different stores. *Ann. Agric. Sci. Moshtohor*, 55:137-144.
- Musa, A.K. and Adeboye, A.A. (2017):** Susceptibility of some cowpea varieties to the seed beetle *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F.) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae). *J. Agric. Sci. (Belgrade)*, 62:351-360.
- Nayak, M.K.; Holloway, J.C.; Emery, R.N.; Pavic, H.; Bartlet, J. and Collins, P.J. (2013):** Strong resistance to phosphine in the rusty grain beetle, *Cryptolestes ferrugineus* (Stephens) (Coleoptera: Laemophloeidae) : its characterization, a rapid assay for diagnosis and its distribution in Australia. *Pest Manag. Sci.*, 69:48-53.
- Nguyen, T.T.; Collins, P.J.; Duong, T.M.; Schlipalius, D.I. and Ebert, P.R. (2016):** Genetic conservation of phosphine resistance in the rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.). *J. Hered.*, 107:228-237.
- Norwood, C. (2017):** New fumigation protocols are being developed to tackle the challenge of increasing insect resistance to current control strategies, Ground Cover. Grain Research Development Corporation, Australia.
- Perera, G.T.S.; Fernando, T.N.P.; Weerasinghe, W.R.U.; Nugaliyadde, L.; Senadeera, S.P.S.K.; Wijesinghe, PRA et al. (2018):** Fumigation standards for liquid phosphine (Eco₂ fume 2% phosphine in 98% carbon dioxide W/W) for the control of quarantine pests of rice, pineapple and bitter gourd. *Trop. Agric. TurisT*, 166:17-32.
- Saha, S.; Chakraborty, D.; Sehgal, V.K. and Pal, M. (2015):** Rising atmospheric CO₂: Potential impacts on chickpea seed quality. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.*, 203:140-146.
- Sujeetha, A.R.; Meenatchi, R.; Venkatesan, P. and Brimapureswaran, R. (2015):** Nitrogen based modified atmosphere for the management of Cigarette

- beetle, *Lasioderma sericorne* in turmeric. IJSART, 1:84-87.
- Tumaming, J.; Depalo, M.; Garnier, J.P., and Mallari, R. (2012):** ECO₂Fume and Vapor PH₃ OS phosphine fumigants—Global application updates. In S. Navarro, H. J. Banks, D. S. Jayas, C. H. Bell, R. T. Noyes, A. G. Ferizli, M. Emekci, A. A. Isikber, and K. Alagusundaram (Eds.), Proc. of the 9th Int. Conf. on Controlled Atmosphere and Fumigation in Stored Products, 15-19 October 2012 (pp. 363-373). Antalya, Turkey, ARBER Professional Congress Services, Turkey.
- Vales, M.I.; Rao, G.R.; Sudini, H.; Patil, S.B. and Murdock, L.L. (2014):** Effective and economic storage of pigeonpea seed in triple layer plastic bags. J. Stored Prod. Res., 58:29-38.
- Valmas, N. and Ebert, P.R. (2006):** Comparative toxicity of fumigants and a phosphine synergist using a novel containment chamber for the safe generation of concentrated phosphine gas. PLOS One 1:e130.
- Venkidusamy, M.; Jagadeesan, R.; Nayak, M.K.; Subbarayalu, M.; Subramaniam, C. and Collins, P.J. (2018):** Relative tolerance and expression of resistance to phosphine in life stages of the rusty grain beetle, *Cryptolestes ferrugineus*. J. Pest Sci., 91:277-286.
- Wong-Corral, F.J.; Castan, E.C. and Riudaviets, J. (2013):** Lethal effects of CO₂-modified atmospheres for the control of three Bruchidae species. J. Stored Prod. Res., 55:62-67.

Occurrence of mites associated with stored products in some localities in Egypt

Aisha, Anas El Mosalami; Abdel-Sattar, Mohammed Metwally; Awad, Ali Abdallah
and Mohamed, Abdel-Hady

Department of Zoology and Nematology, Faculty of Agriculture, Al-Azhar University, Cairo, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 20 / 4 /2022

Accepted: 28/6 /2022

Keywords

Occurrence,
Astigmata,
Prostigmata,
Mesostigmata, mites
and stored products.

Abstract:

This study proves the occurrence of 45 different mite species belonging to 30 genera under 15 families. These mites are belonging to 3 suborders Acaridida (Astigmata), Actinedida (Prostigmata) and Gamasida (Mesostigmata). The 45 mite species were collected from 8 different stored product sources: Potato, oats, barley, garlic, corn, onion, wheat bran and flour, which were collected from 10 regions at 2 governorates, during the two successive years 2019 and 2020. The astigmatid mites in this study were represented by 6 families and 20 different species. On the other hand, the number of mite species in suborder Prostigmata was 11 species belonging to 4 families. The obtained data indicated that the mesostigmatid was represented by 14 different species in 5 different families.

Introduction

Large numbers of mites are known to occur associated with stored products throughout the world. They attack damaged and undamaged grains devouring the embryos and other surrounding tissues. This prevents grain germination and reduces its nutritive value. They also feed on fungi and other micro-organisms. Contamination by alive and dead mite different stages as well as exuviae and faeces results in being harmful for human consumption (Hughes, 1976). Stored products mites are found in different product stores and sometimes, in high concentration. Mites flourish in warm and damp environments where they feed on protein rich substances such as grain, fungi and other micro-organisms.

Mites cause significant grain weight losses and a decrease of

germinability. Their activities cause heating of grain mass and moisture translocation, which permits the development of molds and germination of the grain, contamination by alive and dead mites, different stages as well as exuviae and faeces resulting in being harmful for human consumption (Hughes, 1976). Mites are vectors of toxicogenic fungi. Which contribute to the contamination of food and feed with mycotoxins.

Also, the mites influence the weight and quality of stored products, the effect depends on their density and the length of infestation. If it was evaluated separately the effect can be neglected because the losses caused by mite contamination are quite higher and infested commodities are unsuitable for consumption due to contamination by hazardous compounds. The mites

change the quality of infested food by the production of secrets and faeces. The massive infestation of mites changes the smell of stored products. The stored-product mites cause hypersensitivity not only for stored grain and farm workers, millers and bakers, but they also seriously endanger the health of the city population (Musken *et al.*, 2003). Studies on mites inhabiting stored products were reported previously by Wafa *et al.* (1966), Attiah (1969), Hughes (1976), Taha (1985), Zaher *et al.* (1986) and recently, by Hoda *et al.* (1990), Fawzy (1996), Halawa (2003), El-Sanady (2005), Yassin *et al.* (2018) and Halawa *et al.* (2021).

So, the present work investigates the occurrence of mites associated with stored products in two governorates in Egypt.

Materials and methods

1. Mites collection:

General occurrence from 10 regions at 2 Egyptian governorates was undertaken for two successive years 2019 and 2020. The studied governorates were: El-Menofia (Shubra Qabala, Kafr El Salameh, Quesna, Ashlim and Shimandil districts) and El Giza (Abou Rawash, Sheikh Zayed, 6th of October, Bolak Al-Dakroul and Imbaba districts). Samples of 8 different stored product sources: Potato, oats, barley, garlic, corn, onion, wheat bran and flour were collected monthly from some groceries and houses.

Samples about 1kg. each, of the previous materials, was picked and singly kept in tightly closed polyethylene bags. A label including all necessary information concerning habitat, locality and date of the collection was attached to each bag and then, transferred to the laboratory.

2. Mounting, preservation and identifications:

A sample of 250 gm of each material was isolated by modified

Tullgren funnels, in 3cm deep layers and kept for 24 hours below 40-watt electric lamps. The mites were collected into Petri-dishes with the airing of Vaseline mixed with citronella oil to prevent mite escape (Metwally, 1976). Active mite individuals were transferred by a camel hair brush and examined using a stereomicroscope. Isolated specimens were placed in Nesbitt as a clearing solution (40 gm chloral hydrate, 25 ml distilled water and 2.5 ml concentrated hydrochloric acid) for 24 hours (Krantz and Walter, 2009). After that, mites were mounted singly by placing in a drop of Hoyer's medium which was prepared as follows: distilled water (50 ml), chloral hydrate (50 gm), glycerin (20 ml), and Arabic gum (30 gm) (Hughes, 1976 and Krantz and Walter, 2009).

3. Mite identification:

Identification was carried out according to, Hughes (1976), Summers and Price (1970), Zaher *et al.* (1984), and Krantz and Walter (2009). Mite specimens were kept in the mite collection of Agric., Zoology and Nematology Department Faculty of Agric., Al-Azhar University.

Results and discussion

The collected data proves the occurrence of 45 mite species inhabiting different stored product sources: Potato, oats, barley, garlic, corn, onion, wheat bran, and flour which were collected from 10 regions at 2 Governorates, during the two successive years in 2019 and 2020. They feed on stored materials, fungus, or being predators or parasites and the latter may be of great benefit in the biological control of associated insect and acarine pests. Data in Table (1) shows the occurrence of 20 astigmatid mite species belonging to 6 families, while prostigmatid mites are represented by 11 mite species belonging to 4 families, in addition to

14 mite species of mesostigmatid mites belonging to 5 families.

1. Suborder: Astigmatida (Canestrini)

1.1. Family: Acaridae

As shown in Table (1) the family Acaridae included two mite species:

1.1.1. *Acars siro* L. was collected from flour, corn, oats and wheat bran in four districts.

1.1.2. *Acars farries* Oud. which was collected from oats, barley, and wheat bran in three districts.

1.2. Family: Tyroglyphidae

The family Tyroglyphidae as shown in Table (1) was represented by 12 mite species:

1.2.1. *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* (Schrank) was found in 3 different sources onion, potato and garlic in three districts.

1.2.2. *Tyrophagus tropicus* Robertson which was extracted from corn, barley and oats in 3 districts.

1.2.3. *Tyrophagus similis* Volgin was associated with three different stored materials corn, barley, and oats in three districts.

1.2.4. *Tyrophagus longior* (Gervais) was infested with flour, wheat bran, and barley at Shubra Qabala, Kafr El Salameh, and Abou Rawash.

1.2.5. *Tyrophagus* sp. was collected inhabiting garlic and potato at Shimandil and Bolak Al-Dakrou.

1.2.6. *Tyroliticus casei* Oud was collected from onion, potato and garlic in 3 districts.

1.2.7. *Tyroborus lini* Oud was found in three different sources flour, potato and garlic in three districts.

1.2.8. *Aleuroglyphus ovatus* (Troupeau) was extracted from wheat bran, oats and barley in three districts.

1.2.9. *Caloglyphus berlese* (Michael) was associated with two different stored materials onion and potato in two districts.

1.2.10. *Caloglyphus mycophagus* (Megnin) was infested with corn, wheat bran, and barley in three districts.

1.2.11. *Mycetoglyphus fungivorus* Oud. was collected inhabiting garlic, potato, and flour in three districts.

1.2.12. *Caloglyphus betae* Attiah was collected from barley, wheat bran, and oats in three districts.

1.3. Family: Rhizoglyphidae

Data in Table (1) shows the family Rhizoglyphidae is represented by only one species:

1.3.1. *Rhizoglyphus robini* Claparede was collected from oats and potato in two districts.

1.4. Family: Chortoglyphidae

The family Chortoglyphidae included one species:

1.4.1. *Chortoglyphus* sp. was collected from potato, flour and barley in two districts.

1.5. Family: Carpoglyphidae

The family Carpoglyphidae included one species:

1.5.1. *Carpoglyphus lactic* (Linne) was collected from garlic and onion in two districts.

1.6. Family: Glycyphagidae

As shown in Table (1) the family Glycyphagidae included three mite species:

1.6.1. *Lepidoglyphus michaeli* Oud. was found in two different sources as wheat bran and barley at Kafr El Salameh and Abou Rawash.

1.6.2. *Lepidoglyphus destructor* (Schrank) was extracted from garlic and potato at Shimandil and Bolak Al-Dakrou.

1.6.3. *Austeroglyphus genicalas* (Vithum) was associated with three different stored materials onion, potato and garlic at Imbaba, Shimandil and Bolak Al-Dakrou.

2. Suborder: Prostigmata (Kramer)

2.1. Family: Cheyletidae

The family Cheyletidae as shown in Table (1) was represented by four mite species:

2.1.1. *Cheyletus eruditus* (Schrank) was extracted from corn at Ashlim district.

2.1.2. *Cheyletus malaccensis* Oud. was associated with three different stored materials garlic, barley and potato in three districts.

2.1.3. *Acaroopsis sollers* Rohdenorf which was infested with wheat bran and oats at Kafr El Salameh and Sheikh Zayed districts.

2.1.4. *Euchyeltia* sp. was collected inhabiting garlic and potato at Shimandil and Bolak Al-Dakroul districts.

2.2. Family: Pyemotidae

As shown in Table (1) the family Pyemotidae included two mite species:

2.2.1. *Pyemotes herfsi* Oud. was collected from flour and barley at Shubra Qabala and Abou Rawash districts.

2.2.2. *Pyemotes tritici* Oud. was collected from flour and barley at Shubra Qabala and Abou Rawash districts.

2.3. Family: Tydeidae

As shown in Table (1) the family Tydeidae included two mite species:

2.3.1. *Tydeus kaochi* Oud. was collected from wheat bran and oats at Kafr El Salameh and Sheikh Zayed districts.

2.3.2. *Pronematus* sp. was collected from corn and oats at Ashlim and 6th of October district.

2.4. Family: Stigmaeidae

The family Stigmaeidae as shown in Table (1) was represented by three mite species:

2.4.1. *Agistimus exertus* Gonzalez was extracted from garlic and potato at Shimandil district.

2.4.2. *Agistimus vulgaris* Gonzalez was associated with two different stored materials flour and barley at Shubra Qabala and Abou Rawash districts.

2.4.3. *Stigmaeus africanus* (Meyer and Ryke) which was infested with onion at Imbaba district.

3. Suborder: Mesostigmata Canestrini

3.1. Family: Ascidae

The family Ascidae as shown in Table (1) was represented by four mite species:

3.1.1. *Proctolealaps orientalis* (Muller) which was extracted from corn at Ashlim district.

3.1.2. *Proctolealaps aegyptiaca* Oud. was infested with flour and oats at Shubra Qabala and Sheikh districts.

3.1.3. *Proctolealaps pgymeus* (Muller) which was infested with wheat bran and oats at Kafr El Salameh and 6th of October districts.

3.1.4. *Dendrolaelaps rasmii* Nasr and Mersal was collected inhabiting barley and oats at Abou Rawash and 6th of October districts.

3.2. Family: Rhodacaridae

The family Rhodacaridae as shown in Table (1) was represented by four mite species:

3.2.1. *Rhodacarillus* sp. was extracted from corn and barley at Ashlim and Abou Rawash districts.

3.2.2. *Lasiosius lindquisti* Nawar and Nasr was infested with garlic at Shimandil district.

3.2.3. *Blattisocius keageni* (Fox) was infested with onion and potato at Quesna and Bolak Al-Dakroul districts.

3.2.4. *Blattisocius tarsalis* (Berlese) was collected inhabiting wheat bran and barley at Kafr El Salameh and Abou Rawash districts.

3.3. Family: Laelapidae

The family Laelapidae as shown in Table (1) was represented by four mite species:

3.3.1. *Hypoaspis* sp. was extracted from garlic at Shimandil district.

3.3.2. *Csmolaelaps keni* (Berlese) was associated with two different stored materials corn and oats at Ashlim and Sheikh Zayed districts.

3.3.3. *Androlaelaps zaheri* Hafez, El-Badry and Nasr was infested with wheat

bran and potato at Kafr El Salameh and Bolak Al-Dakrour districts.

3.3.4. *Ololaelaps* sp. was collected inhabiting flour and barley at Shubra Qabala and Abou Rawash districts.

3.4. Family: Uropodidae

Data in Table (1) show the family Uropodidae is represented by only one species:

3.4.1. *Uropoilla marginata* (Koch) was collected from garlic and oats in two districts.

3.5. Family: Parasitidae

The family Parasitidae included one species:

3.5.1. *Parasitus consanguineous* Oud. and Voigts was collected from garlic and onion in two districts.

Survey research associated with stored product mites was done by many authors; Hughes (1961), Zaher (1986) and Taha (1985) for prostigmatid mites and for acarid mites. Also, Attiah (1969) studied the tyroglyphid mites, while El-Naggar *et al.* (1992); El-Sayed and Ghallab (2007) and Yassin *et al.* (2018) and Halawa *et al.* (2021) recorded several mite species associated with stored products. In their study, Zaher *et al.* (1986) noticed that members of the families Cheyletidae and Acaridae were the most common mites, found in many stored seeds and food products in Upper Egypt.

Table (1): Occurrence of the mites associated with stored products in some localities in Egypt.

Family	Species	Host	Locality
Suborder: Astigmata (Canestrini)			
Acaridae	1. <i>Acars siro</i> L.	Flour - Corn – Oats - Wheat bran	Shubra Qabala, Kafr El Salameh, Ashlim, Sheikh Zayed.
	2. <i>Acars farries</i> Oud.	Oats – Barley - Wheat bran	Kafr El Salameh, Abou Rawash, Sheikh Zayed.
Tyroglyphidae	1. <i>Tyrophagus putrescentiae</i> (Schrank)	Onion – Potato – Garlic	Quesna, Shimandil, Bolak Al-Dakrour.
	2. <i>Tyrophagus tropicus</i> Robertson	Corn – Barley – Oats	Ashlim, Abou Rawash,. Sheikh Zayed.
	3. <i>Tyrophagus similis</i> Volgin	Corn – Barley – Oats	Ashlim, Abou Rawash, 6th of October.
	4. <i>Tyrophagus longior</i> (Gervais)	Flour – Wheat Bran- barley	Shubra Qabala, Kafr El Salameh, Abou Rawash.
	5. <i>Tyrophagus</i> sp	Garlic – Potato	Shimandil, Bolak Al-Dakrour.
	6. <i>Tyroliticus casei</i> Oud.	Onion – Potato – Garlic	Imbaba, Shimandil, Bolak Al-Dakrour.
	7. <i>Tyroborus lini</i> Oud.	Flour – Potato- Garlic	Shubra Qabala, Shimandil, Bolak Al-Dakrour.
	8. <i>Aleuroglyphus ovatus</i> (Troupeau)	Wheat Bran– Oats – Barley	Kafr El Salameh, Abou Rawash, Sheikh Zayed.
	9. <i>Caloglyphus Berlese</i> (Michael)	Onion – Potato	Quesna, Bolak Al-Dakrour.
	10. <i>Caloglyphus mycophagus</i> (Megnin)	Corn – Wheat Bran- Barley	Kafr El Salameh, Ashlim, Abou Rawash.
	11. <i>Mycetoglyphus fungivorus</i> Oud.	Garlic – Potato – Flour	Shubra Qabala, Shimandil, Bolak Al-Dakrour.
	12. <i>Caloglyphus betae</i> Attiah	Barley – Wheat Bran- Oats	Kafr El Salameh, Abou Rawash, 6th of October.

Table (1): Continued

Family	Species	Host	Locality
Rhizoglyphidae	<i>Rhizoglyphus robini</i> Claparede	Oats – Potato	Sheikh Zayed, Bolak Al-Dakrou.
Chortoglyphidae	<i>Chortoglyphus</i> sp	Potato – Flour – Barley	Shubra Qabala, Abou Rawash, Bolak Al-Dakrou.
Carpoglyphidae	<i>Carpoglyphus lactic</i> (Linne)	Garlic – onion	Quesna, Shimandil.
Glycyphagidae	1. <i>Lepidoglyphus michaeli</i> Oud.	Wheat Bran- Barley	Kafr El Salameh, Abou Rawash.
	2. <i>Lepidoglyphus destructor</i> (Schrank)	Garlic – potato	Shimandil, Bolak Al-Dakrou.
	3. <i>Austeroglyphus genicalas</i> (Vithum)	Onion- potato – Garlic	Imbaba, Shimandil, Bolak Al-Dakrou.
Suborder: Prostigmata (Kramer)			
Cheyletidae	1. <i>Cheyletus eruditus</i> (Schrank)	Corn	Ashlim
	2. <i>Cheyletus malaccensis</i> Oud.	Garlic – Barley – potato	Shimandil, Abou Rawash Bolak Al-Dakrou
	3. <i>Acaroopsis sollers</i> Rohdenorf	Wheat Bran- Oats	Kafr El Salameh, Sheikh Zayed.
	4. <i>Euchyeletia</i> sp	Garlic – potato	Shimandil, Bolak Al-Dakrou
Pyemotidae	1. <i>Pyemotes herfsi</i> Oud.	Flour – Barley	Shubra Qabala. Abou Rawash
	2. <i>Pyemotes tritici</i> Oud.	Flour – Barley	Shubra Qabala, Abou Rawash
Tydeidae	1. <i>Tydeus Kochi</i> Oud.	Wheat Bran- Oats	Kafr El Salameh, Sheikh Zayed
	2. <i>Pronematus</i> sp	Corn – Oats	Ashlim, 6th of October
Stigmaeidae	1. <i>Agistimus exertus</i> Gonzalez	Garlic – potato	Shimandil, Bolak Al-Dakrou
	2. <i>Agistimus valgaris</i> Gonzalez	Flour – Barley	Shubra Qabala, Abou Rawash
	3. <i>Stigmaeus africanus</i> (Meyer & Ryke)	Onion	Imbaba
Suborder: Mesostigmata Canestrini			
Ascidae	1. <i>Proctolealaps orientalis</i> (Muller)	Corn	Ashlim
	2. <i>Proctolealaps aegyptiaca</i> Oud.	Flour – Oats	Shubra Qabala, Sheikh Zayed.
	3. <i>Proctolealaps pygmeus</i> (Muller)	Wheat Bran- Oats	Kafr El Salameh 6th of October
	4. <i>Dendrolaelaps rasmii</i> Nasr & Mersal	Barley – Oats	Abou Rawash 6th of October
Rhodacaridae	1. <i>Rhodacarillus</i> sp	Corn – Barley	Ashlim, Abou Rawash
	2. <i>Lasiosius lindquisti</i> Nawar and Nasr	Garlic	Shimandil
	3. <i>Blattisocius keageni</i> (Fox)	Onion – Potato	Quesna Bolak Al-Dakrou
	4. <i>Blattisocius tarsalis</i> (Berlese)	Wheat Bran- Barley	Kafr El Salameh Abou Rawash

Table (1): Continued

Family	Species	Host	Locality
Laelapidae	1. <i>Hypoaspis</i> sp	Garlic	Shimandil
	2. <i>Csmolaelaps keni</i> (Berlese)	Corn- Oats -	Ashlim, Sheikh Zayed
	3. <i>Androlaelaps zaheiri</i> Hafez, El-Badry and Nasr	Wheat Bran– potato	Kafr El Salameh Bolak Al-Dakrouer
	4. <i>Ololaelaps</i> sp	Flour – Barley	Shubra Qabala, Abou Rawash
Uropodidae	<i>Uropoilla marginata</i> (Koch)	Garlic – Oats	Shimandil, Sheikh Zayed
Parasitidae.	<i>Parasitus consanguineous</i> Oud. and Voigts	Onion – Garlic	Shimandil, Quesna

References

- Attiah, H. H. (1969):** Tyroglyphoid mites associated with stored food in United Arabic Republic UAR. Min. Agric. Plant protection Department Tech. Bull., 10: 1-51.
- El-Naggar, M. E.; Rakha, M. A. and Taha, H. A. (1992):** Mites of stored grains in Egypt. Egypt. J. Biol. Pest Control, 2(2): 109-122.
- El-Sanady, M. A. (2005):** Studies on some stored product mites and their predators. Ph.D. Thesis, Fac. Sc. (Girls) Al-Azhar University.
- El-Sayed, F. and Ghallab, M. (2007):** Survey on Mites Associated with Major Insect Pests Infesting Stored Grains in Middle Delta. ACARINES: Journal of the Egyptian Society of Acarology, 1: 29-38.
- Fawzy, M. M. H. (1996):** Biological studies on house dust mites in Egypt. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. Agric. Cairo University.
- Halawa, Z. A.; Abdelfattah, N. A. H. and Zinhoum, R. A. (2021):** Survey of some mites associated with stored grains and their products from different governorates. J. of Plant Protection and Pathology, Mansoura Univ., 12 (11): 823-826.
- Halawa, Z.A. (2003):** Mites associated with stored food stuffs in Alexandria Governorate. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt., 80: 47-58.
- Hoda, F. M.; El-Naggar, M. E.; Taha, H. A. and EL-Beheiry, M. M. (1990):** Prostigmati mites are associated with stored products. Agric. Res. Rev., 68: 77-85.
- Hughes, A. M. (1961):** The mites of stored food. Min. of Agr., Fish. and Food Tech. Bull., 9: 278.
- Hughes, A. M. (1976):** The mites of stored food and houses Tech. Bull. Minist. Agric. Fish. Food, Bull., 9: 400.
- Krantz, G. W. and Walter, D. E. (2009):** A Manual of Acarology. Texas Tech. Univ. Press, pp.807.
- Metwally, A. M. (1976):** Ecological and biological studies on super family parasitoida in Mostorod Region. Ph.D. Thesis, Fac. of Agric., Al- Azhar University.
- Musken, H.; Franz, J. T.; Wahl, R.; Paap, A.; Cromwell, O.; Masuch, G. and Bergmann, K. C. (2003):** Sensitization to different mite species in German farmers: in vitro analyses. J. of investigational Allergology and Clinical Immunology, 13(1): 26-35.
- Summers, F. M. and Price, D. W. (1970):** Review of the mite

- family Cheyletidae. Univ. Calif. Pubi. Entomol., 61: pp.153.
- Taha, H. A. (1985):** Morphological and biological studies on some mites associated with stored products. Ph. D. Thesis, 159 pp., Fac. Agric. Al-Azhar University.
- Wafa, A. K.; Zaher, M. A.; El-Kifl, A. M. and Hegazy, M. A. (1966):** Survey on stored grain and seed mites (Acarina). Bull. Ent. Soc., Egypt, 50:225-232.
- Yassin, E.M.A.; Osman, S. A. A. and Rahouma, A. K. A. (2018):** Occurrence of different mites associated with different cereals and legumes crops in different locations of Egypt. Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci. (A. Entomology), 11(4): 51- 58.
- Zaher, M. A.; Mohamed, M. I. And Abdel-Halim, S. M. (1986):** Incidence of mites associated with stored seeds and food products in Upper Egypt. Experimental and Applied Acarology, 2(1): 19-24.
- Zaher, M. A.; Mohamed, M. I. and Abdel-Halim, S. M. (1984):** Incidence of mites associated with stored seeds and food products in Upper Egypt. 17th Int. Cong. Entomol. Hamburg. F. R. G., pp.460.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Occurrences and risk assessment of pesticide residue in tea in Egypt

Hoda, M. Refai; Sherif, M. El- Safty; Mohammed, Abd El-Aziz and Mahmoud, M. Ghuniem

Central Agricultural Pesticides Lab., Agricultural Research Center , Dokki, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 25 / 4 /2022

Accepted: 28 / 6 /2022

Keywords

Tea, pesticides, residue, risk assessment, and Egypt.

Abstract:

Tea is one of the most consumed beverages after water, but unfortunately, the application of pesticides and heavy metals in crops make it unsafe for use. This research was conducted to evaluate the risk of heavy metals and pesticides in samples of natural source tea (Gardens) and different local market brands, the tea pests showed a higher tolerance/ resistance status due to the formation of a greater amount of esterases, glutathione S-transferase and acetylcholinesterase, using GC-MS/MS analysis and LC-MS/MS analysis for 450 pesticides residues, no pesticide residues were detected in 30% of samples, on the other hand, a 60% had detectable pesticide residues, 10% exceeding the MRLs and the highest frequently detected pesticides were tolfenpyrad followed by thiamethoxam. ADI showed that long term exposure of Egyptian consumers to pesticide residues through the consumption of some tea does not associate with health risks. However, it should be borne in mind that the current study is limited to tea.

Introduction

A pesticide may be a substance or combination of substances proposed for thwarting, demolishing, repelling, or diminishing the hurt of any vermin (Sushma *et al.*, 2015). Also, pesticides are any substance or blend of substances of chemical or organic fixings aiming for repulsing, crushing, or controlling any pest, or for controlling plant development. The bug can be frightening crawlies, plant microorganisms, weeds, molluscs, feathered creatures, warm-blooded creatures, angle nematodes (Roundworms), and living beings that equal individuals for food, devastate property, spread or offer assistance pass on or spread afflictions, or are seen as

an unsettling influence (Son *et al.*, 2010).

The most well-known utilized pesticides incorporate insect poisons, herbicides, fungicides and rodenticides (Winchester *et al.*, 2009). The other less eminent pesticides incorporate advancement controllers, plant defoliants, surface sanitisers and a few pool manufactured substances (Bhandari *et al.*, 2019).

Most customarily, pesticides are utilized in prosperity ranges and agricultural yields. They are important in common prosperity for slaughtering vectors of the disease, like mosquitoes whereas, bothers hurting agricultural yields are slaughtered by pesticides. Regularly, pesticides are conceivably

noxious to other non-target life shapes, counting individuals. Along these lines, it is vital to utilize them safely and organize them fittingly (Elbaz *et al.*, 2009).

Organochlorine insecticides and their metabolites (Sigma DDT, sigma HCH, HCB, Heptachlor, Epoxide heptachlor, and Aldrin) were found in samples of black and green tea, and fruit tea. The mean concentration of the organochlorine compounds in the black tea ranged from 0.0002 to 0.003 mg/kg of product, and in the green and fruit teas from 0.0001 to 0.003 mg/kg, in no case the violation of the Maximum Residues Limits was observed K. (Góralczyk *et al.*, 2000).

The tea pests showed a higher tolerance/ resistance status due to formation of greater amount of esterases, glutathione S-transferase and acetylcholinesterase. Thus, over reliance on pesticides end up with pesticide residue in making tea (DDT - 10.4-47.1%; endosulfan - 41.1-98.0%; dicofol- 0.0-82.4%; ethion - 0.0-36.2%; cypermethrin - 6.0- 45.1%) (Gurusubramanian *et al.*, 2008).

In this study we make a survey to detect pesticide residues in tea and estimation of daily and weekly intake.

Materials and methods

1. Instruments and apparatus:

Agilent Gas Chromatograph system 7890A equipped with tandem mass spectrometer 7000C series GC. Includes the Triple Quadrupole GC/MS/ MS EI mainframe, EI ion source, ion gauge controller with routine femtogram-level limits of detection and quantitation ultra-low noise, superior selectivity, inlet: splitless, carrier gas: helium with flow rate 1.830 ml/ min.

Agilent technologies: HP-5 MS capillary column (5 % biphenyl to 95 % dimethylsiloxane). Column internal diameter (ID): 0.25 mm, film thickness: 0.52 μ m, folumn length: 30 m was

used. Agilent high-performance liquid chromatography equipped with tandem mass spectrometer API 4000 Qtrap (Applied biosystems) triple quadrupole mass spectrometer LC-MS/ MS with mass range m/z 50 to 2800 and equipped with atmospheric pressure ion source (Turbo V) that accepts either electro sprayer ionization (TurboIon spray) and atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (ESI/APCI) probes and can measure in negative and positive modes was used.

A Perkin Elmer quadrupole inductively coupled-mass spectrometer (Q-ICP-MS) NexION 300D - USA was used. Agilent performance liquid chromatography HPLC model HP 1100/1200 series consisting of a quaternary pump (G1311A), vacuum degasser (G13779A), autosampler (G1313A), and diode array detector (G1315D) was used.

2. Materials and reagents:

Acetonitrile, 99.9 % HPLC grade was purchased from Lab Scan. Methanol 99.9 % HPLC grade was purchased from Merck. Acetone, 99.9 % HPLC grade was purchased from Lab Scan. N-hexane, 97 % was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Suprapur[®] concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) 65 % (w/w) was purchased from Merck Germany was used.

Nitric acid 2 % (v/v) was prepared as described in anhydrous magnesium sulphate fine powder, Magnesium sulphate grit was purchased from Fluka. Sodium chloride and sodium hydroxide 99 % were purchased from Reidel de Haen. Disodium Hydrogen citrate sesquihydrate and trisodium citrate dehydrate were purchased from Fluka.

Ethyl Acetate, 99.8 % was purchased from Lab Scan. Tetradecane, 99% from HPLC grade was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Formic Acid 98-100 % was purchased from Riedel–de Haen. Pesticide reference standards

purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Augsburg, Germany), with purities > 95 % were used to prepare stock solutions dissolved in methanol for the standard stock solution of LC-MS/MS and toluene for the stock solution of GC-MS/MS.

3. Standards preparation:

Reference standard solutions of concentration 1000 µg/ml of pesticides residues were prepared and were kept at -20 ± 2 °C; for LC-MS/MS stock solutions using acetonitrile and for GC-MS/MS using (hexane: acetone 9:1). The solvents used are appropriate to the analyte solubility, stability and method of analysis (i.e. not negatively influencing the pesticides).

Calibration mixtures of concentration levels 0.005, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5 µg/ml for LC-MS/MS, and, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5 µg/ml for GC-MS/MS were prepared and stored in refrigerator at the desired. Also, a working standard of aldrin with a concentration of 0.1 µg/ml was prepared in a mixture of n-hexane/acetone (9:1) to use as an injection standard for GC-MS/MS. For based on standards preparation procedure described.

4. Sample collection

In this study, 10 tea samples representing different brands and sources packaged in different packaging materials were collected randomly from local markets in Giza, Egypt and subjected to pesticides, it differs from type of tea such as black, green, and Oolong. The samples were

coded and stored before analysis at conditions similar to those of retail shops.

5. Determination

5.1. GC-MS/MS analysis

The initial oven temperature of 70 °C for 2 min, heating from 70 to 150 °C at 25 °C /min, heating from 150 to 200 °C at 3 °C/ min, heating from 200 to 280 °C at 8 °C/min, holding for 10 min. The total run time will be 42 min. Quantification of the pesticides was performed by comparing the peak areas of the pesticides to a calibration curve of the standards, and multitude point calibration was used.

5.2. LC-MS/MS analysis

The ESI source was used in the positive mode, and N₂ nebulizer, curtain and other gas settings were optimized according to recommendations made by the manufacturer; source temperature was 400°C, ion spray potential, 5500 V, declutter potential and collision energy were optimized using a Harvard apparatus syringe pump by introducing individual pesticide solutions into the MS instrument to allow optimization of the MS/MS conditions.

The Multiple reactions monitoring mode (MRM) was used in which one MRM was used for quantitation and the other was used for confirmation. As the first choice, the protonated ion was chosen as the precursor ion (Q1). By varying the collision energy for the precursor ion, the products ions for each compound were optimized by selecting the most intense products ion (Q3) Table (1).

Table (1): Methods performance for some pesticides residues.

Pesticides	Method	LOQ	REC %	RSD	R ²	P.	1 st	2 nd	R.
Abmectin	LC/MS/MS	0.005	88 – 116	17	0.9998	890.5	305.1	307.1	9.09
Acephate	LC/MS/MS	0.005	70 – 110	19	0.9999	184	143.0	49	1.50
Acetamiprid	LC/MS/MS	0.005	85 - 109	13	0.9999	223.1	125.9	89.9	1.96
Atrazine	LC/MS/MS	0.005	82 – 119	7	0.9998	216.1	174.0	68.1	3.91
Azoxystrobin	GC/MS/MS	0.005	77 - 118	13	0.9999	404.1	372	329.1	4.94
Bifenazate	LC/MS/MS	0.005	82 – 106	17	0.9999	301.2	198.1	170.1	5.63
Boscalid	LC/MS/MS	0.005	89 – 117	4	0.9998	343	370	343	5.2
Buprofezin	GC/MS/MS	0.005	80 – 110	6	0.9999	306.2	201.1	306.2	7.87
Carbendazim	LC/MS/MS	0.005	86 – 109	10	0.9998	192.1	160.1	192.1	1.87
Chlorpyrifos	GC/MS/MS	0.005	73 – 100	8	0.9999	349.9	97	197.8	8.21
Cyproconazole I	LC/MS/MS	0.005	94 - 111	20	0.9999	292.1	70.1	125.1	5.65
Etoxazole	LC/MS/MS	0.005	77 – 102	7	0.9999	360.2	141	113.1	8.54
Fenbuconazole	LC/MS/MS	0.005	88 – 118	2	0.9999	337.1	125.1	70.1	6.08
Iprodione	GC/MS/MS	0.005	84 – 107	5	0.9998	330.0	244.9	246.9	6.10
Neburon	LC/MS/MS	0.005	98 – 117	3	0.9999	275.1	88.0	57.1	6.28
Phenthoate	GC/MS/MS	0.005	79 – 106	8	0.9999	321.0	247.1	163.1	6.32
Profenofos	GC/MS/MS	0.005	77 – 101	7	0.9999	375.0	304.8	302.8	7.60
Ortho phenylphenol (OPP)	GC/MS/MS	0.005	80 – 104	4	0.9999	170.07	141.06	115.05	11
Propiconazol	GC/MS/MS	0.005	94 – 115	4	0.9998	342.1	69.1	159.1	6.64
Pyridaben	GC/MS/MS	0.005	87 – 103	8	0.9999	365.2	147.1	309.1	8.93
Pyriproxyfen	GC/MS/MS	0.005	85 – 116	6	0.9998	322.2	96.1	78.1	8.10
Pyrimethanil	GC/MS/MS	0.005	77 – 104	4	0.9999	200.1	107.2	82.0	4.68
Tebuconazole	GC/MS/MS	0.005	94 - 108	5	0.9998	308.1	70.0	124.9	6.49

P. Precursor ion R. Retention time(min) 1st. 1st Qualifier 2nd. 2nd Qualifier

6. Quality control

For pesticides residues, the quantifications limits of pesticides residues were 5 µg/kg. The measurement uncertainty is expressed as expanded uncertainty and in terms of relative standard deviation (At 95% confidence level) is within the range of ± 50 % see Table (1).

7. Estimation of daily and weekly intake

Risk assessment is calculated by comparing the concentrations of residues detected, with the established acceptable daily intake (ADI). The calculated EDI was obtained by multiplying the mean concentrations of detected and the number of tea consumed based on WHO/Global Environment Monitoring System-Food Contamination Monitoring and Assessment Program average consumption diets (WHO/GEMS/FOODS) (Ghuniem *et al.*, 2020 and GEMS/Foods, 2012). Acceptable daily intake (ADI) is a very import concept in chemical risk assessment. It is defined as the maximum amount of a chemical that can be ingested daily over a lifetime with no appreciable health risk. We will calculate it using this equation.

$$EDI = \sum RLi \times Fi / Bw$$

RLi = residue level of the vegetable;

Fi = food consumption data

BW= Body weight.

Results and discussion

1. Pesticides occurrences:

Pesticides used in agricultural areas in the world to eliminate pests that

damage the fruits, vegetables and herbs provide an unquestionable benefit for agricultural production. However, after their application, pesticide residues remain on the crops and constitute a risk for the human health because of their toxicity so the monitoring data obtained from this study enable decision makers to take corrective actions towards risk management. Pesticide residues are substances that remain on or in air, water, soil, or food following its use. Even food grown without direct pesticide use can still contain residues due to spray drift from nearby farms, long range air transport, or existing groundwater or soil contamination (Magkos *et al.*, 2003). Samples were analyzed for detection of 450 pesticides. The MRLs of Codex Alimentarius were used for comparison when those limits were available. In the absence of Codex MRLs, European limits were used.

A total of ten samples of tea during 2019 was collected from the Egyptian local market. The detected pesticides, minimum, maximum, detected levels, numbers and percentages of violating samples are shown in Table and Figure. Table (2) and Figure (1) shows the residue level of different pesticides detected and the percentage of samples with residue level exceeding MRL in tea samples during 2021. No pesticide residues were detected in 30% of samples on the other hand a 60% had detectable pesticide residues, 10% exceeding the MRLs.

Figure (1): The contamination and the violation percentage in tea samples during 2020.

Table (2): Show the mean, maximum and minimum concentration.

NO.	Pesticide	EU Limits	Mean	Max	Min
1.	Acetamiprid	0.05	0.10	0.16	0.06
1.	Ethion	NO	0.12	0.12	0.12
2.	Thiacloprid	NO	0.06	0.06	0.06
3.	Thiamethoxam	20	0.27	0.27	0.27
4.	Fenpyroximate	8	0.02	0.02	0.02
5.	Propargite	5	0.03	0.03	0.03
6.	Chloropyrifos	2	0.02	0.03	0.01
7.	Hexaconazole	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.03
8.	Bifenthrin	0.5	0.07	0.18	0.01
9.	Cyflutrin	NO	0.03	0.05	0.01
10.	Cyhalothrin Lambda	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.01
11.	Cypermethrin	15	0.05	0.09	0.01
12.	Deltamethrin	5	0.04	0.05	0.02
13.	Fenpropathin	3	0.02	0.04	0.01
14.	Oxyfluorfen	NO	0.01	0.01	0.01
15.	Propoconazole	NO	<LOQ	0	0
16.	Indoxcarb	5	0.02	0.02	0.01
17.	Pyridaben	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.02
18.	Triazophos	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01
19.	Quinalphos	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.03
20.	Metalaxyl	NO	0.03	0.03	0.03
21.	Buprofezin	0.05	0.11	0.13	0.09
22.	Lufenuron	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.01
23.	Tolfenpyrad	30	0.39	0.39	0.39
24.	Imidacloprid	50	0.06	0.08	0.03
25.	Carbendazim	0.1	0.07	0.07	0.07
26.	Chlorantraniliprole	0.02	<LOQ	0	0
27.	Chlofenapyr	60	0.07	0.1	0.03

The violated compounds in tea samples were acetamiprid, ethion, thiacloprid, thiamethoxam, fenpyroximate, propargite, chloropyrifos, hexaconazole, thiacloprid, fenpyroximate, bifenthrin, biphenyl cyflutrin, cyhalothrin lambda, cypermethrin, deltamethrin, fenpropathin, oxyfluorfen, propoconazole, indoxcarb, pyridaben, triazophos, quinalphos, metalaxyl, buprofezin lufenuron, tolfenpyrad, imidacloprid, carbendazim, chlorantraniliprole, chlofenapyr, carbendazim. The highest frequently detected pesticides were tolfenpyrad followed by thiamethoxam. It differs from type of tea such as black, green, and Oolong. It is required to

compensate the matrix effects by a matrix-matched calibration which could be more efficient than by ECHO technique in LC/MS and GC/MS system. In this study, analytically confirmed pesticides-free organic sample were used as blank matrix. The blank green tea sample was selected as the representative matrix for green and the blank black tea sample was selected as the representative matrix for black samples. For the determination of matrix effects, the responses of the standard solutions prepared in solvent were compared with the responses of the standard solutions prepared in pesticides-free blank tea sample.

The safety qualities were paid more attention by the consumers all over the world. For the purpose of

control of tea pests in the tea production, chemical pesticides are applied. Due to the following aspects, the residue level on/in tea plant is much higher than that on/in other crops under the same applied dosage. As with other crops, control of pests of pesticide is widely used in tea production. However, due to the above mentioned characteristics that differentiate from other crops, the suitable pesticides used in tea production are somewhat different from the pesticides used in other crops. That is high efficiency to target pests, low acute toxicity, easy to degrade under natural condition, no taint to tea aroma. Up to now, the popular chemical pesticides used in tea production are as follows : Endosulfa , Imidacloprid > Bifenthrin, Cypermethrin > Deltamethrin > Acetamiprid > Propagite. Overview of the MRL violations per country of origin China was 17.6 % in Non-compliant Products including tea, According to the results of determination of China tea sample (Around 50,000 tea samples), those pesticides that higher than the MRL standards of EU are as follows: Fenvalerate > Fenpropathrin > Imidacloprid > Acetamiprid. However, the percentage of tea samples that higher than the MRL standards issued by EU was decreased significantly in recent years.

The results of recovery as indicated by relative standard deviations confirmed that the methodology, including extraction and cleanup procedure are suitable for the tea matrix (Table 3). The QuEChERS method offered the limit of quantification of 0.002 for 450 pesticides. The number of samples categorized as per residue levels are tabulated in Table (1). Percentage distribution of samples of different residues is presented in Figure (1). Acetamiprid residues were detected in

samples no. 4, 9 and 10 with concentration (0.16, 0.06 and 0.07) mg/kg of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. Ethion, thiacloprid, thiamethoxam, fenpyroximate, propargite, hexaconazole, thiacloprid, fenpyroximate, propargite, hexaconazole, thiacloprid, fenpyroximate, oxyflurofen and propoconazole were detected in sample no. 4 with concentration (0.12, 0.06, 0.27, 0.02, 0.03, 0.03, 0.01, 0.01 , 0.01 and LOQ) mg/kg of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. In 1.92 % of total samples analysed, dicofol and hexaconazole residues were detected which were below the EU MRL of 20.0 and 0.05 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, respectively. Ethion and quinalphos were detected in 3.63 and 13.89 % of the samples, respectively, which were below the EU MRL of 3.0 and 0.1 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (Kottiappan *et al.*, 2013). Chloropyrifos residues were detected in samples no. 3, 4, 5, 9 and 10 with concentration (0.01, 0.01, 0.01, 0.02 and 0.03) mg/kg of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. Bifenthrin residues were detected in samples no. 4, 6, 9 and 10 with concentration (0.01, 0.04, 0.06 and 0.18) mg/kg of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. Biphenyl residues were detected in samples no. 3 and 6 with concentration (0.01 and 0.01) mg/kg of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. Cyflutrin residues were detected in samples no. 4 and 10 with concentration (0.01, and 0.05) mg/kg of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. Cyhalothrin Lambda residues were detected in samples no. 4, 6, 9 and 10 with concentration (0.02, 0.01, 0.02 and

0.06) mg/kg of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. cypermethrin residues were detected in samples no. 4, 5, 9 and 10 with concentration (0.06, 0.01, 0.02 and 0.09) mg/kg of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. Deltamethrin residues were detected in samples no. 4 and 6 with concentration (0.02 and 0.05) mg/kg of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. Fenpropathin residues were detected in samples no. 4, 6, 8, 9 and 10 with concentration (0.03, 0.01, 0.01 and 0.04) mg/kg of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. Indoxcarb, pyridaben, triazophos, quinalphos, metalaxyl, lufenuron, tolfenpyrad, imidacloprid, carbendazim, chlorantraniliprole, and chlofenapyr were detected in sample no. 9 and 10 with concentration (0.02 and 0.01 indoxcarb, 0.02 and <LOQ pyridaben, 0.03 and 0.03. Triazophos 0.01 and 0.01, quinalphos and metalaxyl in sample no. 10 is 0.03 mg/kg, lufenuron 0.04 and 0.01, tolfenpyrad in sample no. 9 is 0.39 mg/kg, imidacloprid 0.03 and 0.08, carbendazim and Chlorantraniliprole is in sample no.10 (0.07 and <LOQ) of the total samples analysed which were below the codex alimentarius MRL value. Apart from this sample no. 9 and 10 showed the presence of buprofezin and chlofenapyr residues (0.13 and 0.09) and (0.03 and 0.1) respectively, however, the contents were exceeding the codex alimentarius MRL. Among the samples surveyed in Munnar and Nilgiris region, 6.17 and 19.70 % of the total samples showed detectable levels of residues of pesticides. Among the samples surveyed in gudalur and wayanad (India), 35.29 and 6.52 %, respectively,

of the total samples showed detectable levels of pesticide residues (Kottiappan *et al.*, 2013). It is well known that only hot water extract of black tea (Tea brew) is used for human consumption and not the green tea as such. Hence, it is evident that the possible route of exposure to pesticide residues is the black tea. The real cause depends on the quantum of the residues leached from black tea into tea brew and not on the mere presence of residues in the black tea. All the regulatory agencies, including (Chinese and japan) have fixed the maximum residue levels of pesticides in black/green tea since these are the commodities being traded. However, the residues of pesticides that leach into the brew is abysmally low, and in the majority of cases, the residues do not leach into the brew, making it safer than any other similar drink. The leaching of residues into the brew depends on the solubility of the pesticide in water (Jaggi *et al.*, 2001).

Earlier large-scale survey of teas produced in the tea factories of South India had been carried out for a period of 3 years from 2006 to 2008 and tea samples were analysed for the residues of certain pesticides. Analytical data proved that <0.5 % of tea samples had pesticide residues which were below their MRL (Seenivasan and Muraleedharan, 2011). Extensive surveys were carried out during 2009 to 2011. Though the residues of ethion, quinalphos, hexaconazole, dicofol, propargite and fenpropathrin were most commonly found, only one sample exceeded the MRL fixed for hexaconazole by European Union (Kottiappan *et al.*, 2013).

Table (3): Recovery of fortified pesticides in tea.

Pesticide	Fortification level	Recovery%
Bifenthrin	0.01	86
Buprofezin	0.01	74
Chlofenapyr	0.01	72
Chloropyrifos	0.01	84
Cyflutrin	0.01	91
cypermethrin	0.01	89
Deltamethrin	0.01	82
Fenpropathin	0.01	79

2 . The risk assessment of pesticide residue in tea:

Acceptable daily intake (ADI) is a very important concept in chemical risk assessment. It is defined as the maximum amount of a chemical that can be ingested daily over a lifetime with no appreciable health risk as Table (4).

Humans can get exposed to various chemical substances via oral route (i.e, eating food, drinking

groundwater, hand to mouth transfer). It is necessary to determine the maximum amount of a chemical that can be ingested on a daily basis to protect human health. That is why we need to calculate the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI). For pesticide residues and food contaminants, ADI may also be called Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI). The US Environmental Protection Agency has replaced ADI and TDI.

Table (4): Accepted daily intake.

No.	Pesticide	Accepted daily Intake (Range) mg/kg bw.
1	Acetamiprid	0.07
2	Ethion	0.01
3	Thiacloprid	0.01
4	Thiamethoxam	0.01
5	Fenpyroximate	0.01
6	Propargite	0.01
7	Chloropyrifos	0.01
8	Hexaconazole	0.01
9	Bifenthrin	0.01
10	Biphenyl	0.125
11	Cyflutrin	0.01
12	Cyhalothrin Lambda	0.125
13	Cypermethrin	0.02
14	Deltamethrin	0.02
15	Fenpropathin	0.02
16	Oxyfluorfen	0.01
17	Propoconazole	0.07
18	Indoxcarb	0.01
19	Pyridaben	0.01
20	Triazophos	0.01
21	Quinalphos	0.01
22	Metalaxyl	0.08
23	Buprofezin	0.01
24	Lufenuron	0.01
25	Tolfenpyrad	0.01
26	Imidacloprid	0.06
27	Carbendazim	0.03
28	Chlorantraniliprole	0.01
29	Chlofenapyr	0.03

The present results showed that, the long term exposure of the Egyptian consumers to pesticide residues through the consumption of some tea does not associate with health risk. However, it should be borne in mind that the current study is limited to a tea. Moreover, the estimated risk assessment via long-term exposure is based on toxicological evaluation of the single compounds and not based on an evaluation of cumulative exposure to multiple pesticide residues.

Pesticides can have a cumulative "toxic loading" effect both in the immediate and long term, and each person accumulates and responds to chemicals in a way that is biochemically and biographically unique. From birth, we build up a chemical "body burden" that reflects a combination of childhood and workplace exposures, pesticide residues on food, chemicals in home and personal care products and the quality of air and water in our communities.

The process of dietary pesticide risk assessment has been presented the process estimation of pesticide residue levels, estimation of food consumption patterns, and characterization of risk based on a comparison of exposure estimates with toxicological criteria have been identified. Each component of the process is subject to considerable uncertainty that may compromise the accuracy of the final risk assessment. In estimating pesticide residue levels, common practices range from highly theoretical models assuming that all residues are present at a predetermined level (Typically at the tolerance level) to the use of market basket survey data obtained at the time the food is ready for consumption (GadAlla *et al.*, 2015; Kawahara *et al.*, 2007; Darko and Akoto, 2008 and Osman, 2011).

In this study, analysis by Q-ICP-MS has *been* a fast, simple, and

reliable methodology for the determination of some potentially toxic elements in tea samples, while QuEChERS extraction method followed by analysis by GC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS has been a fast, easy, and reliable methodology for the determination residues in tea samples after acetonitrile extraction/partitioning and cleanup by dispersive SPE. We get 60% had detectable pesticide residues, 10%, exceeding the MRLs also pesticides detected non-carcinogenic risk and carcinogenic risk were evaluated, but that even after a long time consumption gets bad effect on human and basket survey data obtained at the time the food is ready for consumption.

These kinds of studies would contribute to the identification of low-quality fruit tea products on the market and assure a high safety profile of tea.

References

- Bhandari, G.; Zomer, P.; Atreya, K.; Mol, H. G. J.; Yang, X. and Geissen, V. (2019):** Pesticide residues in Nepalese vegetables and potential health risks. *Environmental Research*, 172: 511–521.
- Darko, G. and Akoto, O. (2008):** Dietary intake of organophosphorus pesticide residues through vegetables from Kumasi, Ghana. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 46(12): 3703-3706.
- Elbaz, A.; Clavel, J.; Rathouz, P. J.; Moisan, F.; Galanaud, J. P.; Delemotte, B.; Alperovitch, A. and Tzourio, C. (2009):** Professional exposure to pesticides and Parkinson disease. *Annals of Neurology*, 66(4): 494–504.
- GadAlla, S. A.; Loutfy, N. M.; Shendy, A. H. and Ahmed, M. T. (2015):** Hazard index, a tool for a long term risk assessment

- of pesticide residues in some commodities, a pilot study. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 73(3): 985-991.
- GEMS/Foods (2012):** Global Environment Monitoring System-Food Contamination, Monitoring and Assessment Program (GEMS/Foods) Program of food safety and food aid, Geneva, Switzerland.
- Ghuniem, M. M.; Khorshed, M.; El-Safty, S.; Souaya, E. and Khalil, M. (2020):** Assessment of human health risk due to potentially toxic elements intake via consumption of Egyptian rice-based and wheat-based baby cereals. *International Journal of Environmental Analytical Chemistry*. DOI: 10.1080/03067319.2020.1817911.
- Góralczyk, K.; Wawrzyńczak, D. and Ludwicki, J. K. (2000):** Organochlorine pesticide residues in tea. *Roczniki Panstwowego Zakładu Higieny*, 51(2): 129-134.
- Gurusubramanian, G.; Rahman, A.; Sarmah, M.; Roy, S. and Bora, S. (2008):** Pesticide usage pattern in tea ecosystem, their retrospects and alternative measures. *Journal of Environmental Biology*, 29(6): 813-826.
- Jaggi, S.; Sood, C.; Kumar, V.; Ravindranath, S. D. and Shanker, A. (2001):** Leaching of Pesticide in Tea Brew. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 49 (11): 5479-5483.
- Magkos, F.; Arvaniti, F. and Zampelas, A. (2003):** Putting the safety of organic food into perspective. *Nutrition Research Reviews*, 16(2): 211-222.
- Kawahara, J.; Yoshinaga, J. and Yanagisawa, Y. (2007):** Dietary exposure to organophosphorus pesticides for young children in Tokyo and neighboring area. *Science of the Total Environment*, 378: 263-268.
- Kottiappan, M.; Dhanakodi, K.; Annamalai, S. and Anandhan, S. V. (2013):** Monitoring of pesticide residues in South Indian tea. *Environmental monitoring and assessment*, 185(8): 6413-6417.
- Osman, T. (2011):** Egypt on the Brink. In *Egypt on the Brink*. Yale University Press.
- Seenivasan, S. and Muraleedharan, N. N. (2011):** Survey on the pesticide residues in tea in south India. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 176(1-4):365-371.
- Son, H. K.; Kim, S. A.; Kang, J. H.; Chang, Y. S.; Park, S. K.; Lee, S. K.; Jacobs, D. R. and Lee, D. H. (2010):** Strong associations between low-dose organochlorine pesticides and type 2 diabetes in Korea. *Environment International*, 36(5): 410–414.
- Sushma, D.; Dipesh, R.; Lekhendra, T. and Ram, S. S. (2015):** A Review on Status of Pesticides Use in Nepal. In *Research Journal of Agriculture and Forestry Sciences*, 3(3):26-29.
- Winchester, P. D.; Huskins, J. and Ying, J. (2009):** Agrichemicals in surface water and birth defects in the United States. *Acta Paediatrica, International Journal of Paediatrics*, 98(4):664–669.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1651-2227.2008.01207.x>

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Royal jelly quantity means (Mg/Cups) under different diets and bars level within two successive years

Sherif, A. S. F; Marwa, B. M. Gomaa and Konper, H. M. A.

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 25 / 4 /2022

Accepted: 29 / 6 /2022

Keywords

Royal jelly, diets, bars, and acceptance of the grafted queen.

Abstract:

Recently there has been increasing attention to the use of natural food additives. Royal jelly is regarded as one of the most important honeybee products. It's produced from the hypopharyngeal and mandibular glands of 6-12 days old workers. As it acting an essential role in honeybee growth. The aim of this study is to examine some factors affecting royal jelly quantity production and acceptance percentages. The experiment consisted of 18 colonies that were used as replicators distributed as follows: Six replicates fed on substitute A (Skimmed soybean flour), six replicates fed on substitute B (Chickpeas flour + medical yeast) and six replicates fed on (Maize Pollen) (C) as a control. The first year has acceptance percentages that mean more than the second with non-significant differences. While the soybean showed acceptance percentages mean more than the other diets, with significant between soybean and other treatments were non-significant. Furthermore, the middle bar has acceptance percentages that mean more than the upper and lower bars with significant differences.

Introduction

Royal jelly is a proteinaceous secretion derived from the hypopharyngeal and mandibular glands of young worker bees. It is the only food fed to the queen throughout her lifetime and is also fed to all young larvae for the first three days after hatching. Royal jelly is being produced as a result of the grafting process and the acceptance of grafted queen cups is affected by the type of nutrition and queen cups introduced to the bees (Mohanny, 1999 and Zeedan, 2002).

There are several factors affecting royal jelly production. The age of transferred larvae is the most crucial factor (Sahinler and Kaftanoglu, 1997), feeding (Fuhai *et al.*, 1993), number of transferred queen cell cups (Van-Toor and Littlejohn, 1994) and Kutluca *et al.*, 1998), harvesting interval (Pahinler and Pahinler, 2002), whether, the colony is queenless or queenright and bee race (Van-Toor and Littlejohn, 1994).

The aim of this study is to examine some factors affecting royal

jelly quantity production and acceptance percentages.

Materials and methods

During the late summer season, this experiment was carried out (August and September) only in areas where natural pollen and nectar supplies are scarce for two years in a row, 2020 and 2021, processing substitutes be used under the craniolan hybrid.

1. Use of pollen substitute:

1.1. Substitute (A) skimmed soybean flour:

Ingredients: 400 grams of skimmed soybean + 300 grams of sugar powder + 100 grams of seedless paste + 100 grams of orange skin + 100 grams of Egyptian apple skin + 100 grams of carrots skin + 5 cm of linen Sowing oil. The components are mixed with sugar and fed to the experiment colonies at a rate of 100 grams each week. Plastic bags are used to wrap the replacement, with holes cut from the bottom and placed on the tops of the bee combs.

1.2. Substitute (B) chickpeas flour + medical yeast:

Ingredients: 400 grams of chickpeas + 350 grams of sugar powdered + 100 grams of seedless paste + 100 grams of medicinal yeast + 100 grams of orange skin + 100 grams of apple skin + 100 grams of carrot skin + 5 cm of cinnamon oil and be mixed with a sugar solution.

2. Use of pollen (Maize pollen) C control:

The maize pollen was supplied to the rearing colonies at a rate of 100 grams per colony per week on carton paper beneath the bee combs on the hive's floor. Pollen traps should be repeated on replacement A and B substitutes to guarantee that pollen is present in the region and to prevent the entry of bees carrying pollen from other sources or if a secondary source exists. During the trial time, sugar is administered (Pre-grafting stimulation and feeding after grafting). A sugar

solution with a concentration of 1kg sugar concentrate + 1.5 water. Half a liter of the solution was supplied to each colony.

3. Procedures:

In the experiment 18 colonies were used as replicators distributed as follows:

Six replicates of substitute A. Six replicates of substitute B. Six replicates of substitute C. Each breeding frame has 15 plastic cups and is processed with three screws at three distinct locations (Upper, middle, and bottom). Two hours before the grafting, the breeding frame is exposed to the breeding colony.

4. Statistical analysis:

Using the MSTAT-C (Version 2.10) computer application, all data were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), followed by Duncan's multiple range test to assess the differences between the derived means. Data related to the acceptance percentage of grafting larvae in rearing colonies and the quantity mean of the royal jelly production per cup were analyzed in a split-split randomized complete block design using three replicates for each treatment.

Results and discussion

Data in Table (1) presented the royal jelly quantity mean (mg/cup) from different diets under different bars level during two successive years (2020 and 2021) during late summer (August and September). During the first year, the highest royal jelly quantity means were (156, 134.5, and 153) recorded in the middle/upper bars dieted on soybean and lower on pollen respectively. However, the lowest royal jelly quantity means were (124.4, 155.6, and 147.2) recorded in the upper/lower bars dieted on chickpea and middle bars dieted on soybean respectively. During the second year, the highest royal jelly quantity means were (154.6, 150.2, and 130.9) recorded in the lower, middle and upper bars dieted on soybean, respectively. However, the lowest royal jelly quantity

means were (127.7, 142.3, and 139.6) recorded in the upper/lower and middle

bars dieted on chickpea and pollen respectively.

Table (1): The royal jelly quantity means (Mg/Cups) from different diets under different bars level during two successive years (2020 and 2021) during late summer (August and September).

Diet	First year				Second year				mean s.e±/ diet
	Upper	middle	Lower	AV± s.e	Upper	middle	Lower	AV± s.e	
Soybean	134.5	156	147.2	145.9±8.28	130.9	150.2	154.6	145.2±8.40	145.6±5.73 A
Chickpea	124.4	155.6	151.5	143.8±15.09	127.7	143.8	142.3	137.9±7.33	140.9±8.26 A
Pollen	130.4	155.8	153	146.4±13.36	129	139.6	142.8	137.1±6.78	141.8±7.61 A
Mean	129.8	155.8	150.6	145.4±7A	129.2	144.5	146.6	140.1±4.41A	142.7±4.16

Mean/ bars level upper 129.4±3.850 B
L.S.D value for years at 5 %=18.435
L.S.D value for level of bars at 5 %=5.645

middle 150.2±5.710 A lower 148.6±7.221 A
L.S.D value for different diets at 5 %=5.786

The results could be concluded that the first year has royal jelly quantity mean more than the second with non-significant differences. While the soybean showed royal jelly quantity mean more than the other diets, with non-significant differences between all diet's treatment. Moreover, the middle bar has a royal jelly quantity means more than the upper and lower bars with significant differences between upper and middle/lower, and non-significant differences between middle and lower bars.

Data in Table (2) presented the grafted queen cups acceptance percentage mean using different diets and bars levels for two successive years (2020 and 2021) in late summer (August and September). During the

first year, the highest acceptance percentage means were (76.9 - 70.7, and 66) recorded in the middle bar fed on pollen, lower and upper diet on soybean respectively. but the lowest acceptance percentage means were (60.4 - 67.2, and 70.7) recorded in the upper bar fed on pollen, lower bar fed on pollen, and lower bar fed on soybean respectively. During the second year, the highest acceptance percentage means were (70.6 - 70.5, and 65.3) recorded in the middle bar fed on pollen, lower soybean, and upper soybean respectively. but the lowest acceptance percentage means were (61.6 - 67.9, and 69.2) recorded in the upper and lower bars fed on pollen and middle bar fed on chickpea respectively.

Table (2): Grafted queen cups acceptance percentages Mean using different diets and bars level of two successive years (2020 and 2021) at late summer (August and September).

Diet	First year				Second year				Mean s.e±/ Diet
	Upper	Middle	Lower	AV± s.e	Upper	Middle	Lower	AV± s.e	
Soybean	66	70.7	70.7	70.8±3.86	65.3	69.8	70.5	68.5±2.04	69.7±2.19A
Chickpea	64.3	75.7	69.4	69.8±3.71	64.7	69.2	69	67.6±1.69	68.7±2.05AB
Pollen	60.4	76.9	67.2	68.2±5.16	61.6	70.6	67.9	66.7±3.00	67.4±2.92B
Mean	63.6	76.1	69.4	69.6±2.42A	63.95	69.8	69.1	67.6±1.32A	68.6±1.39

Mean/ bars level upper 63.7±1.28 C
L.S.D value for years at 5 %= 4.08
L.S.D value for level of bars at 5 %= 1.38

middle 73.0±2.18A lower 69.1±1.25 B
L.S.D value for different diets at 5 %= 0.93

The data in Figure (1) illustrated the differences between treatment and control in royal jelly quantity means (Mg/Cup) from Italian and crniolan hybrids with different diets within two successive years (2020 and 2021)

during late summer. The first year on soybean diet showed means more than the control in booth upper and middle bars (4.1 / 0.2) respectively. But on the chickpea diet, all bars (upper, middle, and lower) were less than control (-6 / -

0.2 / -1.5), respectively. The second year showed means more than control in soybean diet (1.9 / 10.6 / 11.8) in all bars (upper, middle, and lower) respectively. However, in the chickpea

diet the middle bar has a higher mean than the control (4.2). As both upper and lower bars have meant less than the control (-1.3 / -0.5), respectively.

The data in Figure (2) illustrated the differences between treatment and control in grafted queen cups acceptance percentage Mean using different diets and bars level for two successive years (2020 and 2021) in late summer. The first year showed means more than the control in booth diet soybean and chickpea (5.6 -3.9) in upper bars respectively. But the middle bars were less than the control (-1.2 / -6.2) in chickpea and soybean respectively. The lower bar showed

means more than control (3.5 – 2.2) soybean and chickpea, respectively.

The second year showed means more than the control in booth diet soybean and chickpea (3.7-3.1) respectively in the upper bar. However, the middle bars were less than the control (-1.4 & -0.8) chickpea and soybean respectively. While the lower bar showed means more than control (2.6 -1.1) for soybean and chickpea respectively.

The soybean showed acceptance percentages mean more than the other diets, with significance between soybean and other treatments being non-significant. Many researchers have supported these findings. Szymas and Przybyl (1995) mentioned how feeding with different pollen substitutes affected different tissues of the honeybee. Potato protein, soybean meal, yeast, low-fat powdered milk, powdered chicken eggs, extruded maize, and vitamin mix. The institute for the development of pharyngeal glands, fat body, and ovaries is similar to that of the bees fed with bee bread. The haemolymph protein and quality of royal jelly produced by honeybee colonies fed only on pollen substitutes compared with those of natural colonies. These pollen substitutes were chickpea, milk, and defatted soy flour. Total sugar amounts of crude protein and 10-hydroxy-2-decenoic acid varied slightly but within the reported range for natural royal jelly. Ideally, no differences were noted in the characters of queen bees reared on the royal jelly (Zaytoon, 2002).

Our results observed the middle bar has acceptance percentages that mean more than the upper and lower bars with significant differences. But In Brazil, the bar positions had an insignificant effect on the acceptance percentage of larvae. But the middle position resulted in the greater weight of royal jelly for queen cells than positions in front and close to the entrance and at the rear and far from the entrance. The higher percentage of larvae acceptances were associated with the greater weight of royal jelly for queen cells and heavier larvae produced in both genetics (Albarracín *et al.*, 2006). El-Barbary (2007) revealed that during summer the mean weight of queens that emerged from cells located in the middle position of the rearing frame was significantly heavier than

that produced on the edge position. Similar results were obtained during spring. The position at which the queen cell presented within the building colony has an effect on the weight of the resulted queens throughout various seasons of the year. The queen cells that were positioned in the middle areas of the rearing frame gave a number of queens with heavy weight in relative frequencies significantly higher than those resulting from cells presented on the edge areas of the rearing frame. The intermediate queen weight was significantly less during summer than those obtained during spring for the middle position. For the edge position, a little increase was recorded during summer than spring for the relative queen weight distribution during the summer and spring seasons. However, the lightest queens were frequented in a significant rate in the peripheral areas than in the middle ones it is, also noticed from these results that the frequency percentages of heavy queens were significantly higher during the summer season than those that occurred during the spring season.

The results of Abd Al-Fattah *et al.* (2003) are in agreement with our findings. They determined that the highest acceptance percentage occurred during summer. Significant difference was found between summer and other seasons. The lowest significant percentage appeared in winter. While moderate results for the acceptance larvae were noticed during the spring and autumn seasons with insignificant differences between them in the North Sinai region. Also, Genc *et al.* (2005) observed the maximum acceptance percentage was in dry grafting in July and grafting with the addition of royal jelly in July and August, respectively.

The highest percentage of accepted queen cells in the two years, 2002 & 2003 respectively obtained from colonies located in the Rasheed

region during the citrus flowering period. While the lowest percentage of accepted queen cells were recorded during the squash blooming period in Kafr EL-Sheikh region (Shawer *et al.*, 2007). Guler and Alpay (2005) found the mean acceptance percentage of *A. mellifera Carnica* was higher than *A. mellifera ligustica* grafted larvae from May to August. Later, Erdogan *et al.* (2017) reported that the average acceptance percentage was similar, but the amount of royal jelly per cell was significant in the Aegean ecotypes and Italian x Aegean crossbred honey bees, respectively. The differences between the colonies for the number of grafted larvae, percentage, and amount of royal jelly per cell were significant. As the number of grafted larvae increased, the rate of acceptance of colonies decreased, but the total royal jelly production of colonies increased. The Aegean ecotype was found to be suitable for royal jelly production under south Aegean region conditions. Here Figure (1) illustrated the differences between treatment and control in royal jelly quantity means (Mg/Cup) from Italian and crniolan hybrids with different diets within two successive years (2020 and 2021) during late summer. These results are in agreement with Saleh (1999), who stated that the crniolan race was better than the Italian race in royal jelly production. As the highest acceptance percentage in queenless colonies was in April. As the lowest in September. Ibrahim (2002) showed the total quantity of royal jelly produced by the colony was higher in queenless colonies than in queenright ones. Not only that but royal jelly production is also being affected by the bee race. Worker larvae grafted at the age of 12 hours were more acceptable and the queen cells gave more royal jelly than older ones. The best time for collecting royal jelly from queen cells

was 3 days after the grafting process (Khattab *et al.*, 1998).

The results could be concluded that the first year has acceptance percentages that mean more than the second with non-significant differences. While the soybean showed acceptance percentages mean more than the other diets with significant between soybean and chickpea/pollen, the differences between chickpea and pollen were non-significant. Moreover, the middle bar has acceptance percentages that mean more than the upper and lower bars with significant differences. The best acceptance percentage was recorded in the soybean diet. While the best bar level for acceptance percentage was the upper bar.

References

- Abd Al-Fattah, M.A.; El-Basiony M.N. and Mahfouz H.M. (2003):** Some environmental factors affecting the quantity of artificially reared queens (*Apis mellifera L.*) in North Sinai region. Egypt. L. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 28(8): 6407-6417.
- Albarracín, V.N.; Funari, S.R.C.; Arouco, E.M.R. and Orsi, R.O. (2006):** Acceptance of larvae from different genetic groups of *Apis mellifera* in queen bee production. Archivos Latinoamericanos de Producción Animal , 14:33–41.
- El-Barbary, N. A. (2007):** studies on some activities of honeybee colonies under the environmental conditions of Damitta region M.Sc . Thesis, Fac. Agric, Cairo University.
- Erdogan, A.; Koc, A. U. and Karacaoglu, M. (2017):** Effects of Aegean ecotype (*Apis mellifera anatoliaca*) and Italian

- (*Apis mellifera ligustica*) x Aegean crossbred honeybee colonies and a number of grafted larvae on royal jelly production. (Turkish). Harrantar mvegdabiliml eridergisi / Harran. Journal of Agric. and Food Science; 12(1):19 – 98.
- Fuhai, L.; Shibi, C.; Shengming, H. and Fuxiu, L. (1993):** The Study on Pollen Substitutes of Honeybees. Honeybee, Royal jelly, Environment, Edited Dept. of Beekeeping Technology, Bee Inst. CAAS, Beijing, China: 22-40.
- Genc, F.; Emsen, B. and Dodologlu, A. (2005):** Effects of rearing period and grafting method on the queen bee rearing. J. Appl. Anim. Res., 27: 45– 47.
- Guler, A. and Alpaya, H. (2005):** Reproductive characteristics of some honey bee (*Apis mellifera* L.) genotypes, J. Anim.Vet. Adv., 4:864 – 870.
- Ibrahim, Y. Y. M. (2002):** Studies on some activities of honeybee colonies under Giza city conditions. M.Sc. Thesis, Cairo University.
- Khattab, M. M.; El-Samny, M. A.; El-Berry, A. A. and Kassem, S. I. (1998):** Some factors affecting the commercial scale production of royal jelly secreted by honey bee (*Apis mellefera* L.) in Egypt. Annals of Agricultural Science, Moshtohor, 36 (3): 1959-1967.
- Kutluca, S.; Genç, F. and Dodolođlu, A. (1998):** Besleyici kolonilere verilen ana arı yüksüklerinin sayı ile hasat aralığı kolonilerin arı sütü verimine etkisi. Tr J. of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, 22: 363-369.
- Mohanny, K. M. (1999):** New treatments for increasing and improving the production of the honeybee colonies. M. Sc. Thesis, Fayoum, Cairo University.
- Sahinler, N. and Kaftanoglu, O. (1997):** Effects of feeding, age of the larvae, and queenlessness on the production of royal jelly. Bee products: Properties, Applications, and Apitherapy, 25: 173-178.
- Saleh, E. A. M. (1999):** Comparative study on the royal jelly in the 1st hybrid colonies of some bee races under the local environmental conditions. M.Sc. Thesis, Al-Azhar University.
- Shawer, M.B.; Taha, E.A.; Helal, R.M.Y. and El-Dakhakhni, T.N. (2007):** Effect of nectar and pollen flora on the rearing of honeybee queens. Conf. Environ. Between Protection and Pollution, Fac. Sci. Qassim Univ., Saudi Arabia, 18-20 Mar. pp.70.
- Szymas, B. and A. Przybyl (1995):** Zastosowanie bialka ziemniaka w zywieniu pszczoly miodnej (*Apis mellifera* L.) pszczeln. Zesz, nauk, 39: 49-53.
- Pahinler, N. and Pahinler, S. (2002):** Effects of the number of queen cells and harvesting interval on the acceptance rates of the larvae, royal jelly quality, and quantity. J. Anim. Vet. Advan., 3:120-122.
- Van-Toor, R.F. and Littlejohn, R.P. (1994):** Evaluation of hive management techniques in production of royal jelly by honey bees (*Apis mellifera*) in New Zealand. J. Apic. Res., 33: 160-166.
- Zaytoon, A. A. (2002):** Effects of feeding pollen substitutes on the royal jelly and haemolymph of honeybees. J. Agric. Sci.

Mansoura univ., 27(10): 7053-7063.

Zeedan, E. W. M. (2002): Studies on certain factors affecting production and quality of queen

honeybees (*Apis mellifera L.*) in Giza region. M.Sc. Thesis, Cairo University.

Estimation of damage and losses caused by different species of snails on certain crops at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate

Abo-Hashem, A.A.; Nadia, M. M. and Fatma, K. Khidr

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 28 /4 /2022

Accepted: 28 / 6 /2022

Keywords

Snails, damage, losses, vegetables, fruits, Kafr El-Sheikh and Egypt .

Abstract:

Different land snail species caused many problems to most of the economic plants. The presented study was carried out to estimate damage and losses caused by *Monacha cantiana* (Montagu) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) , *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae), *Succinea putries* (Gastropoda: Succineidae) and *Thipa pisana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) on Egyptian clover and some vegetable crops and fruits trees in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during the period from October 2019 to September 2020 seasons. Results revealed that, the main Reduction weight in clover plants by different levels of *Monacha cantiana* snails during spring 2021 were (76.3 , 45.5 , 47.5) for *M. cantiana* snails ,and (86.4 , 74.7 , 90.0) for *S. putris* snails in first ,second and third cut, respectively and loss percentages caused by artificial infesting levels ,i.e: 10,15,20,25 snail /level , beside control (Without infection) in first ,second and third cut were (60.5 ,64.0 ,68.4 , 74.6 %) , (57.1 , 60.0 ,69.4 ,74.2 %) , (64.1 ,73.4 , 81.3 , 78.1 %) for *M.cantiana* and (52.3 , 60.2 , 64.1 , 74.6 %) , (60.9 , 62.2 , 63.1 , 65 .7 %) ,(61.9 , 64.3 , 70.0 , 73.0 %) for *S. putris* snails ,respectively . On the other hand, *M. cantiana* and *T. pisana* caused damage in leaves of sweet orange and mandarin , percentage of reduction were 21.6 and 17.0% , respectively, *E. vermiculata* and *T.pisana* caused 9.3 % damage in apple leaves, while *M. cantiana* and *T.pisana* were caused loss percentages 18.7, 14.7 and 9,0 % for lettuce, cabbage leaves, and cucumber fruits, respectively.

Introduction

In Egypt, land snails become very important pests of many fruits, vegetables, field crops, and ornamental plants. Different species of terrestrial molluscs in different localities in the Delta region have become one of the most pests. These species cause damage to the majority of field crops, vegetables and fruit crops (Ismail,1997). Resulting in a serious

reduction in yield production of attacked crops (Kassab and Daoued, 1964; Bishara *et al.*, 1968; El-Okda,1984, El-Deeb *et al .*, 1996 , Asran,1999; Abd-El-Aal, 2001; Zedan *et al .*, 2005 and Abd-El-Maboud, 2008) .

The more succulent raw leafy vegetables, fruits, and buds were extraordinarily attacked in addition to lower damage when land mollusca

became abundant. These land mollusca leaves unpleasant tracks on the injured parts (El-Okda, 1980).

The present work aims to throw light on the situation and size damage of terrestrial gastropoda pests in the Northern and Eastern Delta regions.

Materials and methods

The ecological studies of land snails were conducted under field conditions at Abu-Abdalla village – Sedy Salem district, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate. In this respect, new plantations of field crops such as Egyptian clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum*), horticultural crops as sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*), mandarin (*Citrus clementina*) and apple (*Malus domestica*) in addition to vegetable crops as cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata*), lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) and cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) were chosen to estimate the damage under field conditions were run as the following:

1. Damage estimation in Egyptian clover:

During 2021 spring season, field experiments were carried out to estimate the damage caused by *Monacha cantiana* (Montagu) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) and *Succinea putres* (Gastropoda: Succineidae) on Egyptian clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) at Abu-Abdalla village. The area of (3 x3 m) was cultivated with clover, forty days after germination, and when plants were about 20 cm in length, they were reduced to 20 plants of almost similar size, six groups were caged with wire box (30 cm wide x 30 cm length x 50 cm high). The soil under cages was cleaned carefully from grass, snails, and snail clutches to obtain free –snail plants. The artificial infestation was induced with four levels of adult *M. cantiana* and *S. putres* (i.e., 10, 15, 20, and 25 adults), in addition to the cage was used as a check control unit without

snails. Each treatment was replicated 3 times. One month after infestation, fresh weight of shoots (First cut) was detected, this procedure was repeated two times after one month of cutting reduction percentage of fresh weight was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Damage \%} = \frac{\text{A.W. Control} - \text{A.W. Infestation}}{\text{A.W. Control}} \times 100$$

A.W. Control = Average weight of Control
A.W. Infestation = Average weight of Infestation

2. Damage estimation on different fruit trees:

The experiments were carried out in Sedy Salem district in one feddan orchard area cultivated with sweet orange, mandarin, and apple trees. Ten trees were randomly chosen to estimate leaves damage due to *M. cantiana*, *Thipa pisana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) and *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) snails. Each tree was divided into three parts, top middle, and bottom. Twenty leaves were randomly chosen and collected from each part and transported to the laboratory. The whole leaf and whole damage area were estimated and damage percentages were calculated according to the equation adopted by El-Deeb *et al.* (1985):

$$\text{Damage \%} = \frac{\text{Area damage leaf surface}}{\text{Whole area of leaf}} \times 100$$

3. Damage estimation on a different vegetable:

To estimate the damage caused by different species of snails in lettuce and cabbage, half karate cultivated with lettuce, cabbage and cucumber were chosen and divided into plots, ten leaves from each plot randomly were chosen, while cucumber fruits, 100 fruit were collected randomly. The damage caused by snails on fruits was considered a loss. Each treatment was repeated three times. Total area /leaf in

addition to eating areas by snails were determined by planimeter apparatus. In the case of cucumber fruits, percent damage was calculated using the following formula with slight modification, El-Deeb *et al.* (1990) :

$$\text{Damage \%} = \frac{\text{Total number of rasped fruits}}{\text{Total number of investigated fruits}} \times 100$$

Results and discussion

1. Estimation of damage caused by certain land snail species to different host plants:

Damage caused by *M. cantiana*, *S. putris*, *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata* against different hosts was estimated. Data in Table (1) show that infestation of Egyptian clover plants with different levels of *M. cantiana* and *S. putris* reduced clover fresh weight of variable values of reduction. At 10 snails damage levels were 60.5, 57.1 and 64.0 % at first cut, second and third cutting, respectively.

These values were gradually increased with the increase of infestation level to reach 74.6, 74.3, and 78.1 % for 25 snail level at first, second and third cutting, respectively. Average reduction rates were 66.9, 56.2, and 74.2 % at 10, 15, 20 and 25 snails /20 plants levels of infestation during the three cutting. Data in Table (2) show the reduction in Egyptian clover weight resulting from different infestation levels of *S. putris*. At 10 snails level, % reduction in fresh weight were 52.3, 60.9, and 61.9 % at first second and third cutting respectively. When the infestation increased to 25 snail/20 plant, %reduction in fresh shoots weight reached 74.6, 65.7 and 78.0 % and at first, second and third cutting, respectively.

From previous results, reduction caused by different levels in the two snail species infestation was changed from cutting to another. So, it increased in the first cut at any level of

infestation whereas on average respectively, percent of reduction values caused by all levels of infestation at the first, second, and third cuttings were 66.9, 56.2, and 74.2 % for *M. cantiana*, 62.9, 63.0 and 68.0 % for *S. putris*.

It is interesting to mention that the percentage of weight reduction of clover plants was higher in the third cutting compared to the other two cuttings. Zedan *et al.* (2005) found the mean reduction caused by *M. cartusiana* in fresh weight of shoots for three cutting of Egyptian clover were 38.22, 33.59 and 35.12 % and the general mean losses were 35.65 % while losses percentages were 10.9, 14.2 and 17.25 % in leaves of mandarin, cabbage and lettuce crops, respectively. Metwally *et al.* (2018) show, that the mean reduction caused by *Monacha* spp. in fresh weight of shoots for the cuttings of Egyptian clover were 24.15, 9.09, and 16.185 %, respectively, and the general mean loss was 16.476 %.

Table (1) : Reduction weight in clover plants by different levels of *Monacha cantiana* snails during spring 2021.

Level of infestation	First cut			Second cut			Third cut			L.S.D 0.05			
	Weight	Reduction	% Reduction	Weight	Reduction	% Reduction	Weight	Reduction	% Reduction		Weight	Reduction	% Reduction
10 snails	45	69	60.5	30	40.0	57.1	23.0	41	64.0	33.0	50.0	60.5	12.1
15 snails	41	73.0	64.0	8	42.0	60.0	17.0	47.0	73.4	29.0	54.0	65.8	6.7
20 snails	36	8.0	68.4	22	48.0	69.4	12.0	52.0	81.3	23.3	59.3	73.0	9.8
25 snails	29	85.0	4.6	18	52.0	74.3	14.0	50.0	78.1	20.3	62.3	75.7	7.2
Control	114			70			64.0						
Mean		76.3	66.9		45.5	56.2		47.5	74.2				

Table (2): Reduction weight in clover plants by different levels of *Succinea putris* snails during spring 2021.

Level of infestation	First cut			Second cut			Third cut			L.S.D 0.05			
	Weight	Reduction	% Reduction	Weight	Reduction	% Reduction	Weight	Reduction	% Reduction		Weight	Reduction	% Reduction
10 snails	65.8	72.2	52.3	50.2	76.4	60.9	48.0	78.0	61.9	54.8	76.0	58.4	9.8
15 snails	55.8	82.2	60.2	48.0	79.0	62.2	45.0	81.0	64.3	49.6	86.0	62.3	10.1
20 snails	49.6	88.4	64.1	46.8	80.2	63.1	38.0	88.0	70.0	44.8	35.3	65.7	12.3
25 snails	35	103	74.6	43.2	83.2	65.7	28.0	98.0	78.0	35.6	94.7	73.0	7.16
Control	138			127			126						
Mean		86.4	62.9		79.7	63.0		9.0	68.0				

2. Damage and losses estimation in different fruits and vegetable crops:

Data in Table (3) revealed that *T. pisana* and *M. cantiana* snails caused a loss in leaves of sweet orange trees 21.6 % and 17.0 % to mandarin leaves, while *E. vermiculata* snails on apple induced 9.3 % damage to leaves. On the other hand, Data in Table (4) showed that, *M. cantiana* and *T. pisana* snails were responsible of the damage in cucumber fruits 9.0 % while 21.6 %

in lettuce leaves. Also, the snails acted 17.2 % loss in cabbage leaves at Sedy Salem district. Asran (1999) recorded that, the attack by *Helix aspersa* Müller snails caused a slight damage to fruit leaves. The highest damage of snails was recorded in navel orange 9.3% followed by sour orange 8.4%, mandarin 7.3%, while the lowest were recorded on the leaves of seedless grape and pear, i.e 5.64 and 5.1 %, respectively.

Table (3) : Damage caused by certain land snails for different fruits crops.

Snail species	Plant hosts	Total area leaf (cm ²)	Damage area (cm ²)	%Reduction
<i>Monacha cantiana</i> <i>Theba pisana</i>	Sweet orange	22.16	4.78	21.6
<i>Monacha cantiana</i> <i>Theba pisana</i>	Mandarin	18.6	3.16	17.0
<i>Eobania vermiculata</i> <i>Monacha cantiana</i> <i>Theba pithana</i>	Apple leaves	33.6	3.12	9.3

Table (4) : Damage caused by *Monacha cantiana* and *Thipa pisana* snails for certain vegetable crops under field conditions.

Vegetable crops	Plant part	Total area /leaf (cm ²)	Damage area (cm ²)	% Reduction
Lettuce leaves	Leaves	15.7	2.9	18.7
Cabbage leaves	Leaves	56.4	8.3	14.7
Cucumber fruits	Leaves	10.0	0.9	9.0

References

- Abd-El-Aal, E.M. (2001):** Studies on certain land snails at Sharkia Governorate M.Sc.Thesis. Fac. Agre. Zagazig University.
- Abd-El-Maboud ,M.F.(2008):** Studies on plant parasitics snails in some desert regions in northern coastal zone.M. Sc .Thesis , Fac. of Agric., Al-Azhar University.
- Asran, F.D. (1999):** Studies on harmful terrestrial snails and their management on Egyptian agricultural lands. M. Sc. Thesis Institute. Environ. Stad. Res. Ain Shams University.
- Bishara ,S.I.; Hassan, M.S. and Kalliny, A.S.(1968):** Studies on some land snails injurious to agriculture in U.A.R. Rec. Zool. Bot. Afr., 77 (3-4):239-252.
- El-Deeb ,H.I. ; Asran, A.A. and Kuehnert, G. (1985):** Damage and losses caused by rodent to mandarin and certain varieties of orange. J.Agric. Mansoura Univer.,10 (12):564-566.

- El-Deeb, H.I., Ghamry,E.M.; El-Hawash , N. and Essa, N. H. (1996)** : Relative abundance of some land snails in certain Governorates of Egypt .J.Agric.Sci.Mansoura Univ.,21(8) :87-92.
- El-Deeb, H.I.; Asran, A.A; Kuehnert,G.and ElHalafawy,M.A. (1990)**:Preharvest damage and active burrows of rats in wheat fields. Agric.Res.Rev., Cairo.,28: 229-233.
- El-Okda, M.M.K.(1980)**: Land snails of economic importance on vegetable crops at Alexandria and neighbouring region Agric. Res. Rev.,58(1):79-85.
- El-Okda, M.M.K.(1984)**: Land mloousca infestation and chemical control in El-Ismaelia Governorate. Agri. Res. Rev.,58(1):79-82.
- Ismail, S.A. (1997)**: Ecology, biology and control of certain terrestrial snails infesting some vegetable and field crops in Sharkia Governorate. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Zagazik University.
- Kassab, A. and Daoud, H. (1964)**: Notes on the biology and control of land snail of economic importance in the U.A.R. Journal of Agricultural Research Review, Cairo,42:66-98.
- Metwally, A. M.; Mortada, M. M.;Al-Akraa, T. M. and Bashandy, A. S. (2018)**: Estimation of damage and losses caused by the prevalent species *Monacha* spp. on Egyptian clover, *Trifolium alexandrinum* (L.) under field conditions. 1st International Scientific Conference, Agriculture and Futuristic Challenges, Faculty of Agriculture-Cairo, Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt, April 10th – 12th, 1(I):381-388.
- Zedan, H.; Mortada ,M.M. and Awad, M.H.(2005)**: Survey , damage and losses caused by land snails on certain crops at Dakahlia and Demiatta Governorates . Egypt. J.Agric.Res.,83(2):699-676.

**Statistical study to investigate the effect of climate fluctuations and contamination of
bee products with pesticides on the change in beekeeping in Gharbia Governorate,
Egypt**

Tarek, A. Abd El Rahman¹ and Asmaa, A. Eissa²

¹Central Agricultural Pesticides Laboratory, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

²Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Gizeza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 2/ 5/2022

Accepted: 29 /6 /2022

Keywords

Honey bees,
beekeeping, problems,
pesticides, climate
change and Egypt.

Abstract:

The most severe concerns influencing the global marketing of bee goods are pesticide pollution of bee products and climate change. As a result, diagnostic questionnaires, formal interviews, and field notes were used to gather data on beekeepers' understanding of pesticide product contamination and safety measures for this questionnaire, as well as their knowledge of the effects of climate variability and change on beekeeping productivity. From April to September 2019, a survey of 100 beekeepers was undertaken in Egypt's Gharbia Governorate. According to the findings on pesticide pollution of bee products, 85 percent of the beekeepers in the survey were not informed of the dates of pesticide applications to crops near the hives. Only 3% of the beekeepers in the research are interested in learning the names of pesticides used in the areas around their apiaries. Similarly, 70% of them have no idea whether their items are pesticide-contaminated or not. On the other hand, almost 92 percent of beekeepers report a drop in the number of workers, which they ascribe to a variety of factors, including the use of pesticides. Only 8% of beekeepers tested for pesticide residues in their products before exporting them. The findings revealed that 80% of the beekeepers in the study had never heard of climate change. Only 20% of the beekeepers who took part in the study were interested in learning more about climate change. While only 6% of people are aware of the term "climate change," they predict problems for bees such as decreasing nectar, honey, and pollen, as well as a reduction in hive population in the autumn and early winter. Bee movement causes colony destruction. However, 14% of them do not believe there is a connection between beekeeping and climate change.

Introduction:

Approximately 9000 years ago, humans began harvesting honey from bees. A man gathering honey is depicted in a 7000 B.C. rock painting discovered near Valencia, Spain. Beekeeping and honey processing is

seen in drawings of Egyptian temples from around 2400 B.C. There are hints that honey was used to cure wounds in Egypt's oldest medical papyri, which dates from 1553-1550 BC. Honey and bee pollen grains were commended as a source of youthfulness and health in

ancient literature such as the Talmud, the Bible, scrolls from the East, ancient Greece, and Rome. Grease-honey-lint may be employed as a wound dressing on the Smith papyrus (c. 2,600–2,200 B.C.). “Honey is helpful for all rotten and hollow ulcers,” wrote Discords (About 50 A.D.). Aristotle (350 B.C.) used honey to cure wounds. The first hives in Egypt were cylinders made of clay that could be stacked. “Honey and pollen grains create warmth, clean wounds, and ulcers, soften stubborn ulcers of the lips, heal carbuncles and weeping sores,” Hippocrates stated. Galen, the renowned Roman physician, who prescribed it for a variety of poisonings and intestinal disorders, including gangrenous stomatitis, considered honey. Honey is a “Medicine for men,” according to the Koran's “The Bee” passage. As a poultice in the East, a mixture of honey and pollen grains was utilized (Hassan *et al.*, 2015).

Honey's sensory, chemical, physical, and microbiological qualities all have a role in determining its quality. Honey and other bee products are widely eaten as food and medicine, and contamination could pose major health risks (Eissa *et al.*, 2014). Pesticide and antibiotic contamination in agriculture is a difficult issue to solve. Honey and other bee products are widely eaten as food and medicine, and contamination could pose major health risks. Pesticides pollute honey and other bee-derived goods. Pesticide residues cause genetic changes and cellular disintegration, and antibiotics may increase the number of diseases that are resistant in humans and animals. Contaminated honey has been blamed for a number of cases of baby botulism. When honey is made from some plants, it can be hazardous. It is possible that ingesting honey without knowing where it comes from or how safe it is could be harmful (Noori *et al.*, 2012).

Pesticide residue in honeybee colonies has only been studied in cross-sectional research to date. Honey, beebread/pollen, wax, propolis, and bees have all been used to test residues. Most of them have only looked into a small number of pesticide residues, mostly those associated with honey bee pest control. Analytical methods capable of detecting a wide variety of pesticide residues found in the foraging habitat as well as those employed in colony management were used in several of the investigations.

On the other hand, estimates of climate change forecast upheavals in certain parts of the world a few decades from now, including advancing deserts, retreating ice caps, melting snow, shifting rainfall patterns, and a greater frequency of catastrophic climate events in general (Le Conte and Navajas, 2008).

Due to its effects on honeybees and their diseases, as well as the floral environment, climate is particularly crucial for the honey bee, *Apis mellifera* Linnaeus (Hymenoptera: Apidae), colonies' activity and productivity (Le Conte and Navajas, 2008). Climate change is currently seen as the greatest future concern because of its effects on all living organisms, including plants and their pollinators. However, few studies on the effects of climate change have been conducted. As evidenced by the review article (Abou-Shaara, 2016). Climate change is likely to have an impact on plant and bee distribution, for example (Le Conte and Navajas, 2008).

As a result, the goal of the research reported in this study is to determine the levels of beekeepers' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours regarding pesticide product contamination and safety practices, as well as to understand the effects of climate change on bee products in Egypt. We want to find out how much

(12%) represents merchants, while employees are represented by (11%) and the other (5 percent) (Table 1). The findings are consistent with those published by Al-Ghamdi *et al.* (2016), who stated that 138 people from 14 Arabian countries took part in the study. The majority of those who took part in the survey were between the ages of 31

and 45. (42.8 percent of the total). Most of them were also with a high educational level with a B.Sc. or higher degree (81.2% of the total) and 58.7% of them with experience of less than 10 years in beekeeping.

Table (1): Categories of different characteristics of respondents from beekeepers.

Criteria	Categories	%
Age	Less 30	0
	From 31-49	81
	From 50-60	15
	More than 60	4
Education level	Illiterate	8
	Intermediate education	28
	High qualified	64
Experience in beekeeping	Less than 5	16
	5–10	36
	More than 10	48
Relationship with beekeeping	Owner	44
	Responsible for apiaries	28
	Merchants	12
	Workers	11
	Others	5

3.2. Apiary types and production:

Production of bees and apiary type: All of the apiaries surveyed in the Governorate of Gharbia produce honey for local consumption. The number of apiary hives ranged from 50 to 500, with an average of 125. The study area's hives range in age from 1 to 20 years old. The average annual bee honey production in the research was 5 tons.

The crinoline bee strain has the highest percentage of bee strains in the research area's apiaries, with 58 percent, followed by the Italian bee strain at 24 percent and the Egyptian

bee strain at 18 percent. Over the course of one season, I discovered that alfalfa was the most common source of nectar, accounting for 88%, followed by camphor (36%), citrus (28%), and miscellaneous sources (6%).

Selling honeybees, which accounted for 60% of the income, was followed by selling parcels, which accounted for 56%, selling pollen and bee quarters, which accounted for 8%, and finally selling beeswax, which accounted for 7%, with the percentage of apiaries with all income streams being 12% (Table 2).

According to FAO (2016), the average honeybee output in the examined bees is consistent with the Arab Republic of Egypt's overall average. According to reports, natural honey comes in over 35 different varieties, with some of the more well-known being: Sunflower Honey - Hijazi Honey Alfalfa - Sweet Alfalfa Honey -

Apple Honey - Citrus Honey - Cotton Honey - Mint Honey (Alfalfa Honey).

In addition to bee production, which is considered the most important investment in the field of beekeeping in Egypt, bees produce six main products (Honey, pollen, wax, bee venom, royal jelly, and propolis). It wasn't until 2011 that Egypt began importing honey bees (Mostafa *et al.*, 2018).

Table (2): Bees production and apiary type of respondents from beekeepers.

Question	Variable	%
Is your apiary exported honeybee products?	No.	100
Apiary hives	Less 100	40
	From 101-500	48
	More than 500	12
Bee strain	The crinoline bee	58
	The Italian bee	24
	The Egyptian bee	18
Age of apiary	Less 1	20
	From 1-5	35
	More than 5	49
Nectar sources	Alfalfa source	88
	Camphor	36
	Citrus	28
	Other sources	6
Income sources	Selling honeybees	60
	Selling parcels	56
	Selling pollen	8
	Selling bee quarters,	8
	Selling beeswax	7
	All income sources	12

3.3. Types of beehive and bee products pollutants:

Diseases and pests that harm bees: The results in the apiaries analysed revealed that beekeepers

reported the emergence of Nosema in all apiaries, with brood diseases accounting for 88 percent of the apiaries studied, and other diseases accounting for 20%. Varroa mites were found in

80% of apiaries, with hornets accounting for 60% of the infestations (Table 3). Bee wolves and other pests infested 25% of the apiaries investigated, whereas wax moths infested 7% of the apiaries. The findings also revealed that treatment with formic acid and beta-cross against illnesses and pests, in general, had a positive effect on the majority of apiaries, with more than 85 percent losing nearly half of their colony.

Pesticides and threaten bees:
The study showed that the percentage of 52% of beekeepers under study do not recognize contamination of the beekeeper or its products with cross pollutants such as pesticides, while 48% of beekeepers know that there is a problem of contamination of the products of the bees. About 68% of the beekeepers in question believe that the cause of contamination of bee products is due to chemical contamination. Referring to beekeepers acknowledge the possibility of chemical contamination due to several reasons, including contamination by residual direct pesticides during the application, of 25%, while 32% of beekeepers refer to the reason for feeding bees on a general flower treatment with pesticides. Some beekeepers refer to the treatment of beehives with some

pesticides. Refer 33% of beekeepers to all the above and 10% of beekeepers refer for other reasons. About 92% of the beekeepers concerned observed the phenomenon of deficiency in workers, while 8% of the beekeepers concerned did not notice this phenomenon, and 20% of the beekeepers attributed the phenomenon to the use of pesticides in the areas surrounding the bees. While 80 % of the beekeepers attributed the phenomenon to different reasons.

About 85% of the beekeepers under study indicated that beekeepers are not notified of the date of application of pesticides in areas close to the beekeepers, while 15% of beekeepers indicated that they could be notified of the date of application. Of some beekeepers 3% mentioned some trade names of pesticides used in the areas close to the beekeepers under study (Table 4).

Review the life history and foraging behavior of bumblebees and honeybees and discuss how these traits may influence routes and levels of exposure. Overall, the major pesticide exposure routes for bumblebees and honeybees are similar. Furthermore, bumblebees may receive comparatively higher pesticide doses via contact or oral exposure (Spivak and Sheppard, 2019).

Table (3): Potential diseases and pests that threaten bees.

Diseases and pests	%
Nosema	100
Brood diseases	88
Bee paralysis Virus	5
Other diseases	20
Bee wolf	25
Varroa	80
Hornets	60
Wax moths	7
Other pests	25

Table (4): Pesticides and threaten bees.

Question	Variable	%
Did you know that there is a problem with contamination with bee products?	Yes	48
	No	52
The kind of contamination with bee products	Chemical	68
	Natural	32
Reasons of chemical contamination	Pesticide residues during application.	25
	Feeding bees on general flowers treatment with pesticides	32
	The treatment of beehives with some pesticides	33
	The other reasons	10
Note the phenomenon of the disappearance of worker bees	Yes	92
	No	8
Notification of the date of application of pesticides in the areas close to the bees under study	Yes	15
	No	85

Table (5) shows that six pesticide active ingredients were used in different farms in the areas close to the beekeepers under study. About 83.33% of the pesticides used belonged to the (WHO) toxicity class II (Moderately hazardous), with a few classes U (Unlikely to pose an acute hazard in normal use) recoded (16.66%). Insecticides were used by 66.66% of the farmers, followed by fungicides (16.66%), and acaricides (16.66 %), respectively.

About 50% of the pesticides used belonged to the neonicotinoid

Table (5): Classification of pesticides, toxicological class used in the fields close to the beekeepers under study.

Active Ingredient	WHO Toxicity Class (a *)	Classification	Registration Situation (b**)
Mancozeb	U	Dithiocarbamates	R
Amitraz	II	Amitraz	NR
Imidacloprid	II	Neonicotinoid	RUP
Acetamiprid	II	Neonicotinoid	RUP
Thiamethoxam	II	Neonicotinoid	RUP
Chlorpyrifos	II	Organophosphate	RUP

(a *): II: Moderately hazardous

U: Unlikely to pose an acute hazard in normal use

(b**): R: Registered

NR: Not registered

RUP : Restricted use of pesticides

3.4. The effect of climate change on bees and their products:

Climate change can influence honeybees at different levels. It can have a direct influence on honeybee

group, followed by the organophosphate group, amitraz, and dithiocarbamates group recoded 16.66 %. 5 active ingredients were registered in the state of Egypt, with a percentage value of 83.33%, unclouded 4 active ingredients Restricted use pesticides were 66.66%. In addition, the percentage of Not registered pesticides was 16.66%.

Only 8% of beekeepers were found to analyze pesticide residues in their products for export, while 92% of beekeepers do not analyze pesticide residues in their products.

behaviour and physiology. It can alter the quality of the floral environment and increase or reduce colony harvesting capacity and development. It can define new honeybee distribution

ranges and give rise to new competitive relationships among species and races, as well as among their parasites and pathogens. Beekeepers will also be obliged to change their apiculture methods. (Le Conte and Navajas, 2008).

The results showed that 80% of beekeepers under study did not know about the term climate change. While only 20% of beekeepers under study are interested in, knowing about climate change. 20% of beekeepers are divided into two parts, that 6% of beekeepers who know the term climate change refer to some phenomena that affect bees and

the result of climate changes, they expect problems for bees, such as reducing nectar, honey, and pollen besides decreasing of hive population during Autumn and early Winter. Migration of bees, damages colonies. On the other hand, 14% of beekeepers believe that there is no direct relationship between bees and their production with surrounding or expected climatic changes. All beekeepers under study have no vision or expectation of possible measures to address the effects of bees exposed to these climate changes (Table 6).

Table (6): The effect of climate change on bees and their products.

Question	Variable	%
The term climate change	Yes	20
	No	80
know the term climate change refers to some phenomena that affect bees	Yes	6
	No	14
vision or expectation of possible measures to address the effects of bees exposed to these climate changes	Yes	0
	No	100

It is recommended that use (IPM) system to minimize the use of pesticides, prevention of neonicotinoid group treatment near apiaries, thinking carefully about the use of pesticides, especially where plants are in flower. Ministry of Agriculture should help beekeepers to find a good strain that survives climatic changes, growing more flowers, and shrubs that provide nectar and pollen as food for bees and other pollinators (Eucalyptus is very useful). Providing a clean source of water for bees to take back to the hive, thinking carefully about the use of pesticides, especially where plants are in flower, the establishment of windbreaks and shelter around apiaries, ensuring sun shades in early summer, ensuring pollen substitute and sugar feeding during starvation. Beekeepers must learn and train on artificial insemination and molecular biology is a useful tool for measuring the genetic diversity of honey bee populations and

liking their adaptability to climatic changes and to different pathogens.

References

- Abou-Shaara H. F. (2016):** Expectations about the potential impacts of climate change on honey bee colonies in Egypt. *Journal of Apiculture*, 31(2) : 157-164 .
- Al-Ghamdi, A. A. ; Alsharhi, M. M. and Abou-Shaara, H. F. (2016):** Current Status of Beekeeping in the arabian countries and urgent needs for its development inferred from a socio-economic analysis. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 10 (2) : 87-98.
- Eissa, A. A.; Hassan, A. S. M. and Abd El Rahman, T. A. (2014):** Determination of total aflatoxins and carbamate pesticide residues in some bee honey samples using QuEChERS method and high performance liquid

- chromatography. Food and Public Health, 4(5): 209-213.
- FAO (2016):** <http://www.fao.org/faostat/ar/#data/QL>.
- Hassan, A. S.; Abd El Rahman, T. A. and Eissa, A. A. (2015):** Quantitative evaluation for some metal elements in honey from various countries. Agricultural Research Journal 52(3): 58 – 62 .
- Jallow, M.F.A.; Awadh, D.G.; Albaho, M.S.; Devi, V.Y. and Thomas, B.M. (2017):** Pesticide risk behaviors and factors influencing pesticide use among farmers in Kuwait. Sci. Total Environ., 574: 490–498.
- Le Conte, Y. and Navajas, M. (2008):** Climate change: Impact on honey bee populations and diseases. Revue scientifique et technique, 27(2): 499-510.
- Mostafa, M. S.; El-Agroudy, N. M.; Shafiq, F. A. and Hassan, M. B. E. (2018):** Economics of honeybee in Egypt. Middle East J. Appl. Sci., 8(3): 820-826.
- Noori, A.; Salom, K.; Al-Ghamdi, A. and Ansari, M. J. (2012):** Antibiotic, pesticide, and microbial contaminants of honey: Human Health Hazards. The Scientific World Journal. Volume Article ID 930849, p. 9.
- Spivak, M. and Sheppard, W. S. (2019):** Honey bee exposure to pesticides: a four-year nationwide study. www.mdpi.com/journal/insects

An examination of palatableness of some leaf plants utilizing two terrestrial snails in Egypt

Bashandy, A. S. and Awwad, M. H.

Department of Agricultural Zoology and Nematology, Faculty of Agric., Al-Azhar Univ., Cairo, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 8 / 5/2022

Accepted: 30/6 /2022

Keywords

Terrestrial snails, no-choice, free-choice, palatability and food consumption.

Abstract:

Land snails markedly *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) and *Theba pisana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) caused many problems to a great number of the economic plants in Egypt. So, the target of this study was to estimate the palatability and consumption ratio of snails invading twelve plants belonging to eight families by two methods: no-choice and free-choice feeding. Data displayed in no-choice feeding that cabbage and lettuce were the most palatable compared to other plants at 5.171 g and 3.763 g. But the lowest consumption leaves of Hibiscus and Swiss chards were 0.862 g and 0.473 g, for Land snails: *E. vermiculata*, respectively. Furthermore, for *T. pisana*, leaves of snow thistle were the most acceptable was 2.516 g, and leaves of spiny emex, and Strawberry disclosed the lowest palatableness rates which were 0.532g and 0.127g respectively, during intervals experimental. On the other hand, in free-choice feeding, berseem leaves showed the most preferred which was 6.829 g and 4.267 g for the two snails, *E. vermiculata* and *T. pisana*, respectively. Moreover, leaves of wheat and strawberry were the lowest consumption of *E. vermiculata*. But the lowest consumption of wheat recorded for *T. pisana* was during five days.

Introduction

Herbivorous pests such as terrestrial mollusks are pests for many plant species in different places in the world (Feldkamp, 2002). The damage to land Mollusca is caused in different ways, direct way by feeding on several plants such as field crops, orchards, and vegetables. While indirect ways as infection by bacteria,

fungi, and viruses due to the feeding of snails by scratching the plants (Lindqvist *et al.*, 2006).

The objective of this study is to assess the consumption and preference of selected food types between free-choice and no-choice by two terrestrial gastropods species: *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) and *Theba pisana*

(Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) under laboratory conditions.

Materials and methods

1. Tested snails:

Adult snails of *E. vermiculata* and *T. pisana* were collected by hand from *Citrus limon* trees during mid-March 2022 from Buhaira Governorate. Animals were put in transparent bags and transported to the laboratory of Zoology Agricultural and Nematology Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Al-Azhar University to be washed with fresh water (Godan, 1983 and Badawey, 2002).

2. Tested plants:

Test leaves for twelve plants regarding eight families which were Amaranthaceae: swiss chard; *Beta vulgaris* var. *cicla*, Cruciferae: cabbage; *Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata*, london rocket; *Sisymbrium Irio*, turnip; *Brassica rapa*, Compositae: chicory; *Cichorium intybus*, lettuce; *Lactuca sativa*, snow thistle; *Sonchus oleraceus* L., Gramineae: wheat; *Triticum aestivum*, Leguminosae: berseem clover Egyptian; *Trifolium alexandrinum*, Rosaceae: strawberry; *Fragaria* spp., and Malvaceae: hibiscus; *Malva sylvestris*, Polygonaceae: spiny emex; *Emax spovosis*.

3. Adaptation land snails:

For acclimatization, the snails were kept in glass cages (40×20×15) cm full of mixed soil (Clay: Sand) approximately (1:1) with suitable moisture and closed with a muslin cloth to avoid snail escaping (Before the start of the experiment, the soil was sterilized in the oven at a temperature of 150 °C for half an hour, then the soil was left to cool and then used) and fed on leave lettuce for two weeks under laboratory conditions at RH. 70% and Temp. 16.8 °C. Thirty healthy adult snails were chosen from each species for each replicate that was repeated three times. The animals were

starved for 48 hours before beginning the examination (Miller, *et al.*, 1988 and Shetaia, 2005).

4. Capability and daily consumption of snails:

The experiment was divided into two parts the first part for free-choice feeding and the second part for No-Choice feeding.

4.1. No-Choice feeding for land snails:

Sixty healthy animals were chosen for each treatment and then divided into three replicates each of 30 snails with sizes. A known weight from leaves plants was offered to snails in plastic jars (500 gm) and covered with a plastic lid with 15 holes for ventilation, for five successive days. The consumed mass of each foodstuff by snails was recorded daily, and jars were replenished (Eshra, 1997 and Al-Akraa *et al.*, 2010).

4.2. Free choice feeding for land snails:

Two groups of wooden boxes for each land snail species that used in the trial. Each group had nine boxes that were divided into three subgroups wooden boxes (50 × 40 × 20 cm) were used for four plants and contained mixed soil with 10 cm depth and 60% moisture. The first group was lettuce, hibiscus, Swiss chard, and strawberry, and the second group was berseem, wheat, cabbage, and turnip, and the third group was chicory, London rocket, snow thistle, and spiny emex. Each box contained 30 animals that were placed in the middle of the box. Around the snails was placed on the four sides of the box a known weight of fresh leaf samples of each plant. The food materials and their sides were altered daily to avoid a preference for a certain location (Mohamed, 2004). The tested leaf samples were changed daily after being weighed. The corrected reductions in weight by snail consumption were estimated for five successive days.

4.3. Data Analysis:

Data were statistically analyzed according to CoStat software version 6.311 using one-way ANOVA analysis and Duncan's multiple range test (0.05) to determine the significance of treatments (Duncan, 1955).

Results and discussion

The present study was conducted to know the most preferred plant leaves by two land snails by two methods.

1. No-choice feeding for land snails:

Data in Table (1) indicated that the average consumption weight of leaves of cabbage was the best susceptibility for *E. vermiculata* followed by lettuce and turnip with an average number of 5.171, 3.763, and 3.658 g after five days, but the Swiss chard, strawberry, berseem, and wheat were the lowest average consumption that was 0.473, 0.384, 0.365 and 1.47g, respectively. Furthermore, the average consumption of leaves weed was high for chicory followed by London rocket and snow thistle that was 3.178, 2.536, and 1.649 g. Therefore, the lowest average consumption of weeds; hibiscus, and spiny emex were 0.862g and 0.166 g after five days. Data in Table (2) revealed that at the average consumption weight of leaves of turnip was the most palatability food leaves for the white garden snail; *T. pisana* was 2.318g. Followed by cabbage, Swiss card, and lettuce were the moderate average consumption, which was 1.819, 1.793, and 1.722g. moreover, the leaves of berseem, wheat, and strawberry were the lowest average consumption that 0.589, 0.269, and 0.127g. besides, the most attractive leaves of weed were snow thistle and chicory. the average consumption for it is 2.516 and 1.906g. but the mean consumption of leaves of hibiscus and London rocket. The lowest consumption one was spiny emex which was 0.532g.

Ultimately, land snails; *E. vermiculata* exhibited the highest agreeable, and consumption rates leave of cabbage and lettuce were 5.171g and 3.763g. It was recorded that the lowest palatable and eating rates of leaves of hibiscus and Swiss chard were 0.862g and 0.473g. In addition, the land snails; *T. pisana* demonstrated that snow thistle was the most consumption and acceptability which was 2.516g. Besides, spiny emex and strawberry disclosed the lowest consumption and palatableness rates, which were 0.532g and .0127g. during intervals experimental.

2. Free choice feeding for land snails:

The statistical analysis of data in Table (3) showed that there was a significant difference between average weight consumption for land snails, *E. vermiculata*. The most consumption was lettuce and hibiscus that was 4.939, and 3.960g, respectively. On the contrary, data in Table (3) displayed the no-significant difference between the average consumption of weight plant leaves for land snails, *T. pisana*. But the meanest average consumption for hibiscus and lettuce was 2.714 and 2.581g, respectively. The lowest one was strawberry leaf consumption for two kinds of land snails that were used in the trial. The statistical analysis of data in Tables (3) and (4) appeared a significant difference between average weight consumption for two land snails. The most consumption was berseem leaves rate of 6.829g and 4.267g. the lowest consumption of wheat leaves was 1.148g and 0.606g for the two snails, respectively. There was statistical analysis showed significant differences in consumption of plant leaves in the third group of Tables (3) and (4). For *E. vermiculata*, the average consumption of chicory was 4.992g. But for *T. pisana* was 3.621, 3.341g, and 3.407g for chicory, snow thistle, and London rocket, respectively.

Further, the lowest consumption of spiny emex leaves was 1.628g and 1.370g, during five days.

Eventually, statistical analysis of data in Tables (3) and (4) appeared a significant difference in the rate of consumption of plant leaves. berseem showed the preferred and consumption leaves for the two snails. On the other hand, wheat and strawberry were indicated as the lowest consumption and palatability for land snails; *E. vermiculata*. on the contrary, land snails; *T. pisana* recorded the lowest acceptability and consumption of wheat during five days.

These outcomes concur with Bishara *et al.* (1968) found that the snail *Thepa* sp. fed mostly on Egyptian clover and somewhat on beans and rice. Also, El-Okda (1984) uncovered that the land snails, *Monacha* sp. also, *Oxychillus* sp. made high injury to the Egyptian clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) and broad leaf weeds. In addition, Chang (1991) announced that the new leaf plate structure lettuce was more like to land snail, *Cepeae nemoralis*, either under lab or field conditions. Too, Asran (1994) revealed that the day-to-day normal food consumption ranged from 0.005 to 0.026 g/day for the land snail *Helix aspersa*. Nakhla and Tadros (1995) found a huge food inclination of banana plants for *E. vermiculata*, banana plants, orange trees for *H. vestalis*, the weed, *Medicago polymorpha* for *T. pisana*, and orange trees for *Rumina decollate*. As well, Abd El-Hak (1997) showed that new leaves of lettuce were more liked for land snails; *Monacha* sp., and *Eabania* sp. followed by peas and cabbage while garden rocket leaves were the most reduced. Besides, Arafa (1997) displayed that the mean

consumption daily (mg/snail) of *Eobania* sp. for 7 days was 1.1, 1.2, 1.4, 1.3, 1.5, 1.4, and 1.9 mg/snail on lettuce, sweet peas, cabbage and nursery rocket, individually. Additionally, Eshra (1997) inferred that lettuce leaves were the most choice competed with cabbage leaves, fruits of carrot and squash fruits showed the least one. Moreover, Shoeib (1997) tracked down that *E. vermiculata* ate up Dahlia leaves more than cabbage and lettuce. But, Mahrous *et al.* (2002) detailed that cabbage and lettuce held onto the biggest quantities of *Monacha cartusiana* snails. While pepper, pea, and tomato pulled in lower numbers. Plus, Mohamed (2004 and 2016) showed that the land snail favored to cabbage and lettuce compared to other plants. Asran *et al.* (2016) appeared that *E. vermiculata* elected lettuce followed by squash, carrots, and potatoes. Bashandy (2018) observed that cabbage was the most palatable and had an average consumption rate of 0.552g, further London rocket and Snow thistle were the lowest consumption for it that 0.244g and 0.215g, for the march slug; *Deroceras leave*, respectively.

From this, we conclude that cabbage and lettuce, and other plants' leaves are more palatable to land snails compared to other plants. Some weeds are also preferable to terrestrial snails, which are considered alternative hosts in the absence of the most preferred crop. Therefore, we recommend the possibility of using cabbage and lettuce as snail-trapping plants in the field as one of the mechanical control methods for them. Also, those favorite weeds must be disposed of during the agricultural operations of the field.

Table (1): Consumption average of certain fresh leaves of vegetables and weeds for the land snail, *Eobania vermiculata* under laboratory conditions

Plants	Strawberry	Lettuce	Cabbage	Turnip	Swiss chard	Wheat	Berseem	Snow Thistle	Chicory	Spiny Emex	Hibiscus	London rocket
Consumption average/day	1 st	3.208	4.647	4.091	0.590	0.101	0.424	1.604	2.849	0.166	0.852	2.563
	2 nd	3.763	5.479	3.339	0.491	0.140	0.349	1.745	3.470	0.175	0.875	2.643
	3 rd	4.353	5.538	3.387	0.447	0.179	0.307	1.641	3.159	0.167	0.857	2.436
	4 th	3.728	5.019	3.817	0.365	0.168	0.398	1.607	3.232	0.157	0.862	2.503
	5 th	3.763	5.171	3.659	0.473	0.147	0.345	1.649	3.178	0.166	0.862	2.536
Mean	3.763 b	5.171 a	3.658 b	0.473 g	0.147 h	0.365 gh	1.649 e	3.178 c	0.166 h	0.862 f	2.536 d	

Means with the same letter are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$) according to Duncan's multiply range test. LSD 0.05 = 0.4298

Table (2): Consumption average of certain fresh leaves of vegetables and weeds for the land snail, *Theba pisana* under laboratory conditions

Plants	Strawberry	Lettuce	Cabbage	Turnip	Swiss chard	Wheat	Berseem	Snow Thistle	Chicory	Spiny Emex	Hibiscus	London rocket
Consumption average/day	1 st	1.550	2.113	2.771	1.968	0.313	0.696	3.695	2.608	0.692	1.259	1.414
	2 nd	1.786	1.990	1.739	1.936	0.370	0.588	2.390	1.833	0.427	1.276	1.299
	3 rd	1.881	1.720	2.889	1.639	0.252	0.569	2.266	1.947	0.607	1.115	1.142
	4 th	1.701	1.260	2.656	1.858	0.210	0.539	2.115	2.020	0.499	1.444	1.086
	5 th	1.690	2.013	1.536	1.565	0.204	0.554	2.118	1.126	0.435	1.583	1.044
Mean	1.722 cd	1.819 c	2.318 ab	1.793 c	0.269 f	0.589 f	2.516 a	1.906 bc	0.532 f	1.335 de	1.197 e	

Means with the same letter are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$) according to Duncan's multiply range test. LSD 0.05 = 0.4298

Table (3): Daily consumption of some plant leaves by *Eobania vermiculata* under laboratory conditions.

Plants	Group I					Group II					Group III				
	Strawberry	Lettuce	Hibiscus	Swiss Chard	Cabbage	Turnip	Wheat	Berseem	Snow Thistle	Chicory	Spiny Emex	London Rocket			
Consumption average (g)/ day	1.044	10.687	8.611	7.856	6.346	4.724	1.021	7.124	6.397	10.631	1.986	2.093			
1 st	1.796	3.499	4.633	3.238	4.293	6.382	1.104	6.228	4.368	4.514	1.559	4.902			
2 nd	1.120	3.756	3.085	1.992	3.137	1.504	1.183	7.908	2.761	2.825	1.556	5.349			
3 rd	0.352	3.665	1.153	1.701	2.972	1.865	1.453	5.262	2.023	3.274	1.481	3.979			
4 th	1.210	3.032	2.320	2.860	2.667	1.456	0.980	7.624	2.145	3.720	1.557	2.602			
5 th	1.104 b	4.928 a	3.960 ab	3.529 ab	3.883 b	3.186 b	1.148 c	6.829 a	3.539 ab	4.992 a	1.628 b	3.785 ab			
Mean															
LSD 0.05		3.372				1.956				2.701					
Mean	1.104 c	4.928 ab	3.960 bc	3.529 bc	3.883 bc	3.186 bc	1.148 c	6.829 a	3.539 bc	4.993 ab	1.628 c	3.785 bc			

Means with the same letter are not significantly different (p<0.05) according to Duncan's multiply range test. LSD 0.05 = 2.586

Table (4): Daily consumption of some plant leaves by *Theba pisana* under laboratory conditions.

Plants	Group I					Group II					Group III				
	Strawberry	Lettuce	Hibiscus	Swiss Chard	Cabbage	Turnip	Wheat	Berseem	Snow Thistle	Chicory	Spiny emex	London Rocket			
Consumption average (g)/ day	2.168	3.963	1.971	0.663	7.591	3.27	0.979	3.953	3.224	3.397	1.188	3.073			
1 st	2.892	4.622	5.001	1.464	3.457	4.569	0.75	3.421	4.256	4.954	1.481	3.673			
2 nd	2.08	1.047	3.284	1.086	2.076	1.45	0.199	4.416	3.099	4.059	1.348	4.621			
3 rd	1.499	0.977	1.638	0.994	1.725	1.161	0.155	4.907	3.49	3.216	1.726	2.791			
4 th	1.061	2.297	1.679	0.977	1.909	0.874	0.949	4.637	2.635	2.479	1.108	2.879			
5 th	1.940 a	2.581 a	2.714 a	1.037 a	3.351 a	2.265 ab	0.606 b	4.267 a	3.341 a	3.621 a	1.37 b	3.407 a			
Mean															
LSD 0.05		1.561				2.025				0.916					
Mean	1.94 bcd	2.581 abc	2.715 abc	1.037 cd	3.352 ab	2.265 bc	0.606 d	4.267 a	3.341 ab	3.621 ab	1.3702 cd	3.4074 ab			

Means with the same letter are not significantly different (p<0.05) according to Duncan's multiply range test. LSD 0.05 = 1.487

Acknowledgment

We gratefully thank Prof. Dr. Abd El-Sattar Mohamed Metwally, Department of Dept. of Agric. Zoology and Nematology, Faculty of Agric. Cairo, Al-Azhar University, Egypt - for critical reading of the manuscript and providing constructive comments.

References

- Abd El-Hak, A.I.A. (1997):** Studies on some land molluscs at Sharkia Governorate. M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Al-Azhar University.
- Al-Akraa, T. M. M.; El-Danasory, M. A. and Mohafez, M. A. (2010):** Food preference and food consumption of some land snails under laboratory conditions. J. of Plant Protection and Pathology, 1 (4): 189 – 193.
- Arafa, A. A. (1997):** Studies on some land mollusca at Sharkia Governorate. M.Sc. Thesis Fac. Agric., Al -Azhar University.
- Asran, A.A.; Keshta, T.M.S.; Mohamed, Gh. R. ; Ali, M. A. and Abou-Hashem, A.A. (2016):** Preference of brown garden snails *Eobania vermiculata* to some vegetables under laboratory conditions. Egypt. J. of Appl. Sci., 31(1): 1-8.
- Asran, F.D. (1994):** Studies on harmful terrestrial snails and their management on Egyptian agricultural lands. M.Sc. Thesis, Agric., Ain Shams University.
- Badawey, M. A. (2002):** Studies on glassy clover snail and possibility of its calcium and protein components to be used for nutrition, M.Sc. Thesis in Agric. Zoology and Nematology, Al-Azhar University.
- Bashandy, A. S. (2018):** Studies on Some Terrestrial Gastropods Injurious to Some Important Crops at Giza Governorate. Ph.D. thesis, Agric. Zoology and Nematology, Fac. of Agric., Al-Azhar University.
- Bishara, S. I.; Hassan, M. S. and Kalling, A. S. (1968):** Studies on some land snails injurious to agriculture in U.A.R. Rev. Zool., Bot. Afr., LXXVII (3-4): 239 – 252.
- Chang, H.W. (1991):** Food preference of the land snail *Cepeae nemoralis* in a north American population. Dept. of Biol. Ind. Univ., 24(1-2): 107-114.
- Duncan, D. B. (1955):** Multiple ranges and multiple F-test. Biometrics, 11: 1-41.
- El-Okda, M. M. (1984):** Land mollusca infestation and chemical control in El-Ismailaia Governorate. Agric. Res. Rev., 62(1): 87-92.
- Eshra. E. H. H. (1997):** Ecological and biological studies on land snails associated with some important economic crops. M.Sc. Thesis Fac. Agric., Al-Azhar University .
- Feldkamp, S. (2002):** Modern biology. Holt, Rinhart and Winston, USA., pp. 725.
- Godan, D. (1983):** Pests and Slugs: Biology and Control. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York. pp. 445.
- Lindqvist, I.; Lindqvist, B.; Setala, H. and Tiilikala, K. (2006):** Brich oil reppels slugs and snails, AFPP. 3rd international conference on non-chemical crop protection method, 13- 15 Lille France.
- Mahrous, M.H.; Ibrahim, M.H. and Abd El-Aal, E.M. (2002):**

- Occurrence, population density and importance value of land snails infesting different crops at Sharkia Governorate. Zagazig J. Agric. Res., 29(2): 613-629.
- Miller, E.; Swails, G. ; Swails, D. ; Olson, F. and Staten, R. T. (1988):** White Garden snail *Theba pisana* (Muller): Efficacy of selected bait and spray able molluscicides. J. Agric. Entomology., 5(30): 189-197.
- Mohamed, G. R. (2016):** Susceptibility and Consumption Rates of *Monacha cartusiana* and *Helicella vestalis* Land Snails to Certain Plants. Middle East Journal of Applied Sciences, 6(4): 896-899.
- Mohamed, G. R. (2004):** Ecological and biological studies on some species of snails. M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. of Agric. Mosh., Zagazig University.
- Nakhla, J. M. and Tadros, A.W. (1995):** Studies on the seasonal abundance of land snails on date palm shoots in Sharkia Governorate. Egypt. J. Res., 73 (2): 347-355.
- Shetaia, Z. S. (2005):** Integrated control of land snail's pests in the fields of Sharkia Governorate. Ph.D. Thesis in Agric. Zoology and Nematology, Al-Azhar University.
- Shoeib, M. A. (1997):** Ecological studies on some common snail species and their control in Ismailia Governorate. M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agric. Suez Canal University.

Instruction to authors

Original articles are full length papers describing original research. The paper should not exceed 15 pages of double-spaced typed text (including abstract, tables, figures and references). One double-spaced typed page contains approximately 300-350 words. Reviews are normally by invitation from the Editor-in-Chief. However, authors are encouraged to submit a tentative title and a table of contents of a proposed review for consideration. These reviews should not exceed 20 pages of double-spaced typed text (Including abstract, tables, figures and references). Scientific notes and short communications to the Editor usually on matters of general concern to plant protection, are welcome but should not exceed 4 typed pages. The decision to publish submitted scientific notes and short communications with the Editor-in-Chief.

Manuscripts should be written in clear, concise, and grammatically correct English. Submission of a manuscript implies: that the work described has not been published before; that it is not under consideration for publication anywhere else. Authors should submit their manuscripts online. To the Email: shaabanabdrabou59@yahoo.com

Manuscript preparation

Title: The title should reflect the most important aspects of the article, in a preferably concise form of not more than 150 characters and spaces. By-line The authors' names should be followed by affiliations and addresses.

Abstracts are required for all the manuscripts. They should be typed in one paragraph and limited to max.150- 200 words. The abstract should not contain any undefined abbreviations or unspecified references.

Keywords: Most important words of paper. Should be from 4 to 6 words.

Text: Main text should contain (1) an Introduction (2) a Material and Methods (3) a Results (4) a Discussion (5) a Conclusion (6) a References

Text formatting: Use a normal, plain font (e.g., 14 Point Times Roman) for text.

Abbreviations should be defined at first mention and used consistently thereafter. Authors should adhere to the rules governing scientific nomenclature to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. All biotica (crops, plants, insects, birds, mammals, etc.) should be identified by their scientific names including authors (and Order: Family) when the English term is first used in the main text, with the exception of common domestic plants and animals. Scientific names should be as follows: In the Title only give the Latin name but No authority or (Order: Family); in the Abstract all Latin names should be accompanied with the correct authority and with (Order: Family); in addition, at the first mention in the body of the text - and only then - these data should be given; authority, the order, family, should also go in the Key Words list.

Footnotes

Footnotes on the title page are not given reference symbols. Footnotes to the text are numbered consecutively; those to tables should be indicated by superscript lower-case letters (or asterisks for significance values and other statistical data).

References

The list of References should only include works that are cited in the text and that have been published or accepted for publication. Personal communications and unpublished works should only be mentioned in the text.

Cite references in the text by name and year in parentheses. Some examples:

- Negotiation research spans many disciplines (Abd-Rabou, 1996).
- This result was later contradicted (Simmons and Abd-Rabou, 2009).
- This effect has been widely studied (Abd-Rabou, 1998; Simmons *et al.*, 2002; Evans and Abd-Rabou, 2005 and Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2005).

List style

Reference list entries should be alphabetized by the last names of the first author of each work.

Journal article

Abd-Rabou, S. (1998): The efficacy of indigenous parasitoids in the biological control of *Siphoninus phillyreae* (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) on pomegranate in Egypt. Pan-Pacific Entomologists, 74 (3): 169-173.

Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005): Two new species and additional records of Egyptian Aphelinidae. Zootaxa, 833:1-7.

Simmons, A. and Abd-Rabou, S. (2006): Whitefly populations in vegetables crops with different fertilizers. 52nd Annual meeting of the South Carolina Entomological Society, Mc Cormick, Sc., October 19-20.

Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A. M. (2012): *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) whitefly as a pest in Egypt. Advances In Agricultural Research In Egypt, 10 (1): 1-82.

Figures Line-drawing should be clear and of high quality. Cite all figures in numerical order in the manuscript.

Tables The title should be self-explanatory and include enough information so that each table is intelligible without reference to the text or other tables. The title should summarize the information presented in the table without repeating the subheadings. Subheadings should be brief, nonstandard ones can be explained in footnotes. Cite tables in numerical order in the manuscript. Information presented in a table should agree with that in the text.